

Kingmakers

life's gateway to the stars

A review of the maximal potential access of life as we know it on Earth, to the extrasolar environment, leading to interrogations regarding the role of humans, and to the need of an urgent moratorium.

Key words: directed panspermia; extrasolar planets; extremophile microorganisms; extraterrestrial life; life in space; terraforming planets; habitability; search for life; water; exoplanets; habitable zones; meti; ethics; space ethics; morals, COSPAR; Breakthrough Starshot; Arch Mission Foundation; Genesis project.

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To Celeste, Elio and Kenya.

Special thanks to Clementine Bacri, Pierre Léna, Eric Vernier.

Context:

Signals

No regulation is addressing the sending of messages to space.

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Such messages, provided these are being picked up, bear the potential of dramatically impacting us, but also the biospheres we would be interacting with.

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Since 1979, about 30 of such transmissions happened, conveying messages produced by small groups of people in the name of mankind, to targets closer and closer to us, some such as GJ273b, a potentially habitable exoplanet, so close that a feedback could theoretically be received within the years to come.

Lifeforms

The committee for space research (COSPAR), edits the policy on planetary protection spacefaring nations do refer to. When targeted celestial bodies are not of direct interest for understanding the process of chemical evolution or the origin of life, “no protection of such bodies is warranted, and no planetary protection requirements are imposed.”

When life is suspected, up to 20.000 spores are allowed per lander.

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According to the biological understanding, given appropriate conditions, a single of these microorganism, should it be autotroph, bears the potentiality of successfully seeding an entire world, leading to the birth of a biosphere. As demonstrated by the near term capability of the human species when considering projects such as Breakthrough Starshot, and when considering ideologic propositions such as the one being formulated in the Genesis project proposed by Claudius Gros, a developing biosphere may lead to species, such as ours, embodying the ambition and the capability to engage in the massive seeding of extrasolar worlds.

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In 2019, a probe intentionally carrying stowaway dehydrated, revivable organisms named tardigrades, crashed on the moon. No legal issues were raised. No pursuits were undertaken against the initiator of this project, claiming himself to be the “first space pirate”

Abstract

Projects such as Breakthrough Starshot are being funded, working on swarms of miniaturized interstellar probes. The probes are to be pushed by laser beams whose operation could be detected from a quarter of the stars within our galaxy, with technologies similar to ours. Meanwhile, since 2016, the Arch Mission Foundation launches miniaturized time capsules to space carrying data, microorganisms and human DNA, allegedly capable of surviving billions of years. In this context, the possibilities of intentional, incidental or malevolent consequences beyond the solar system are explored.

In game design theory, a kingmaker situation happens when a player, while unable to win the game, may decide who is to win. The thesis developed here is that humans are soon to reach such a situation. Considering cosmological scales, the human species is not likely to survive long. It will evolve, speciate, or go extinct. Still, via the spread of earth originated lifeforms towards interstellar targets, or by signaling to preexisting extrasolar lifeforms, humans may fundamentally condition the future. Via time capsules, signaling devices and probes capable of interstellar range, humans do hold, or are soon to hold, a kingmaker position regarding life as we know it on Earth, and its extrasolar advent.

By its multiple implications, the kingmaker decision is conditioning the future of humans, of life as we know it, and of life as we do not know it, should it exist. As such, the amount of impacted experiences and sensibilities is considerable. More, as the expansion of known and potential lifeforms is impacted, so is the share of the universe, potentially transformed by those lifeforms. Ultimately, some mass being converted to energy, even the gravitational binding holding things together could be altered, leading to an accelerated dislocation of the accessible universe. Encompassing these considerations, the scope of the kingmaker decision is eventually limited by the laws of physics. This limit, the event horizon, is consecutive to the expansion of the universe and to a maximal speed for causation. Amounting for a maximum of 3% of our possibly infinite universe, the volume comprehending the potentially impacted elements stands as very significant: a hundred billion billion billion times larger ($1e+29$) than what lies within the volume of our solar system.

The kingmaker decision is considered inescapable, underassessed, tractable and urgent, leading to the conclusion that involvement on the topic is valuable. Given the moral uncertainties, it is proposed to build up an informed moral decision, while doing our best to save time and opportunities. A conservative stance is proposed advocating the need for a responsible approach to space, considering proper values beyond the one attributed to humans. The creation of an international ethical panel on the question is advocated, along with the enforcement of a temporary moratorium banning extrasolar access by all means, including probes, time capsules and signals.

Abstract (FRENCH)

Des projets de sondes interstellaires miniaturisées, comme celui de Breakthrough Starshot, sont financés et en développement. Le fonctionnement des faisceaux laser de 100 GW, propulsant ces sondes, pourrait être détecté depuis le quart des étoiles de la galaxie, avec des technologies similaires aux nôtres. En parallèle, depuis 2016, l'Arch Mission Foundation lance dans l'espace des capsules temporelles miniaturisées contenant des données, des micro-organismes et de l'ADN humain, potentiellement capables de survivre des milliards d'années. Dans ce contexte, les possibilités de conséquences intentionnelles, accidentelles ou malveillantes au-delà du système solaire sont explorées.

Une situation de faiseur de roi se produit lorsqu'un joueur, incapable de gagner la partie, peut décider qui va gagner. La thèse est ici développée que les humains sont proches d'une telle situation. Évoluant, et soumise à des risques existentiels, l'espèce humaine ne devrait pas avoir une survie notable en comparaison des temporalités cosmologiques. Pourtant, via la propagation de formes de vie d'origine terrestre vers des cibles interstellaires, ou en se signalant auprès de formes de vie extrasolaires préexistantes, les humains peuvent fondamentalement conditionner l'avenir. Via des capsules temporelles, des dispositifs de signalisation et des sondes capables de portée interstellaire, les humains détiennent, ou vont bientôt tenir, une position de faiseur de roi concernant la vie telle que nous la connaissons sur Terre.

Par ses multiples implications, la décision en jeu conditionne l'avenir des humains, de la vie telle que nous la connaissons et de la vie telle que nous ne la connaissons pas, si elle existe. En tant que tel, la quantité d'expériences et de sensibilités impactées est considérable. De plus, à mesure que l'expansion des formes de vie est affectée, la part de l'univers transformée par ces formes de vie l'est également. Via la conversion d'une part de masse en énergie, l'univers accessible pourrait en outre voir sa dislocation s'accélérer. La portée de la décision en jeu est limitée par les lois de la physique. Cette limite, l'horizon des événements, est consécutive à l'expansion de l'univers et à une vitesse maximale de la causalité. Représentant au maximum de 3% de notre univers, le volume comprenant les éléments impactés est très significatif: cent milliards de milliards de milliards de fois plus grand (10^{29}) que ce qui se trouve dans le volume de notre système solaire.

Notre décision concernant ce rôle dans l'expansion interstellaire de la vie telle que nous la connaissons sur Terre est considérée comme inéluctable, sous-évaluée, traitable et urgente, ce qui conduit à la conclusion que l'implication sur le sujet est précieuse. Compte tenu des incertitudes morales, il est proposé de construire une décision morale éclairée, tout en faisant de notre mieux pour conserver du temps et des opportunités. Une position conservatrice est proposée préconisant une approche éthique de l'espace, tenant compte au-delà de l'Homme, de la valeur propre de la biodiversité extrasolaire potentielle. La création d'un panel international d'éthique sur la question est préconisée, ainsi que l'application d'un moratoire temporaire concernant les activités ayant une portée dépassant le système solaire, ceci comprenant les sondes, les capsules temporelles et les signaux.

Introduction

Life as we know it on Earth

Earth's surface, atmosphere and oceans support a 100km thick biosphere, weighing ~2000 gigatons, made of constantly evolving biologic systems, accounting for a thousand of billion billion billion of diverse, individual, encapsulated and interconnected lifeforms¹. Representing ~80% of this biomass, photoautotrophs organisms collect and reroute ~10% of the total inbound solar energy, chemically reassembling raw materials into animated, self-maintaining biological structures where potential energy is being stored². Via the trophic networks, these feed the remaining ~20%. Respiration, photosynthesis and trophic chains are constantly cycling the materials of the planet's surface, oceans and atmosphere³, to such an extent that geological conformation, chemical composition, energy and element cycles cannot be understood independently of the study of the evolution of biodiversity⁴. Earth thermodynamic equilibrium itself is intertwined with the activity and distribution of living organisms⁵.

Then, matter is displaced and processed by lifeforms, beyond metabolic activity and trophic chain. Human activity alone is as such estimated to have processed and displaced around 30 trillion tons of matter: ten times the mass of all living organisms⁶. This shall be understood as the lower bound of the global physical impact, such processes being not exclusively human.

Intertwined with metabolic and physical activity, is then the variety of sensibilities, which do interact, and produce an amount of experiences, processes, representations, and cultures, not limited to the human share of these⁷, and consequently extremely difficult to apprehend.

According to the current paradigm, biodiversity does deeply interact with the chemical structure, energy flow and element cycles on the surface of Earth, through metabolic activities and direct physical movement, while producing an interacting assembly of individual experiences, which may not be reduced to their human component.

¹ [1] ([Bar-On et al. 2018](#)) [The biomass distribution on Earth](#). (1e30, 1e31 when counting viruses)

² Estimated 8%, with an annual inbound solar energy of 4.19E+21J/yr, and an annual gross photosynthetic energy production of 4.19E+21J/yr, with a 1% global photosynthetic efficiency.

³ The equivalent atmospheric carbon is cycled, every six years. See ([A.1](#)) [life, physically](#)

⁴ [2] ([Lovelock and Margulis 1974](#)) [...] [The Gaia hypothesis](#)

⁵ [IPCC AR4 9-1 : Understanding and Attributing Climate Change](#)

⁶ [3] ([Zalasiewicz et al. 2017](#)) [Scale and diversity of the physical technosphere...](#)

⁷ Stress is experienced at the monocellular level. Animals demonstrate sensibility. Trees demonstrate some form of intelligence. Octopuses demonstrate general intelligence, Mammals demonstrate various levels of consciousness, languages and cultures...

Out there ?

The question is raised of the possibility and of the potential impact, of the expansion of such a transformative action, beyond the Solar System. Life led on Earth to significant changes in energy flow, material cycles and chemical composition, along with the creation of interacting experiences. Could life propagate out of the Solar System ? What then could it do to the remaining of the universe ?

This question is of uttermost importance, because we humans are the ones likely to propagate life out there. Science fiction ? Not really. Terraformation and life-seeding projects⁸ are well implanted in a human imagination filled with galactic empires. Within this context, some ethical standpoints, amongst which biotist ethic, panbiotist ethic⁹, and extrapolations from the biblical injunction to colonize the world¹⁰, do indeed advocate it is the purpose of humanity to spread life to space^{11,12}. Then, humans are developing miniaturized probes and signaling systems, capable of intergalactic range, alongside spacebound, lightweight, billion year capable time capsules. We will see that humans are likely to be empowered with probes and signals, capable of intergalactic range. When these will be operational, those probes and signals have a probability to carry life-related elements, or even lifeforms. Incidentally, intentionally, or malevolently, humans may soon offer life as we experience it on Earth, a potential impact extending well beyond the limits of the Solar System.

Capability

Miniaturised probes are being developed, targeting to reach 20% of the speed of light¹³. While the purpose is the exploration of the nearby stellar system, Alpha centauri, investigation shows that such probes have thanks to their nearly relativistic speed, the potential of ranging not only to every single star in the Milky Way, but to escape our galaxy gravitational limits and the ones of the clusters we belong to, to reach out to hundreds of millions galaxies ($2e+8$): billions of billions of planets in the habitable zone of their stars ($5e+18$), according to the current paradigm

⁸ [4] [\(Gros, 2016\) Developing Ecospheres on Transiently Habitable Planets: The Genesis Project](#)

⁹ [5] [\(Mautner, 2009\) life-centered ethics, and the human future in space](#)

¹⁰ Genesis: 1:26 & 1:9

¹¹ [4] [\(Gros, 2016\) Developing Ecospheres on Transiently Habitable Planets: The Genesis Project.](#)

¹² [6] <http://www.panspermia-society.com/>

¹³ [7] [\(Breakthrough Initiatives 2020\) Starshot.](#)

¹⁴.While at this speed, Alpha Centauri is only twenty years away, reaching places billions of light-years away takes time. This is where a parallel ongoing development has a peculiar importance: ultrasilient time capsules are being developed, precisely to address such challenges, capable of preserving information for an advertised duration of $10e+14$ years¹⁵: a duration bigger than the age of the universe itself.

And, there is more: to accelerate the probes to such speed, the concept relies on a ground based laser array, pushing the probes via solar sails. This 100Gw laser, once operational, will have a signaling power sufficient to be seen with the naked eye, from any of most proximate 70 millions stellar systems. With a telescope such as our VLT (Very Large Telescope), the operations of this laser could be detected from extragalactic distances: ten thousand galaxies, hundreds of thousands of billions of potentially habitable planets, wherefrom our signals could be decoded.¹⁶

The diffusion of Life-related elements such as information coded in time capsules, or deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA), may have exponential consequences, provided a substrate is available capable of decoding and expressing the transmitted information or elements. This relates the possibility of the impact via those means, to the question of the existence of extraterrestrial life. But extrasolar life is not a required media when considering that more and more autotrophic microorganisms, or even animals capable of stasis such as tardigrades, are found to be capable to survive time, pressures, temperatures and impact deceleration, compatible with a space journey, a 10.000G acceleration on launch, and a crash at destination.

So if this is reality, humans are about to be empowered with probes, time capsules and signals, soon capable of intergalactic range, onboard which, lifeforms, or life-related elements, might be embarked, with the potential for seeding a share of the accessible universe, deploying a transformative action at this scale.

Kingmakers

Oxford English Dictionary defines a kingmaker as the one who makes or sets up kings. The thesis defended here is that humans are right now at an extremely specific moment in their history where they hold a kingmaker position regarding the potential impact of life as we know it,

¹⁴ Author's calculation as per model developed in *Annex IV Scope*.

¹⁵ [8] ([Arch Mission Foundation, 2020](#)) [5D Optical Memory Crystal](#).

¹⁶ Author's evaluation as per model developed in *Annex IV Scope*.

to astronomical scale. According to our proposition, we may decide about releasing life to space, which has impacts regarding the magnitude of its potential flourishing, and on its odds of survival. The below work is dedicated to the investigation of the logic and hypotheses leading to the establishment of this assertion, and to the evaluation, of the orders of magnitude of the maximal environment concerned by our possible decision as kingmakers. Considerations justifying the conservative handling of the question are then proposed, which leads to the proposition of an enforced global moratorium until an informed moral decision is being built, and agreed on.

Outline

Underlined words, are hyperlinks to the considered sections

I) PREREQUISITES

In this section are proposed a word of caution, and a toolkit for non-specialists to go through this work, addressing motivation (tool n°1), large numbers (tool n°2), scales (tool n°3), exponential growth (tool n°4), life as an identity, (tool n°5) before focussing on units (tool n°6).

II) ARGUMENTATION

So as to encompass the subtleties of the possible impacts, working definitions are proposed in A) Working definitions, which will allow us to formulate the reasoning and identify the hypotheses. After adopting a working definition for “life”, we will distinguish life and life-related elements. First order life, fully autonomous, will be differentiated from higher order life, which require specific substrates to express itself. Eventually, life will be considered to possibly behold a material or informational nature.

A precise definition will then be adopted for the Solar System boundaries, which will be defined timewise and spacewise, allowing for a clarification of what “extrasolar” means.

From this, in B) Logical Paths the paths connecting the hypotheses to the assertion of humans being kingmakers regarding life as we know it on Earth, are detailed, found to be cross-related, and a conditional scheme is proposed and analysed, leading to the conclusion of a robust reasoning, leading from the determined hypotheses, to the conclusion of a strong path

to the kingmaker position. (Twelves supporting hypotheses are identified, that will be further explored in the section III) HYPOTHESES.)

In C) On the explored Magnitude, the exploration of the magnitude of maximal impacts is discussed, detailing a large tolerance to errors in the evaluation, and to underachievements in the projected technological paths. The transformative action at stake is then envisioned, with consequences ranging to the matter content and to the dynamic of expansion of the accessible universe. (The evaluation of magnitude will be detailed in IV) EVALUATION, and is supported by the work in Annex IV Scope).

III) HYPOTHESES, chapter 1: Life

To investigate the hypotheses related to life, in A) Life, physically we set up a macroscopic representation of what is life as we know it, through the exploration of the vast amount of matter it interacts with on Earth.

In B) Life, interpreted we identify key properties, critical to the understanding of its potential impact, should it become extrasolar. After considerations on the question of defining life (B.1), our characterisation takes place (B.2), and is developed from its constitutive parameters: the properties of self-reproduction (B.3), energy transduction and resource conversion (B.4), evolution, (B.5) and requirement for a substrate (B.6).

Being then tooled with a sharper representation, in C) The resistance of life, we investigate the hypotheses regarding space resistance (C.1), time resistance (C.2), and interstellar resistance of lifeforms, (C.3) which participate to the conclusion that life might gain an extrasolar access through the involvement of humans.

In D) Life as we do not know it, the question of characterising life as we do not know it, is addressed (D.1), and the hypothesis on the existence of extraterrestrial intelligence is detailed, and assessed (D.2).

III) HYPOTHESES, chapter 2: Extrasolar access

In this second chapter of section III) HYPOTHESES, we investigate the hypotheses related to the natural and historical access of life, as we know it on Earth, to the extrasolar space.

Natural access refers to the extrasolar access that is occurring naturally, naturally here meaning excluding the influence of humans.

Historical access refers to the integration of this natural access over the past history, to which is added the integrated access due to human intervention. Historical access refers as such to every possible access life as we know it on earth might have had along its history, including through the media of human intervention.

To proceed with the evaluation of these hypotheses we start by defining some physical boundaries for the solar system, relevant to our question of the diffusion of life, in A) The Solar System, physically, before envisioning it in B) Habitability, from the perspective of the evolution of its habitable zone, when defined as per the liquid water criteria.

The boundary of the extrasolar space being defined, a consideration is given in C) Isolation, onto what isolation means regarding the evolution of biologic systems, allowing us to consider the Solar System as a relevant unit to discuss with.

The hypothesis on natural then historical access are then investigated, in D) Hypothesis on natural access and E) Hypothesis on historical access, supported by the work presented in annex *Annex III History of extrasolar Access*, to conclude that the critical hypotheses of no natural nor historical access, may be considered as reasonably robust.

III) HYPOTHESES, chapter 3: Humans

This last chapter of section III) HYPOTHESES, is exploring the conditions considered as mainly relating to humans. To proceed, we first in (A) Breakthrough-type technologies, detail what is referred to when considering near term technologies, considered realistically operating 20 years ahead. Amongst these, we focus on the perspectives offered by Breakthrough Starshot model (A.1), and reinforced by recent strategies for photo gravitational assist, amongst which a proposition by the author (A.2). The potential signaling power of the Breakthrough Starshot laser is envisioned (A.3). Cost considerations, and contextual elements, (A.4) will give us an indication on the reasonability of Breakthrough Starshot goals (A.5), informing our hypotheses regarding interstellar signaling an interstellar travel, the question of time capsules being settled by the achievements of the Arch Mission Foundation. (A.6). The technological hypotheses being considered as realistic in the near term, the critical question of incidental, intentional, or malevolent boarding of life or life-related elements, onto our soon to come probes, signals or time capsules, is addressed, in B) Hypothesis on Boarding. The question of the survival of civilisation is investigated, in C) Hypotheses on technological civilisation, and the

reversibility by humans means, of the process of incidentally, intentionally or malevolently seeding a world is questioned in D) Hypothesis on irreversibility.

IV) EVALUATION

Section IV) EVALUATION, will start with A) a finite accessible space, by bounding the question of the potential impacts. The scope of the kingmaker decision, defined as the maximal set of things possibly impacted by the decision, is then envisioned in B) An existential choice, leading to the consideration that the kingmaker decision is existential¹⁷, not only to humans, but to life as we know it on Earth, and to the potential extraterrestrial biodiversity, should it exist. A synthesis of the work detailed in *Annex IV Scope* is then proposed, in C) A significant magnitude, where the maximal set of things possibly impacted by the decision, are estimated numerically, and considered very significant. When an existential decision, potentially impacting such a wide environment, is to be taken, time is valuable for a proper assessment to happen. In D) The universe flowing away, considerations are shared regarding the ongoing losses of opportunities inherent to the constant expansion of the universe, and the relative urgency of this decision. In E), the impossibility is of exponential growth, the limits of our finite, accessible environment, are demonstrated ad absurdum, before strategies for compensating for the losses of opportunities are discussed, in F) Compensating for the loss of opportunity.

V) OBJECTIONS

Section V, Objections, is trying to address some of these, starting with general consideration regarding A) Flaws in the logic, B), Issues with hypotheses, and C) the choice of exploring the maximal set of impacted elements. In D), Errors and imprecision in the proposed evaluation are addressed, before E) the assumption of a continuous spread is challenged, and defended.

VI) DISCUSSION

After precisising in A) Kingmaking the relation the human species may have to its kingmaking position, we propose, in B) Empowerment, to consider that we hold some control, and as such have some responsibility over this situation we now are aware of, arguing in C) Moral imperative, that the existential considerations and magnitude at stake leads to the moral

¹⁷ Oxford languages defines existential as “relating to existence”. In this discussion, something will be considered as existential to something else when the first conditions the existence or absence of the later.

obligation of trying to act in perspective. In D) Cause election, an utilitarian approach is used, to conclude that personal involvement on the question might be worthwhile, the question being tractable, important and widely underassessed. In E) Moral uncertainty, the issue of being incapable of a moral conclusion on the topic is addressed, and a conservative approach is proposed, of a course of action allowing for the minimisation of the potential damage, the time for a moral decision to develop.

VII) SYNTHESIS

VIII) CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

IX) BIBLIOGRAPHY

Annexes

Because one of the most important elements is the realisation of the odds at stake, this exploration will proceed parallelly with the development of a simple, understandable model of the possibilities, providing us with orders of magnitude of the possible consequences of what is happening now. The details of the construction of these models have been considered as irrelevant to the main reasoning, and are consequently addressed in annexes:

Annex I, Solar System, is addressing the question of defining the Solar System in adequation with the reflexion regarding the expansion of life.

Annex II De Sitter Model develops a constant expansion model allowing to easily estimate elements within reach as a function of the initial speed of the transmission or travel.

Annex III History of extrasolar Access, is investigating the potential impact life on Earth might have had historically out of the Solar System.

Annex IV Scope, proposes numerical estimations for the elements potentially impacted by the decision humans may or may not take regarding the extrasolar advent of life.

Annex V Future Work is addressing the proposed directions of research and actions, to yield the largest progress on the question addressed in Kingmakers life's gateway to the stars.

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List of units

yr - year	ly - light-year	pc - parsec, 1 pc = 3.26ly
Kyr - thousand years	Kyr - thousand light-year	AU - astronomical units, 1AU = 63241ly
Myr - million years	Myr - million light-year	kps - kilometers per second
Gyr - billion year	Gyr - billion light-year	%c - percentage of the speed of light
		J - joules

For improved readability of the orders of magnitude, scientific notation is using eX as the symbol for 10^x. As example, 3x10⁹ is noted 3e9, 3e+9, or 3e+09.

List of symbols

Underlined text is referring to hypotheses identified in *II.B) Logical paths*. The referred hypotheses are clickable hyperlinks to the sections of the document the hypotheses are addressed. Example: [hypothesis on time resistance](#)

Used at the stage of the evaluation of the scope of the decision, opportunities, defined as sets of circumstances where the potential extrasolar impacts are evaluated, are noted as:

Ω - generic symbol for opportunities: points at which maximal potential impacts are evaluated.

Ω 2020 - point of evaluation as per 2020

Ω 2020 ex man - ibid, excluding the contribution of humans

Ω 2040 - as per Breakthrough type technologies¹⁸

Ω ∞ - unlimited technological development, physical limits

ΩHistorical - the set of historical opportunities

¹⁸ For an introduction read the abstract of: [9] ([Parkin 2018](#)) [The Breakthrough Starshot system model](#).

Used at the stage of the evaluation of the history of potential impact

S[∞]- stellar systems below event horizon

ETI[∞]- potential stellar systems containing extraterrestrial intelligence below event horizon

ET[∞] - potential stellar systems containing extraterrestrial life below event horizon

nETI - potentially impacted stellar systems containing extraterrestrial intelligence

nET - potentially impacted stellar systems containing extraterrestrial life

Used in presented formulas

c - speed of light in the void: 300.000kps

v_0 - initial speed

v_e - ejection speed, speed above which an object may escape a gravitational attraction

v_{∞} - hyperbolic excess speed, eventually reached when escaping a gravitational attraction

M_{\odot} - solar mass, approximated to $2e30$ kg

L_{\odot} - solar luminosity, approximated to $1.2e34$ J/year

H - Hubble constant, approximated to $H= 74$ km/s/Mpc.

σ_{nom} - nominal surfacic mass, of a graphene lightsail: 8.6×10^{-4} gram m^{-2}

List of abbreviations

DNA deoxyribonucleic acid

ET - extraterrestrial

ETI - extraterrestrial intelligence

GWP - gross world product

HVS - high velocity star

HZ - habitable zone

ISS - International Space Station

METI - messaging to extraterrestrial intelligence

NASA National Aeronautics and Space Administration

RNA ribonucleic acid

SETI - search for extraterrestrial intelligence

SKA - Square Kilometer Array

SOI - sphere of influence

GLOSSARY

Key concepts are provided for reference, by alphabetical order.

Quoted elements in this glossary, are sourced from *Oxford Languages* dictionary¹⁹

Breakthrough-type technologies: In this discussion, we use the Breakthrough Starshot project, promising laser propelled probes traveling at 20%*c* within a generation²⁰, light sails allowing 20%*c* on long range trajectories²¹, without the support of a laser²², and the already prototyped Arch Mission Foundation time capsules, lasting 10e14yr²³, as references for near future technologies. These technologies, considered possibly mature 20 years ahead, are referred to as Breakthrough-type, or near-term technologies.

Causation: constitutive of causality (“the relationship between cause and effect”), causation is “the action of causing something”. As such, it relates to the process that permits causality to happen. Causation exclusively exists when a possible process relates the cause and effect. Special relativity limits the speed of all processes to the speed of light. Causality being dependent on causation, it is limited to the environments within which processes may happen below the speed of light. The expansion of the universe, whose impacts are detailed in *Annex II, de Sitter model*, limits such processes to a physical distance called the event horizon. In this discussion, causal fracturation will be envisioned, between parts of space that become causally separated, due to the expansion of the universe. Assessing the scope of the decision humans may make regarding the diffusion of life, the consequences are ultimately limited by physics to this event horizon, which may be understood as a physical limit to causality with reference to humans as a cause.

Demiurgic species

¹⁹ [10] ([Oxford Languages 2020](#)) *Oxford Languages* dictionary was selected considering the authoritative impact it now has onto the shared representations of google search users (92% of searches are on google, and *Oxford Languages* is the dictionary used by google to propose definitions following search requests).

²⁰ [9] ([Parkin 2018](#)) [The Breakthrough Starshot system model](#),

&[11] ([Lubin 2016](#)) [Implications of Directed Energy for SETI](#),

²¹ Detailed III.E) [Strategies for photo gravitational assist](#)

²² [12] ([Heller et al. 2017](#)) [Optimized trajectories to the nearest stars...](#)

&[13] ([Heller and Hippke 2017](#)) [Deceleration of High-velocity Interstellar Photon Sails...](#)

²³ [14] ([Arch Mission Foundation, 2020](#)) [5D Optical Memory Crystal](#).

In this discussion, a demiurgic species is a species amongst which some individuals are pursuing the goal, for any given reason, to achieve the widest possible seeding of life (sometime referred to as universal directed panspermia), to the maximal possible amount of stellar systems, and which have some capability to do so.

Existential: Oxford languages defines existential as “relating to existence”. In this discussion, something will be considered as existencial to something else when the first conditions the existence or absence of the later.

Exponential growth: something is exponentially growing when its quantity is growing in proportion to its current quantity. Populations of lifeforms, self-reproducing in unlimited environments, with unrestricted resources, tend to experience exponential growth, the population of each generation being multiplied by a basic reproduction rate, moderated by a possible death rate in the meantime. For an intuitive grasp on exponential growth, refer to *Prerequisites, Tool n°4*, and, in the context of living organisms, to *III) Life, B.3. Self Reproduction*

humans

By humans, we here refer to the 7.8 billion of highly intelligent primates calling themselves humans, today on earth, their ascendance and their descendance, up to the blurry distance in time where ascendants and descendants do not qualify as humans anymore. A good proxy for the estimation of this distance in the past is the distinction we today make between humans and chimps, which are definitely not considered as humans. The last common ancestor between humans and chimps being dated to exist 7 million years ago²⁴, we may consider that those 7 million years are a safe upper boundary for the past distance in time beyond which the ancestors of today's humans are not humans anymore. The distance in the future beyond which the descendants of humans are no more humans is to our perspective impossible to estimate. The sole element we might have a grasp on is the speed at which evolution is going: accounting for the fact that genetic engineering allows for a new mean of evolution, we may only hypothesize that evolution will go faster in the future, due to genetic engineering, and consequently, that 7 million years in the future is a safe upper boundary to the moment the descendants of humans are no longer humans.

²⁴ [15] [\(Kumar et al.2017\) TimeTree: A Resource for Timelines, Timetrees, and Divergence Times](#)

Kingmaker: Oxford English Dictionary defines a kingmaker as “One who makes or sets up kings”. In game design theory, a kingmaker situation is one where one of the players, while unable to win the game, is given the power to decide who is to win. The thesis defended here is that humans hold a kingmaker position regarding the potential impact of life as we know it, to astronomical scale. It is proposed that due to evolution and existential risks, humanity will not have a significant survival time, when compared to cosmological times, while it may decide upon the diffusion of life, something which is conditioning the survival and expansion to astronomical scales, of life as we know it.

Life: In the proposed argumentation, life refers to anything “evolving, self-reproducing, transducing energy and converting its substrate”. As such, lifeforms may experience exponential growth, and transduce energy while converting their substrate, up to the exhaustion of the limiting resources to be converted, or the lack of energy.

Life (as we know it on Earth): refers to what is known on Earth, to bear the above properties. In this essay, we propose to adopt the perspective of life as we know it, consequently to the absence of relevance of the concept of species over long durations, developed in *Prerequisites, tool n°5*

Life (orders of life): life is called first order or autonomous when the considered substrate is materials, unprocessed by another form of life. This distinction is important because the earlier presence of life is unnecessary for 1st order life orders to possibly have an exponential growth. Life is called higher order, substrate based or dependent when the required substrate is being or has been produced by another life form. This distinction is important because the earlier presence of life is a necessity for higher orders of life to possibly have an exponential growth.

Life-related elements: life-related elements refer to parts or bits of life, such as bits of organism, genus or code, which miss one of the properties of life (evolving, self-reproducing, energy transducing, substrate conversion), but might acquire full life properties through evolution or the integration with other life forms. This distinction is important because life-related elements are not capable of self reproducing when alone, and may hence not undertake an exponential growth. life-related elements may acquire the missing properties through evolution,

which takes time, or through engineering from a preexisting intelligent life form, which requires the given life form to pre-exist.

Life (material and informational) life, or life-related elements, may behold a material or informational nature. From the adopted definition, organisms, viruses, are material forms of life. Ideas, computer viruses, or simulated life,²⁵ are of informational nature. Fragments of DNA are material life-related elements, while DNA sequences are informational life-related elements. This distinction is important because informational life or life-related Elements may travel on signals, while material life or life-related elements require a massive vector to travel

Massive and non massive: see *Transmission* in this glossary

Opportunity: *Oxford Languages* proposes “an opportunity is a time or set of circumstances that makes it possible to do something.” In this work, opportunities are considered as a set of circumstances at a moment in time, where the potential impacts constitutive of the scope of the decision humans may take or not take from their kingmaker position, are evaluated. Those evaluation points are noted **ΩHistorical**, **Ω2020**, **Ω2020 ex man**, **Ω2040** and **Ω∞**, and referred to in plain text as historical opportunities, opportunities in 2020, opportunities in 2020 excluding the influence of humans, opportunities in 2040 and maximal opportunities.

Near-term: in this discussion, near-term signifies possible within 20 years. See *Breakthrough-type technologies* in this glossary

Paradigm: In our context, a paradigm refers to “the world view underlying the theories and methodology of a particular scientific subject”.

Currently, the paradigm in cosmology, we do refer to in this work, is the lambda, cold dark matter model (Λ CDM) model, of an universe in expansion parameterized by a cosmological constant Λ , containing ordinary matter, and cold dark matter. The Λ CDM model is also referred to as the standard model of cosmology, or as the concordance cosmology. This model, of a universe starting with a singularity called the big bang, built on general relativity, is the simplest one accounting for the observed redshift of distant galaxies, for a distribution of matter in the

²⁵ [16] (Bedau 2007) [ARTIFICIAL LIFE A-Life Artificial Life simulations](#)

universe coherent with the observations, and with the observed cosmic microwave background. The expansion of the universe forecasted for future times, may be approximated by a constant expansion model, the de Sitter model, extensively used in this work for the estimation of horizons and space within reach, and detailed in *Annex I, de Sitter model*.

Scope: The scope of something is “the extent of the area or subject matter that something deals with or to which it is relevant.” In this discussion we attempt to assess the scope of the decision humans may or may not take from their kingmaker position. As such, the scope of the considered decision is the maximal set of things potentially impacted by it.

Sustainable: is sustainable, something “able to be maintained at a certain rate or level”. In the context of this discussion, are considered sustainable processes that do not impair their own existence: as such, as demonstrated ad absurdum, constant growth is unsustainable in our finite accessible universe.

Technological civilisation:

In our context, a technical civilisation is a civilisation within which, the technologies referred to as breakthrough type technologies (see *breakthrough type*, this glossary), are considered as near-term.

Transmission, transmitters (Massive, non-massive): Transmission is “the action or process of transmitting something.” Transmission happens over time, or over time and space and in such case is limited to a maximal speed which is the speed of light, limiting all processes in the framework of special relativity. Two classes of transmitters are considered here: massive, and non-massive:

Non-massive transmitters, such as electromagnetic waves, light, photons, gravitational waves, have no mass, and travel at the speed of light. Non-massive transmitters have a range physically limited to the event horizon, cannot transmit material elements, but may transmit information.

Massive transmitters, such as rocks, rockets, spaceships, probes, spores, atoms are physical entities that have a mass, and consequently an inertia, leading to huge requirements of energy to be accelerated, to speeds ultimately limited to the speed of light. These may carry

information, and material elements. In this work, transmission via massive transmitters is considered to be realistic limited to about 20%*c* with near term technologies, leading to a range limited to horizons shorter than the event horizon. Massive transmitter may transmit information and material elements.

The concepts of transmission and causation are intertwined, causation requiring the transmission of something for its process to happen, and transmission being a form of causation.

Transmitters: see *Transmission* in this glossary

Value (instrumental or proper): the value of something refers to “the regard that something is held to deserve; the importance, worth, or usefulness of something.” When assessing the scope of the kingmaker’s decision, the perception of what is valuable conditions what is taken into account for deciding. In our discussion, value may be considered as instrumental, or as proper. Proper value refers to the consideration that the value is attributed to the considered element itself, while instrumental refers to a value which only exists with respect to the benefit a given moral agent may get from the considered element. In this work will be outlined the fact that the preservation of outer space and celestial bodies, as per the current conceptualisation from the space treaty, only holds an instrumental value with regard to humans, and to their quest for the origin of life. One of the propositions of this work is that this instrumental view of space should be dropped, and that a deontological stance should be adopted with the attribution of a proper value to non-human objects and lifeforms, including to potential extraterrestrial lifeforms and biospheres.

I) PREREQUISITES

In this section, we propose a toolbox for navigating large scales of space and time.

To enjoy this discussion to its value, prerequisites are required. We will have to think beyond our individual experience. This is uneasy, because it means considering things that never happened, stories that haven't been told, and scales never been reached. We will have to reconsider what we think for granted, and picture spaces and environments way beyond what we are used to manipulating. Evolutionary biologists, geologists, astrophysicists, are used to doing this, but even if you classify amongst these, your conceptual approach is most probably the one of a researcher, to an object of study.

I need more from you: we want you to approach this question just as if you were to possibly have an impact on its advent, not as a theoretical object, but as a practical one. Why ? Because, as you'll progressively get to as you read, you may. Indeed, there is a link between us, now, and the potential bloom of life in the extrasolar space.

In this section are proposed a word of caution, and a toolkit for non-specialists to go through this work. If you are at ease with orders of magnitude, and eager to get into the hot topic: read cautiously the word of caution, skip the toolkit, and go directly to *II) Argumentation*. If you still wonder why you keep reading, or if you have issues with big numbers, let's tool you up: we will be addressing motivation (tool n°1), large numbers (tool n°2), scales (tool n°3), exponential growth (tool n°4), life as an identity, (tool n°5) before focussing on units (tool n°6).

A word of caution:

Caution: precision will never pretend to be better than the order of magnitude.

All along this work, while the highest efforts have been made to ensure the best possible precision, in line with the most updated paradigm as per our literature survey, numbers are provided here exclusively for the consideration of orders of magnitude, and representational purpose. All details upon calculations are provided in the annex. Precision will never pretend to be better than the order of magnitude. Special consideration is to be taken when considering provided estimations related to the distribution of life or intelligent communicating life. These are highly speculative, the probabilities of presence being possibly eventually encountered about anywhere in between 0 and 1. Such estimations are provided for a

representational purpose only, and while being coherent with the current paradigm, are highly uncertain.

- Whatsoever, check your distances and bearings before intergalactic navigation -

Tool n°1: gaining a strong motivation to dig in

“Why should we bother with such science fiction ? Climate change is coming, civilisation is doomed, COVID is on us, kindergarten is closed !!!”.

To try to overcome this issue of our subject being instinctively discarded as irrelevant, I propose to start this discussion by addressing your motivation to dig in, through a unacademic but necessary proposition:

Why you care

- You, as a human being alive in 2020, do care, because right now, systems are financed, prototyped, hundred of these flying over your head²⁶ right now, which by 2040, this is the subject of this essay, are likely to initiate the transformation of hundreds of billions of billions of stellar systems, into a playground for life as we know it on Earth. Strictly out of control.
- You care because you have no clue on whether this bloom to happen is good or bad, the only certitude being that it is going to be of astronomical magnitude, and that there is no way back.
- You care because on the ongoing track, this is going to happen just like this, undecided.
- You care because you could do something about it.

Now that this has been read, you have an inescapable responsibility, which is to challenge what I've just written here, and either, conclude it is untrue, or face the question of whether it would be ethical for you to get involved in the resolution of the issue.

**Mankind is about to mix it up with its highest possible
impact, ever. Will you stay aside, or take side ?**

²⁶ [17] (Tavares, 2019) [What is KickSat-2?](#)

Tool n°2: numbers, significance, and orders of magnitude

Significant numbers

I perfectly know you might not like numbers. Still, I want you to realise the extreme magnitude of things, and ironically, to do so, words like “extreme”, “huge”, “more incredibly extreme”, are not enough. Numbers matter for picturing scales. When I say I’ve eaten a real lot of pizzas last week, it is not the same as stating I ate twenty thousand pizzas last week. I’m ok, thank you.

Initially, the below argumentation was planned to be made without numerical evaluation, due both to the risk of losing people on the way, and to the difficulty and extra workload related to providing these. The decision was taken to use numbers, for their unbeaten representational significance. We are to use numbers for two purposes:

1. Consider magnitude: what is the maximal impact ?
2. Help picture: what does it entail, for what ? for who ?

Because here are our targets, the numbers we’ll provide you with will be as significant as can be: we’ll try and keep it to one digit, plus a given amount of zeros. Things like 1000 chickens. or 200.000 pies.

Orders of magnitude:

When we’ll have so many zeroes that it will be long to write these down, we’ll use the notation “e”. For example: 200.000 pigeons will be written: $2e+5$ pigeons. The second number indicates the amount of digit to follow the first number. In accordance with the scientific habit, we’ll refer to this as the order of magnitude. So the order of magnitude of something is the amount of numbers, to follow the first digit. Some time, there will be a minus sign (-). This will mean we are speaking of X out of the given order of magnitude. $2e-5$ refers to 2, out of five orders of magnitudes of pigeons, which means 2, out of 100.000 pigeons.

We intuitively use orders of magnitude for evaluations and for comparison, so even if you’re not into numbers, it will make sense to consider that 1000 more of something, is three orders of magnitude bigger, and that 1.000.000.000.000 more, is twelve orders of magnitude bigger (twelve digits after the first one.).

Tool n°3: a workable reference for scales

A key representation in the below work is the difference of volume between what is inside the Solar System, and what is outside of it, limited by the event horizon. The event horizon is the maximal distance to which a causal relation may propagate. This space, containing the maximal possible consequences of what is decided on Earth, is limited by the maximal speed of propagation of consequences, which is the speed of light²⁷, and by the expansion of the universe, which is at some point going faster than those possible consequences. By volume, this is $1e+29$ times larger than our Solar System²⁸. If this means nothing to you, it is normal: to me neither.

To help conceptualize, I propose to consider the ultimate limits of our humane experience with volumes, and compare a percent of a water droplet, which would be just barely perceptible to your eye, to the entire oceans on Earth. 29 orders of magnitude separate those volumes²⁹, the same as between the Solar System and the volume within the event horizon. The smallest bit of water you could catch with your naked eyes, lost within a space a hundred of billion billion billion (100.000.000.000.000.000.000.000.000) times more voluminous. Let this be our representation. This is big, but not infinite. This is related to the experience we have, we can work it. Let's set aside the "too big for me", you've just done it.

Fig 1. The volume ratio between the Solar System and the space within the event horizon.

²⁷ Central hypothesis to Special Relativity

²⁸ Calculated from Solar SOI= 3.25Ly, Event horizon 15.7e9Ly.

²⁹ Droplet: 1.8e-6Liters, Oceans on Earth, 1.3e21 Liters.

Once we've set this representation, a short focus on orders of magnitudes is useful. A factor of 10 separates two orders of magnitudes, a factor of 100 separate 2 of these, and so on. So $1e27$ is two orders of magnitudes smaller than $1e29$. Using the representation above, it is very easy to conceptualize high orders of magnitudes: when $1e29$ is the ocean compared to a percent of a droplet, then $1e27$ is the oceans to a drop. $1e21$ is the ocean to a milk bottle, $1e18$, to a cubic meter.

Tool n°4: picturing exponential growth

As humans, we have extensive issues imagining what exponential progress means.³⁰

Live entities do self-replicate. Given the proper environment and resource access, each generation sees an instantiation by a R factor, moderated by the possible death rate in the meantime. When speaking about animals, we call this the generation renewal rate. Speaking about viruses, we'll evocate a basic reproduction number R_0 . Dealing with ideas, which might be to some extent interpreted as similar to viruses³¹, we'll speak of a net promoter score, evaluating the amount of people you will convince once you are yourself convinced with an idea.

Self-replicating entities have their population varying exponentially with generations: $P = R^g$ where P is the population, R the renewal rate, and g the number of generations. When R is bigger than 1, growth is accelerating constantly, leading to what is referred to as an exponential growth. With R lower than 1, we'll speak of an exponential decay.

To get a grasp of what exponential growth means, I share the idea to **start from the end**: let's consider the case of a bacteria population tripling every three day, in an ecosystem capable of sustaining the growth of a billion of these bacterias. Considering the first ones does not give the feel of an impressive expansion: we have 1, then 3, then 9 bacterias in the ecosystem, after 9 days, well, 27 bacterias have grown. Not much of an issue in our billion capable ecosystem. When considering the case starting by the limiting factor: the representation changes drastically: 3 days before the completion of colonisation, only one third of the ecosystem had been colonised, and 9 days before, only about 4%. Only now, when considering this bacteria, that may grow 960 million of instances of itself and populate the entire ecosystem in 9 days only,

³⁰ As experienced with COVID outbreak, and identified long ago by experimental psychologists: see [18]

³¹ [19] (Sperber, 1996). *La Contagion des idées*.

from a population representing only 4% of it, do we realise what an exponential growth does represent.

There is a reason why the exponential growth of self-replicating things, amongst which living organisms in favorable ecosystems, feel like explosions: the same equations are at the core of the nuclear chain reactions. **Exponential growth is difficult to reason with, because these have a slow start, while having explosive conclusions. Thinking from the end backward might help us considering their power.**

Tool n°5: life, as a workable identity.

In our experience of life, we are categorising the living world by species. This works well for short timeframes. Not when envisioning long futures, and here we will be considering hundreds of billion years. Evolution is slow compared to our experience, but superfast per cosmological times: billions of species have been created along the history of evolution (99.9% dead by now). Diverging from a single species, you get space faring humans, whales, bats and dogs in less than 94Myr³². In 400.000 years, 0.1% of the history of Earth, hominids evolved to the space age! Species, amongst them the human species, are irrelevant categories for thinking millions to billions of years, and even for thinking less than a century ahead, should we give any credit to the omens of trans and post-humanists³³.

Species are equally irrelevant when considering serious space travel: as seen with chimps and humans, a journey at 20% of the speed of light to the Andromeda galaxy, our closest neighbour, will take time enough for species onboard to turn into new ones. Should you somehow freeze the travellers, via dehydration, congelation, hibernation ? Too bad: your individuals on the home planet do speciate in the meantime.

So how are we envisioning biodiversity when considering futures beyond speciation time ? We propose to drop our instinctive, human centered way of thinking. After accepting the consideration that at extreme scales of time and space, the concept of species is irrelevant, here is another switch to flip. We'll need to stop thinking as humans, and start to think of us, as living things, part of a larger category encompassing all lifeforms we know of. We will refer to this as "life, as we know it on Earth".

³² [15] ([Kumar et al.2017](#)) [TimeTree: A Resource for Timelines, Timetrees, and Divergence Times](#)

³³ [20] ([Bostrom 2014](#)) [Superintelligence: Paths, Dangers, Strategies.](#)

Tool n°6: a focus on units

Units for addressing such scales are different to what we are used to, which is an added complexity. Here is an overview of the ones that we'll use. Years, light-years, astronomical units, cubic light years, kilometers per second, and percentages of the speed of light, kilograms and solar masses.

Timewise it is simple, we will speak of years, thousands years (Kyr, e+3yr), million years (Myr, e+6yr), billion years (Gyr, e+9years). For short distances, within the Solar System, we'll use astronomical units (AU) , one AU being the distance from the Sun to Earth. For long distances, we'll prefer light years, which relate to the maximal distance a beam of light is capable of traveling for a year. We'll have light-years, (ly), thousands of (Kly, 1e3Ly), millions of (Mly, 1e6ly), and billions of (Gly, 1e9ly). "Slow" speeds will be referred to as kilometers per second (kps), and high speeds, as percentages of c, the speed of light in the void, ranging at 300.000 kps. 20%c will refer to 20% of the speed of light.

Last but not least, a useful unit in cosmology, that we will use occasionally, is solar masses, noted M_{\odot} , one M_{\odot} being equal to approximately $2e30$ kilograms.

In section I) PREREQUISITES, we've proposed what to our account is the minimal set of tools for non specialists to proceed: we've had a word of caution regarding the precision of the results presented here, and we've tried to address motivation (tool n°1), large numbers (tool n°2), scales (tool n°3), exponential growth (tool n°4), life as an identity, (tool n°5) and units (tool n°6), to make these more accessible.

We now are fully motivated, cautious with numbers, capable of picturing what these represent, and we've realised that the concept of a human species is extremely local in time, and irrelevant for thinking at large scales. We've dropped it as a reference, and we are now prepared to think with an expanded view, considering life as a reference.

It is time to investigate precisely the logic of what is proposed here: this is the purpose of the next section: II) ARGUMENTATION

II) ARGUMENTATION

In this section, we present the reasoning concluding to the existence of a kingmaker situation.

Now geared up with a cautionary approach to numbers, a motivation to dig in, and tools for manipulating large scales, we propose in this section to detail the argumentation underlying the assertion along which humans are holding a kingmaker³⁴ position regarding the potential impact of life as we know it, to astronomical scales, through technological achievements and spacefaring ambitions. Before digging in the exploration of their validity (III) HYPOTHESES), we will here consider the logical paths from those hypotheses to our conclusions. This section is as such dedicated to the exploration of the reasoning itself.

A) outline

So as to encompass the subtleties of the possible impacts, working definitions are proposed in A) Working definitions, which will allow us to formulate the reasoning and identify the hypotheses. After adopting a working definition for “life”, we will distinguish life and life-related elements. First order life, fully autonomous, will be differentiated from higher order life, which require specific substrates to express itself. Eventually, life will be considered to possibly behold a material or informational nature.

A precise definition will then be adopted for the Solar System boundaries, which will be defined timewise and spacewise, allowing for a clarification of what “extrasolar” means.

From this, in B) Logical Paths the paths connecting the hypotheses to the assertion of humans being kingmakers regarding life as we know it on Earth, are detailed, found to be cross-related, and a conditional scheme is proposed and analysed, leading to the conclusion of a robust reasoning, leading from the determined hypotheses, to the conclusion of a strong path to the kingmaker position. (Twelves supporting hypotheses are identified, that will be further explored in the section III) HYPOTHESES.)

In C) On the explored Magnitude, the exploration of the magnitude of maximal impacts is discussed, detailing a large tolerance to errors in the evaluation, and to underachievements in the projected technological paths. The transformative action at stake is then envisioned, with

³⁴ A kingmaker is “One who makes or sets up kings”. In game design theory, a kingmaker situation is one where one of the players, while unable to win the game, is given the power to decide who is to win.

consequences ranging to the matter content and to the dynamic of expansion of the accessible universe. (The evaluation of magnitude will be detailed in IV) EVALUATION, and is supported by the work in Annex IV Scope).

B) Working definitions

Clarification is required regarding what is meant by life, and by extrasolar. To settle this, here below are a proposition of a working definition for life, along with key properties, and a precise definition of the boundary of the Solar System, which delineates the beginning of the extrasolar space and as such also clarifies what extrasolar means.

Life

The selection process for a working definition of life, is defended in III)life.B.Life. interpreted, where the identified most relevant properties of life, regarding our question, are explored, and where the life-related hypotheses sustaining the presented reasoning are addressed.

In the proposed argumentation, life refers to anything “evolving, self-reproducing, transducing energy and converting its substrate”.

Life in this discussion is called first order or autonomous when the considered substrate is material, unprocessed by another form of life. It is called higher order or dependent when the required substrate is being or has been produced by another lifeform.

life-related elements refer to parts or bits of life, such as bits of organism, genus or code, which might acquire full life properties through the integration with other lifeforms.

life, or life-related elements, may behold a material or informational nature. From the adopted definition, organisms, viruses, are material forms of life. Ideas, computer viruses, or simulated life,³⁵ are of informational nature. Fragments of DNA are material life-related elements, while DNA sequences are informational life-related elements. This distinction is important because informational life or life-related elements may travel on signals, while material life or life-related elements require a massive vector to travel.

Solar System boundaries

Spacewise, following the analysis synthesized in III)Solar System and detailed in *Annex I Solar System*, the sphere of influence (SOI), 3.25Ly radius, is retained as a boundary. From the point

³⁵ [16] (Bedau 2007) ARTIFICIAL life_A-life Artificial life simulations

of view of living organisms, and of interstellar navigation, this delineates the volume inside which energy is required for escaping the solar influence.

Timewise, the Solar System is identified as splitted into three different periods, separated by catastrophic events not anticipated to be survivable by life as we know it: the helium flash ending the red giant phase, +7.6Gyr ahead, the planetary nebula, at +7.7Gyr and the unsustainable tidal disruption in the narrowing habitable zone of the dimming white dwarf, at +15Gyr. Time capsules or temporary navigations might allow to avoid those cataclysmic events, and conceptually, the two later periods are considered as potentially accessible, separated stellar systems.

C) Logical paths

A working definition for “life”, and “extrasolar”, being elected, we may proceed with the logic of the argumentation. In C.1 Logic, we will detail the arguments, and multiple possible logical paths, leading to the conclusion that humans hold a kingmaker position regarding the potential impact of life as we know it, to astronomical scale. In C.2 Hypotheses, twelve hypotheses are identified, and given short names for easier reference in the discussion. These are regrouped in three classes, depending on the domain these are considered to primarily relate to (these will later be addressed in this order in III)Hypotheses). In C.3. Conditional scheme, a conditional scheme is proposed to synthesise the reasoning, and an analysis is proposed, leading to the consideration that the presented logic is resilient to a variety of combinations of failing hypotheses.

C.1 logic

Highest level

In the hypotheses where life as we know it on Earth has little to no natural possibility of interstellar access, where historical interstellar access, including via human activities, may be considered as negligible, and given the survival of technological capability for mankind, multiple paths are identified where humans might provide first order life as we know it on Earth with an extrasolar impact. As such, being currently the only possible provider for such access, the role of humans is critical in controlling this access, which we will refer to as a gateway to the stars. Humans are in this perspective holding a kingmaker position regarding life as it is known on earth.

Irreversibility

In the hypothesis where no control may be exerted on life or life related elements once out of the Solar System, then the created gateway to the Stars is a non return path: once life blooms on a remote world, or once a life related element is picked up by a hypothetical extraterrestrial lifeform (ET), there is no possible way back.

Travel

If life is resistant enough to survive an interstellar journey, if we humans are capable of developing interstellar travel, and if life as we know it, as passenger(intentionally), hitchhiker(incidentally) or stowaway (malevolently), may gain interstellar access via human technologies, then we, humans, become a gateway to the stars for life as we know it.

Signal

If life-related informational elements³⁶, such as ideas, technologies, computer virus or genetical codes may be transmitted via electromagnetic waves, if somewhere else, intelligent life exist, capable of picking, decoding and transducing these, and if we humans are capable of developing an interstellar signaling and communication system, then we humans are representing a possible gateway to the stars, for elements related to life as we know it, and even for first order life as we know it, should a genetic code ever be transmitted and transduced on a system capable of expressing it.

Time capsules

If life, or life related elements, are resistant enough to survive extreme lengths of time onboard a time capsule, and if we humans are capable of producing such a long lasting time capsule, then we humans represent a gateway to the stars, for life as we know it, via the media of an hypothetical civilisation, picking up and opening the given time capsule, or without this media, through a timed or conditional reactivation, way beyond the time at which all life on Earth will have stopped.

³⁶ life-related elements refer to parts or bits of life, such as bits of organism, genus or code, which miss one of the properties of life (evolving, self-reproducing, energy transducing, substrate conversion), but might acquire full life properties through evolution or the integration with other life forms. (See glossary for details)

C.2 Hypotheses

From the above logic, twelve main hypotheses are extracted, detailed below.

Hypotheses are given short names to allow for easier reference, and are classified in three categories, depending on the domain these are considered to relate principally. These are listed below with hyperlinks to the locations in [PartIII\) Hypotheses](#), where these are addressed, and are underlined so as to allow for quicker identification in the text and the table of content.

Hypotheses regarding life, with hyperlinks to location in the document:

- [Space resistance](#): some lifformes, or life related elements may survive the constraints related to space flights.
- [Time resistance](#): some lifformes, or life related elements may survive for extreme durations.
- [Interstellar resistance](#): some lifformes, or life related elements survive interstellar journeys.
- [Existence of ETI](#) : Intelligent life (ETI) exist, capable of picking, and transducing information recovered from a signal, a time capsule or a spaceship

Hypotheses regarding the extrasolar environment, with hyperlinks to location in the document:

- [Natural access](#): life has little to no natural possibility of interstellar access
- [Historical access](#): life has had no historical possibility of interstellar access

Hypothesis regarding humans, with hyperlinks to relevant chapters in the document:

- [Interstellar signaling](#): humans are to develop interstellar communication systems
- [Time capsules](#): humans are to develop time capsules
- [Interstellar travel](#): humans are to develop interstellar probes or spaceships
- [Technological civilisation](#): A space capable civilisation is surviving
- [Boarding](#): some life forms may be embarked intentionally, incidentally, or malevolently, on a probe or a spaceship made by man, and life related information, such as ideas, technologies, computer virus, genetical codes may be transmitted via onboard information systems, or signals
- [Irreversibility](#): control may not be exerted on life out of the Solar System.

C.3 Conditional scheme

A conditional scheme (fig 2.) is proposed, to synthesise the reasoning presented in C.1 Logic, outlining the conditional relations between the extracted hypotheses, and the conclusion of the creation of a gateway to the stars controlled by humans, setting humans in a kingmaker position.

Via the development of interstellar travel (paths 1 & 3, on fig2.), via interstellar signaling (path 5), or via time capsules (paths 2 & 4), humans are given five routes to the position of deciding upon opening or not, the door for life or life related elements, to the extrasolar space.

Fig 2. Conditional scheme: humans becoming kingmakers regarding life expansion

Unspecified nodes are “and” conditions, plain black gates labeled **&or** need a minimum of one upstream condition to be valid. Conditions in **bold** are critical

Four critical conditions leading to the failure of this reasoning are found to be :“life has little to no natural interstellar access”(natural access), “life has had no historical possibility of interstellar access” (historical access), “a technological civilisation exist” (technological civilisation), and “some life forms may be embarked intentionally, incidentally, or malevolently, on a probe or a spaceship made by man, and life related information, such as ideas, technologies, computer

virus, genetical codes may be transmitted via onboard information systems, or signals” (boarding).

Three of those critical hypotheses, no natural access, no historical access, and boarding, are found to be highly likely to stay satisfied. As such, the hypothesis on the survival of our technological civilisation is the sole critical condition being envisioned, that could likely fail. For the kingmaker position to never exist, though, a civilisational collapse has to happen before any of the currently limiting conditions, Interstellar signaling, Time capsules, or Interstellar travel is satisfied.

Now considering non-critical conditions, It is found that as many as three simultaneous failures may be accepted, as long as maximum one of these happens in the set of hypotheses related to technological developments (Interstellar signaling, Time capsules, Interstellar travel).Then, any two of the three technological solutions under development (interstellar travel, time capsules, interstellar signaling) may fail, without compromising the conclusion.

The mechanics leading to the acquisition of the decisional capability by mankind, possibly following five, partly intertwined, different paths, are found to be logically relatively robust.

As a synthesis on the analysis of the conditional structure it may be concluded that the logic is resilient to a variety of combinations of failing hypotheses, and that the reasoning itself may be considered as robust against the hypotheses regarding technological achievements, and the existence of ETI, the unique unassured critical hypothesis, being the one of the survival of our technological civilisation.

C.4 Conditional strength of hypotheses

The hypotheses listed above are investigated in III) Hypotheses. A review of the conclusions regarding the strengths of these hypotheses is presented here, in perspective with their position in the conditional scheme.

Related to life:

Space, time, and interstellar resistance (hypothesis on space resistance ,time resistance, interstellar resistance), are found to be increasingly credible, with the discovery of organisms resisting acceleration up to 400.000Gs, ionizing radiation, and temperatures up to 1000°C. This, alongside with a range of natural and artificial possibilities for stasis via dehydration, or cryogenisation.

While not critical, an unsecured and important hypothesis is the one on extraterrestrial intelligent life: “extraterrestrial intelligent life (ETI) exists, capable of picking, and transducing information recovered from a signal, a time capsule or a spaceship” (hypothesis on the existence of ETI). The failure of this hypothesis is not critical to the conclusion, with two remaining paths for the gateway: spaceships (hypothesis on interstellar travel), and time capsules (hypothesis on time capsules), the latter being extraordinarily advanced. Still, it will be seen that this hypothesis on the existence of ETI, beyond participating in 3 out of five of the possible paths to the kingmaker situation, is critically conditioning the nature and magnitude of the potential impact of releasing life, and from the perspective on magnitude, may be understood as a double sided knife³⁷

Related to extrasolar access :

The hypothesis regarding the absence of extrasolar Natural access, and Historical access, are critical ones, but found to be very robust: by the investigated literature, natural interstellar exchange of lifeforms is considered to be slow, if ever happening (see III, Solar System, E) Hypothesis on historical access).

Then, when integrating what might have happened until now, including the human signaling and travelling activity, it can be concluded that life as we know it has had a negligible potential impact onto the extrasolar space (see III, Solar System, E) Hypothesis on Historical access)

Related to humans :

On technology: the conditions on interstellar travel and interstellar signaling are being extremely actively worked on by the Breakthrough Starshot ecosystem³⁸. Time capsules, probably the most advanced of the considered breakthrough type technologies³⁹, are nearing operational capability. The three conditioning technologies (interstellar travel interstellar signaling and time capsules), have prototypes running, and the three are being financed. An allegedly credible twenty year operational target has been set. As seen above, two of these

³⁷ See VII) SYNTHESIS Gateway to the stars

³⁸ [7] (Breakthrough Initiatives 2020) Starshot.

³⁹ Breakthrough-type technologies discussed here are Breakthrough Starshot project, promising probes traveling at 20%*c* and a galactic range laser, light sails allowing 20%*c* on long range trajectories, without the support of a laser, and the already prototyped Arch Mission Foundation time capsules, lasting 10e14yr

hypotheses may fail simultaneously without impairing the conclusion. Delays or and large underachievements⁴⁰ are not impairing it either.

On the uncontrollability of extrasolar life once released, and on the impossibility of canceling the activation of the gateway “Control may not be exerted on life out of the Solar System” (hypothesis on irreversibility), the appealing quantity of examples of our failure to control life on Earth, starting by ourselves, then ranging from patagonian beavers, to australian camels via rats on the pacific islands, sheds little doubt on this later question. Pretending to control blooming, evolving life, light-years away out there, when you are unable to manage a beaver, appear unreasonable. Even for god-playing geneticists. This condition, while critical, is to us very unlikely to be failing.

The question of the survival of our space capable technological civilisation is critical to the kingmaker position. The perspectives on this are extremely diverse, and the possibility of a collapse is real considering history. Following a collapse, the possibility that key easy-access resources have been exhausted and may impair the apparition of a new space age, is envisioned. This aspect of the hypothesis is shedding a light of urgency onto the decision to be taken by humans as kingmakers: should the spread of life be something good to do, the decision shall better be taken rapidly. More: a self reinforcing mechanism of the scheme in fig 2. may be proposed: the more the failure of the hypothesis of technological civilisation is probable, i.e. the more a collapse is likely, the more people may actually be pushing for an escape, a colonisation plan, or a panspermia strategy to an accessible world, for the purpose of “saving mankind”, or simply, as advocated by musk for its martian plans, “to do it before we can’t”. This possible mechanism, that we are unable to prove, is referred to as *the arch effect*, with reference to the biblical myth and, should it be effective, would reinforce largely the kingmaker situation, by pushing for a decision to happen.

Last in our set is the hypothesis on boarding, which is critical, but considered unlikely to be failing: whatever the efforts of planetary protection⁴¹It is considered impossible that all spaceships and time capsules with a potential for interstellar impact, are decontaminated to the point not even a single spore remains. A single autotrophic microorganism is indeed enough to build up an entire biodiversity from scratch given survivable conditions are there upon arrival.

⁴⁰ See D) , on the explored magnitude, on this topic

⁴¹ Planetary protection refers to the measures taken to avoid interplanetary contamination. International guidelines are set by COSPAR, whose legal basis are the Article IX of the Outer Space Treaty

When considering higher orders of life related elements, possible traveling on signals, the question is not even addressed by the community.

C.5 Synthesis on the proposed argumentation

All hypotheses envisioned above from their position in the logic of the assertion that humans are to accede to a kingmaker position, and discussed in detail in the next section *III) Hypotheses*, are found credible, and robust as per the current scientific and technological paradigm⁴². A large amount of combinations of failed hypotheses may be accepted without failing the conclusion.

Two hypotheses are highly unsecured: the one on the existence of extraterrestrial intelligence, and the one on the survival of a technological civilisation. The latter is the unique critical condition to the reasoning, to be considered as unsecured. It is satisfied at the moment, and its failure, to be conclusive, would have to happen before the technological conditions of interstellar travel, interstellar signaling, or time capsules do happen. An hypothetical self-reinforcing effect is proposed, linking those hypotheses with the one of the use of the would be gateway. The *Ark effect* is postulating that when the perspective of a collapse is closing, humans do accelerate the pace for the development of interstellar travel, interstellar signaling, time capsules, and push for the use of the gateway when it is available.

In this situation, the conditions we humans might have an impact on, regarding the constitution of this kingmaker situation, are considered to be the development of the technological means (interstellar travel, interstellar signaling, time capsules), the management of our risk of technological collapse (hypothesis on technological civilisation), to some extent the management of the risk of boarding, via measures like planetary protection, and to some extent, the consideration for this *Ark effect*, should it exist.

Given this setting, at this stage of the analysis, it is considered probable that the kingmaker situation of humans regarding life as it is known on Earth, is to be realised, if it is not already existing through the developed capability regarding time capsules. In this context of being capable of making a decision, it becomes important to explore the scope⁴³, and the magnitude of the possible impacts of this decision. Here below are developed elements fundamental to

⁴² a scientific paradigm refers to “the world view underlying the theories and methodology of a particular scientific subject” (see glossary for details). The technological paradigm refers to the currently developed technologies, along with a perspective regarding the pace at which new ones are generated.

⁴³ As detailed in *Annex IV, Scope*, and proposed in the Glossary, “the scope a considered decision is the maximal set of things potentially impacted by it”

consider before undertaking this evaluation, which will be the purpose of section IV, *Evaluation*, based on a model developed in *Annex IV, de Sitter* and on calculations developed in *Annex IV, Scope*.

D) On the explored magnitude

Astronomical magnitude

The magnitude of this potential decision will be explored and is astronomical. While limited due to physics and the expansion of the universe, it is way beyond anything we humans may experience, and conceptually extremely difficult to grasp. Long story short, we are to feed life, with 29 orders of magnitude more of volume, and everything within. Stars, energy, habitable planets, possible ET, commercial networks, extragalactic access, sensibilities, feelings, existential questions, love, maybe? Not to forget death and suffering. Hundreds of billion billion billion more of volume, and of everything within. More, 15 of these orders of magnitude are to be directly dependent on Breakthrough Starshot-type technological advance (interstellar travel, interstellar signaling).

A large margin for error or underachievement

In the discussion proposed in V), p74, we'll argue that the increase of a single order of magnitude, of the space accessed by life as we know it, is sufficient to render the discussion critically important. With 15 of these announced to be available 20 years ahead, there is some margin for errors, and underachievement.

Our estimates may be false by up to 14 orders of magnitude, in volume before the discussion is rendered obsolete. With the upper bound to the incertitude in the evaluation, being estimated in *Annex IV Scope*, to be of 4 orders of magnitude, a margin of 10 orders of magnitude remains.

Of course, while the ultimate limits of physics as given by the current paradigm, are unnegotiable, it is envisioned that Breakthrough-type targets are exceeded or missed. For this discussion to be rendered irrelevant though, the Breakthrough speed target of 20%*c* would have to be missed by a factor 500, regarding extragalactic opportunities, and by a factor of 5000, when considering intragalactic ones. Just as conceiving a supersonic aircraft and ending up with something not even capable of rolling at the speed of a snail, this is not happening.

More: given the maximal increase of 29 orders, set by the ultimate physical limit of the event horizon, should our estimations be reasonable by the order of magnitude, which has been the target while providing them, and should Breakthrough target of 20%^c be reached, by order of magnitude, no higher increase will ever be possible⁴⁴(by orders of magnitude, of accessible elements within volume), due the nearing of physical limits of the reachable universe.

Transformative action

Critical to the conceptualisation of the odds at stakes, is the understanding of the exponential character of life development until the exhaustion of its limiting resources, which provides it with a powerful transforming power for the substrate it develops within. When self reproducing elements are considered, as developed in the toolkit⁴⁵, growth happens exponentially. When living things grow exponentially, not only the living things increase in population with a rate governed by their number: so do the converted elements of the considered environment or substrate. As explored in III.Life.B.4, Life is consequently exponentially transforming its substrate. Until it has to stop due one of the required resources being missing.

First order impact

This direct transformation is obvious when what is considered is the exponential expansion of autonomous life, such as autotrophic organisms, or biologic ecosystems, creating, maintaining and reproducing themselves from simple elements and energy harvested in their environment. The obvious are usually the most unintuitive things to realise, still: now stop reading and look around you, as developed in the next section: can you spot a simple thing which is not alive, or has not been somehow reworked by life? Not such an easy question: from the atmosphere you are breathing, to the concrete below your feet, from the dinosaur juice you feed your car with, to the stones your building is made of, to any single thing that you eat. Even rainwater and snowfall happen around condensation nuclei, which may be biological (viruses, spores) or organic (Black carbon). As it did to Earth, life could rework those 29 orders of magnitude we've discussed.

⁴⁴ (29-15=14, <15)

⁴⁵ [Tooln°4](#): picturing exponential growth

Higher order impact

Less obvious and nevertheless critical is the transformative power of self-replicating life related elements, requiring a substrate to operate, and referred to as higher order life⁴⁶. Should the proper substrate be encountered, computers, organisms, networks, brains, autotrophs or ecosystems to integrate with, higher order life related elements, such as ideas, might flourish and transform the substrate, which in turn changes the way it alters the non-living environment. Higher orders of life are a critical part of the issue: not only because informational ones may travel at the speed of light, to colonise and flourish amongst preexisting network and things, but more problematical, because these are possibly the ones we care the most about: ideas (3rd order), ethics(3rd order), interactions (3rd order). More, when considering life at the scale of biospheres, noospheres as per Vernardsky understanding may drive critical metabolic changes at lower orders: we're just seeing it with covid, where 3rd life (COVID), impacts the noosphere (4rd order), in such a way that the entire metabolism of life on Earth is changed. 6% diminution of energy consumption⁴⁷, directly induced by the global noosphere, as a response to the perceived threat.

Would development on Earth have been different, would our science and philosophy have flourished in a different manner, faster or slower, if Aristotle had had the brightest star in the sky, blinking the number π ? And how would the Earth noosphere react to such a thing, now ? Keep reading, we'll get a strong estimate of the amount of habitable planets, to which we could signal with such a magnitude.

Maximal magnitude

In this work, we are to propose a conceptualisation of the maximal possible things at stake. This has two parts: their nature, and the maximal extent to which these might be impacted. See what life is doing to Earth itself: changing atmosphere, reworking surfaces, rerouting energy ? We will consider the maximal impact, when what is concerned is the entire universe, and see that the matter content, and expansion dynamic of the universe itself, might be eventually affected.

⁴⁶ See III) Life.B.6 Substrate, and glossary, for more on higher orders of Life;

⁴⁷As outlined in [21] ([IEA, 2020\) Sustainable Recovery](#))

After having in I) PREREQUISITES, geared up with a cautionary advice and a set of representational tools, we've been in II) ARGUMENTATION, outlining our reasoning, setting working definitions regarding life and the Solar System, before detailing the logic leading to our conclusion of a kingmaker situation. Hypotheses were extracted, supporting our proposition, and a conditional scheme linking these to the conclusion was proposed. Its analysis settled the robustness of our assertion and it was concluded that the kingmaker situation is very probable, if not already in place. This led to the necessity of envisioning the scope encompassed by the possible decision humans could take regarding life, and considerations where envisioned regarding the allowable errors in representation, and the magnitude of the potential impacts. The next section, III) Hypotheses, will address the precise investigation of all the identified hypothesis

III) HYPOTHESES

In this section, we investigate the conditions supporting the existence of a kingmaker situation.

Considering the multiplicity and intertwining of the logical paths to the defended kingmaker position of humans regarding life, and the related options, the choice is made, rather to follow one of those paths and then to be left over with remaining intertwining options to relate it to, to proceed with the exploration of the hypothesis following a narrative chosen so as to limit cross references and allow a progressive explanation of the concepts at stake. As a consequence two ways may be chosen for going through the below investigation.

You may either choose directly to go to the hypothesis you're interested in, taking the risk of finding cross reference to earlier concepts, or simply follow the narrative along our exploration, with the risk of the hypothesis you're more interested in, to lay at the end of the document.

Section II, HYPOTHESES, is divided in three chapters, Chapter 1 addresses hypotheses mainly related to life, Chapter 2, the ones related to the extrasolar access, and Chapter 3, to humans.

The hyperlinks below are provided for direct navigation

Chapter 1 : Hypotheses mainly related to life

- Space resistance: some lifformes, or life related elements may survive the constraints related to space travel.
- Time resistance: some lifformes, or life related elements may survive for extreme durations.
- Interstellar resistance: some lifformes, or life related elements survive interstellar journeys.
- Existence of ETI : Intelligent life (ETI) exist, capable of picking, and transducing information recovered from a signal, a time capsule or a spaceship

Chapter 2 : Hypotheses mainly related to extrasolar access

- Natural access: life has little to no natural possibility of interstellar access
- Historical access: life has had no historical possibility of interstellar access

Chapter 3 : Hypotheses mainly related to humans

- Interstellar signaling: humans are to develop interstellar communication systems
- Time capsules: humans are to develop time capsules
- Interstellar travel: humans are to develop interstellar probes or spaceships
- Technological civilisation: A space capable civilisation is surviving
- Boarding: some life forms may be embarked intentionally, incidentally, or malevolently, on a probe or a spaceship made by man, and life related information, such as ideas, technologies, computer virus, genetical codes may be transmitted via onboard information systems, or signals
- Irreversibility: control may not be exerted on life out of the Solar System

PART III) HYPOTHESES

Chapter 1 : Life

Investigating in this chapter :

- Hypothesis on space resistance
- Hypothesis on time resistance
- Hypothesis on interstellar resistance
- Hypothesis on the existence of ETI

In this chapter, we investigate the hypotheses related to life. To do so, we do propose a working definition for life, allowing its characterisation and identification, before considering the hypotheses relevant to the kingmaker discussion, regarding resistance to time, space, and interstellar travel. Life *as we do not know it* is then precise, and the hypothesis relating to its existence is addressed.

In **A) Life, physically** we set up a macroscopic representation of what is life as we know it, through the exploration of the vast amount of matter it interacts with on Earth.

In **B) Life, interpreted** we identify key properties, critical to the understanding of its potential impact, should it become extrasolar. After considerations on the question of defining life (B.1), our characterisation takes place (B.2), and is developed from its constitutive parameters: the properties of self-reproduction (B.3), energy transduction and resource conversion (B.4), evolution, (B.5) and requirement for a substrate (B.6).

Being then tooled with a sharper representation, in **C) The resistance of life**, we investigate the hypotheses regarding space resistance (C.1), time resistance (C.2), and interstellar resistance of lifeforms, (C.3) which participate to the conclusion that life might gain an extrasolar access through the involvement of humans.

In **D) Life as we do not know it**, the question of characterising life as we do not know it, is addressed (D.1), and the hypothesis on the existence of extraterrestrial intelligence is detailed, and assessed (D.2).

A) Life, physically

The bloom of life on Earth has had tremendous consequences. Out of raw materials, transforming and partly storing available energy through molecular modifications, life transformed the planet surface from the molecular to the macroscopic scales across 17 orders of magnitude⁴⁸. The assembly, maintenance, and massive reproduction of organisms has noticeably changed the flow of energy on Earth, virtually turning it into a massive solar power collector, and energy storage facility.

Indeed, today algae (for 46%), and land plants (for 54%)⁴⁹ reroute about 8% of the incoming solar energy⁵⁰, to power directly 82%⁵¹ of a 100 km thick biosphere, and the rest of it via a trophic network: 2000 gigatons (2e15kg)⁵² of encapsulated and connected biologic systems, accounting for a thousands of billion billion billion individual lifeforms (1e30, 1e31 when counting viruses)⁵³, feeding over each other, ultimately powered by gravitationally induced nuclear reactions happening inside our star, the Sun.

When by volume (2000km³) life on Earth is not so considerable (at the terrestrial radius, it only represents a shell 4mm thick), what is considerable is the quantity of matter constantly transformed through its processes: assembling carbon for their structures, and storing solar energy into chemical bounds, primary producers extract so much carbon to be injected in the trophic chain that within 6 years of operation, the equivalent of entire atmospheric carbon has gone through the cycle. Mankind alone, through its constant reworking of its environment, is estimated to have already processed and displaced around 30 trillion tons of matter: ten times the entire mass of life itself, 50kg per square meter of terrestrial surface.⁵⁴ life is also storing energy in the structure of the organisms it is constituted of. The global energy storage right now is 2e22 J, representing about 20 years of mankind's current consumption (accounting for both energy storage age and biomass accapuration)

⁴⁸ From the length of the dihydrogen bound, to the diameter of Earth. See Annex/Evaluation/Scales.

⁴⁹ [22] (Field et al 1998) [Primary production of the biosphere...](#)

⁵⁰ Estimation made with an annual inbound solar energy of 5E+24J/yr, and an annual gross photosynthetic energy production GPP= 5.15E+21J/yr, with a 1% global photosynthetic efficiency. (Processed Sunlight = 4e23J, From GPP and Photosynthetic efficiency)

⁵¹ Calculation from the data presented in the figure below.

⁵² A ratio of 2 is used between carbon and dry mass, as per the conclusions of [1]

⁵³ [1] (Bar-On et al, 2018) [The biomass distribution on Earth.](#)

⁵⁴ [3] (Zalasiewicz et al, 2017) [Scale and diversity of the physical technosphere...](#)

Overall, life on Earth (including humans) is collecting $5e+21\text{J/yr}^{55}$, 90% of it via natural photosynthesis, and 10% via the human harvesting of fossil fuels, the remaining contributions (Nuclear energy, hydroelectricity, geothermy...) being negligible. Of this global energy input for the biodiversity, humans use their entire collecting contribution for their own purpose, and, do acaparate 15% of the net primary production from photosynthesis, for their activities: grasslands, feeding livestock, wood, building areas, croplands, induced fires⁵⁶. While representing a ridiculously small share of the overall individuals ($1/1e+21$), and biomass ($1/10.000$). Humans do control $\frac{1}{10}$ of the overall energy flow feeding life on Earth.

Overflying Earth, something I had the opportunity to do at low altitude for hours and hours to a very wide variety of places,⁵⁷ barely nothing can be seen whose direct morphology has not been modified by life, when not directly by us. From the atmosphere lifting our wings to the ocean below us, to any visible sedimentary rock, city, countryside or deserted landscape, almost everything has been processed or strongly impacted by life at work. The fuel powering our cruise is solar energy, stored in synced decayed living organisms. Even the snow over greenland, condensated for some of it, around black carbon nuclei from the russian arctic extraction activities⁵⁸

As demonstrated on Earth, the transformative power of life is extreme. It has become one if not the main driver in the modification of the structure and composition of the upper crust, oceans and atmosphere of our planet. Figures 3 and 4 are provided, for a synthetic consideration of what life on Earth is, and of what humans represent in this structure.

Fig 3. Biomass distributions across different trophic modes⁵⁹

In gigatons of carbon (GTC): 82% do collect the solar inbound flow, which is then distributed through the trophic networks alongside for the remaining

⁵⁵ Sum of GPP from NDVI models, with energy collected by man from fossil sources (84%), nuclear, (4%) hydroelectric (6%), eolian,(2%) photovoltaic (1%), and geothermia. (1%)

⁵⁶ [23] (Krausmann et al, 2013) [lobal human appropriation of net primary production ...](#)

⁵⁷ (Wings for Science, 2020) www.wingsforscience.com

⁵⁸ [24] (Zhu et al. 2020) [FLEXPART v10.1 simulation of source contributions to Arctic black carbon](#)

⁵⁹ [1] (Bar-On et al.2018) [The Biomass distribution on Earth](#)

Fig 4. Repartition of taxa, by biomass (GtC)⁶⁰
 In gigatons of carbon(GtC): humans represent 1/10.000 of the overall

B) Life, interpreted

Now with a consideration for the magnitude of the transformative action of living organisms on Earth, a sharper conceptualisation of what life is, is required for our discussion.

After an overview of the existing approaches ([B.1 On defining life](#)), the decision is taken to develop our own characterisation, outlining the transformative action, including life as we do not know it in the concept, and being inclusive regarding broader understandings of what life may be. This approach leads to the proposition that: “life is evolving, self-reproducing, transducing energy and converting its substrate”(B.2 Characterisation). The various aspects of this characterisation are then explored: self reproduction ([B.3 Self reproduction](#)), energy transduction and resource conversion ([B.4 energy transduction and resource conversion](#)), evolution ([B.5 Evolution](#)), and substrate ([B.6 Substrate](#)).

B.1 On defining life

Defining life is a research program by itself: from a philosophical standpoint, it has been attempted from the perspectives of animation (Aristotle), organisation (Kant), mechanism (Descartes), from the ones of emergent property of complex systems, and from the perspective

⁶⁰ [1] ([Bar-On et al.2018](#)) [The Biomass distribution on Earth](#)

of evolution (Darwin)⁶¹. Beyond sole philosophy, there are as many definitions as areas of interest. Biologists speak of homeostasis, physicians of a list of vitals, while some such as the astrophysicist Jean-Pierre Bibring, even consider that there is no sharp transition between the living and the non living. Life as we know it being a particular product of a track of evolution, amongst a very high quantity of possible ones, rendering the entire concept of life, totally useless.⁶²

As the question has troughly been addressed, it could have been tempting to use an existing characterisation. Amongst 123 inventoried definitions for life⁶³, the most instinctive pick could have been the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) astrobiological research definition: “life is a self-sustaining chemical system capable of Darwinian evolution”. Sadly, this proposition is found unsatisfactory, as it is extremely descriptive of the processes, and might consequently be totally off course regarding life as we do not know it. Considering life as we know it, it is not really satisfying either, for it forgets the rapid and ongoing developments of A-life⁶⁴, and the research toward autonomous self reproductive robots and general artificial intelligence, that might end up with the creation of a postbiological life not possibly being encompassed by the proposed definition.

No definition was found in the litterature, satisfying our needs. This led to the decision to develop our own characterisation.

B.2 Characterisation

The election of a clear conceptual characterisation of life is required for a fruitful discussion.

The proposed approach for tooling us with a working definition is instrumental:

First, we want to encompass in our conceptualisation, the possibility for life as we know it, life as we do not know it, and life on different substrates. This, because unknown life might be impacted by our decision, and transferring or magnifying our impact. To achieve this, we exclude a definition relying on the means by which the properties that make life are obtained: we want to be able to consider or recognise life when it is not forcefully using chemical, or

⁶¹ [25] [\(Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy 2018\) “life”](#)

⁶² [26] [\(Bibring 2020\) Interview at France Inter](#)

⁶³ [27] [\(Trifonov 2011\) Vocabulary of Definitions of life Suggests a Definition](#)

⁶⁴ [16] [\(Bedau 2007\) Artificial life](#)

metabolic processes. For the same reason, we exclude definitions based on the type of substrate.

Second, we want to clearly outline the impact related characteristics we need to consider when thinking about the release of its transformative action to larger scales: life is self reproducing, bearing the potential for exponential, explosive growth. Life is transforming, transducing energy, and converting the substrate it is building its structures from, bearing the potential for transformation until the exhaustion of limiting resources. Life is evolving, bearing the potential for unanticipated emergent properties, and self acceleration.

Then we want to be inclusive regarding what one considers life to be. There is indeed a large grey zone of things that depending on sensibilities, or research themes, may, or may not be considered as part of life on Earth. To some, the entire Earth geophysical system⁶⁵ civilisations⁶⁶, algorithms⁶⁷, genes⁶⁸, memes, viruses⁶⁹, ideas⁷⁰, thoughts⁷¹, simulations running on computers⁷², computer viruses, may be qualified as life, or part of life.

May we consider life on Earth and deprive it of suffering, intelligence, sensibilities, ideas ? When we are about to consider releasing life at astronomical scales, I propose that it would be unwise. Our proposition shall hence encompass these understandings, while being clear on the fundamental difference between these, and the more basic, life as understood from a biologist point of view. To achieve this delineation, we will rely on the substrate the envisioned life is build on, and see that not only this approach allows for a clean separation and the elimination of the grey zone, but also that it permits, for our purpose, to envision two categories, 1st order life, and higher order life, that are closely related to the way these may be distributed and propagated through space.

Taking into account these requirements, the below characterisation is proposed:

⁶⁵ [2] ([Lovelock and Margulis 1974](#)) [...] [The Gaia hypothesis](#)

⁶⁶ [28] ([Besley and Peters 2020](#)) [life and death in the Anthropocene...](#)

⁶⁷ [29] ([Blackwell 2009](#)) [Live Algorithms](#)

⁶⁸ [30] ([Dawkins 2016](#)) [The Selfish Gene](#)

⁶⁹ [31] ([Forterre 2010](#)) [Defining life: The Virus Viewpoint](#)

⁷⁰ [19] ([Sperber, 1996](#)). [La Contagion des idées](#). When viruses shall be considered alive, so may ideas

⁷¹ Noosphere, as per vernadsky's conception

⁷² [16] ([Bedau 2007](#)) [ARTIFICIAL life A-life Artificial life simulations](#)

Definition:

“life is evolving, self-reproducing, transducing energy and converting its substrate”

To which is added:

Not critical to argumentation, helpful to conceptualisation and fully developed in (B.6)

“First order life is autonomous”

“Higher order life requires its substrate to be produced by life of a lower order.”

To the minimal, consensual and linguistically identified definition: “life is self-reproduction with variations”⁷³, the above proposition adds energy-resource impact and classification by order.

By these definitions, the following elements will qualify as life : autotrophs (1st order), human beings (2nd order), human viruses, genes, memes, dependent A-life, civilisations, technologies, companies (3rd order), languages, noosphere (4th order). Life on Earth, being autonomous on the substrate of Earth, qualifies as life, and is 1st order, which is independent of the inclusion or not, of for example noosphere in the concept. Fully autonomous A-life would be 1st order. Interestingly, unknown life could be identified, and classified, with such an approach : “Bob !!! This is fascinating !!! This static thing from the mars samples⁷⁴, that you’ve had a spill onto your eye... it’s multiplying now, it is turning your eye into jelly ! it’s evolving to try and eat your brain too ! it’s alive Bob ! We’re the discoverers of extraterrestrial life, Bob, 2nd order !!!”.

B.3 Self-reproduction

What makes life primarily concerning is its capability to self reproduce, allowing for population growth in colonised volume, to follow exponential growth, only slowed by the exhaustion of limiting resources⁷⁵. As developed earlier⁷⁶, exponential developments are difficult for us to grasp. The mathematics are the same for explosions. When growth itself is not impairing resource access, a population doubling per time unit does convert the entire last half of its resource pool, within the given unit time. For illustration purpose, on figure 5 below is shown an exponential growth of bacteria E.Coli. The same duration (150 minutes) separates the three

⁷³ [27] (Trifonov 2011) Vocabulary of Definitions of life Suggests a Definition

⁷⁴ Soon to land in our P4 laboratories...

⁷⁵ [32] (Slavov et al. 2014) Constant Growth Rate...

⁷⁶ See: PREREQUISITES/Toolkit

pictures. What would be the maximal extent ? and speed ? of such a bloom, should life access to resources be extended in space ?

Fig 5. *E.coli* colony exponentially growing on microscope slide.⁷⁷

B.4 Energy transducing and resource conversion

Important to our understanding of possibilities is the necessary availability of energy for lifeforms to assemble and maintain their organisms. Looking again at the images above, the transformative power is obvious, reassembling the elements, and turning the entire substrate into something else. Energy is extracted from the environment for this chemical reassembly of elements to happen, which is partly stored in the transformed structure, and partly dissipated through heat, via metabolic activities, and due to inefficiencies. In the example above, once all glucose and ethanol have been converted, the colony dies. What happens when such processes go out of the test tube and colonise a planet is what we experience on Earth, except that on Earth, a constant flow of inbound energy is being offered by the Sun through photosynthetic activity, allowing for the populations to exponentially grow to what may then be sustained by this flow. Our concern is: what happens when the access may be given to the entire universe ? Is it likely to be transformed ? Also, the necessity of energy and resources is problematic when considering the extreme long duration involved in a possible space expansion, involving journeys far away from the energy flow from stars: can life survive, or somehow be put on stasis, to minimize its requirements on the way ?

⁷⁷ [33] (Stewart et al. 2005) [Aging and Death...](#)

B.5 Evolution

Evolution led on Earth to the emergence of encapsulated, interconnected systems of increasing complexity as described above, from ribonucleic acid (RNA) to cells, organites, organes, organisms, societies. Within this biosphere, sensations, sensibilities, intelligence and various levels of consciousness interact to produce a tremendous arsenal of physical productions that we call the technosphere, without reducing it to the human production⁷⁸, and an extraordinary universe of ideas, feelings, cultures⁷⁹ and moral representations that we call the noosphere, without reducing it to human thoughts. Interestingly, we must note that we have only hereby listed the emergent elements we are aware of, as humans. It is very likely that in a similar way to ants, which are not aware of the infinite possibilities of human poetry, we humans are not aware of the overall emergent properties our biodiversity might lead to at higher levels.

Understood as the change of frequency of properties amongst a population, including the possibility for emergent properties to appear along time, evolution is a critical element to our analysis: its observed biologic pace in pre-anthropic times, with shifts happening within millions of years, make it relevant to the times involved in possible interstellar expansion, where the closest galaxy is million light-years away, even when solely natural biological components of life are considered. When considering processes such as genetic engineering, culture, technology, societies, the property is even more important, due to their accelerating evolution pace being far quicker than the times of potential expansion in space. Evolution, the ultimate historical science, is something we humans have extreme conceptual difficulties with, when addressing possibilities, due to the emergent properties which are created through its process, and which we are today incapable of anticipating. Would you pretend to be able to forecast general intelligence in octopuses from looking at a plasmid ? Language from observing a rat looking mammal ? Computers from looking at hunters gatherers ? That within twelves years, mankind would go from sputnik to a man on the moon ? When looking at 19th century civilisation, that half of a 8 billion population of humans would actually have turned into informational cyborgs, powered up by their smartphones ? Me neither. Still, we have extreme issues, when conceptualising future times, not to forget that there are similar game changing properties to appear.

⁷⁸ [3] [\(Zalasiewicz et al, 2017\) Scale and diversity of the physical technosphere...](#)

⁷⁹ [34] [\(Lewens, 2018\) Cultural Evolution](#)

B.6 Substrate

For our argumentative purpose, a disambiguation is considered required, considering the envisioned substrate: we'll differentiate autonomous 1st order life, from substrate dependent higher orders of life.

1st order life, or simply "life" when unspecified, is in this text referring to life, on the most basic physical substrate, capable of creating itself from unprocessed elements. An isolated autotroph organism, capable of surviving and reproducing from a lone individual, would qualify as life. Also qualifies, an ecosystem containing the required primary producers, or required technological solution to feed higher level heterotrophs such as humans, allowing survival and exponential growth of the system given the availability of simple resources. As such, Earth Biodiversity as a whole may be interpreted as a 1st order form of life, while humans may not: they require a lower support ecosystem, and as such qualify as higher level.

Elements of life, higher orders of life, "life on life", substrate based life, or Xorder life are referring to things, *evolving, self-reproducing, transducing energy and converting substrate*, that cannot create themselves from unprocessed elements, and need a complex substrate to express themselves, being produced or having been produced by a lower order life. As such, heterotrophs such as humans, requiring a productive ecosystem to feed on, qualify as "life on life"(2nd order). societies, as *evolving* self-reproducing, transducing energy and converting the substrate of networked humans, do qualify as "life on life"(3rd order).

From this perspective, potential expression, and exponential transforming action may only happen given the adequate substrate is there upon arrival. When habitability as defined by exobiologists might be sufficient for first order life to exponentially grow, it is not the case for higher orders: either you have to spread the lower orders first or along, or you need to rely on potentially pre-existing ones, the ones of life, as we do not know it. A lone heterotroph spationaut is bound to die should not no appropriate 1st order life be present on arrival. To the contrary, a potential exponential impact could possibly follow the interstellar transmission of an idea (3rd order), given the proper intelligence network is there upon receipt, to decipher it

C) The resistance of life

Having envisioned life from its physical interactions (A), and defined it from the properties considered critical to our discussion (B), now is time to assess the hypotheses we made in

relation to its resistance. To proceed, we have first to overcome our natural tendency to project what we humans experience of life, on life as we know it. We will have to forget about the projection that life is fragile, short lived. This is largely untrue. 3 seconds of inattention, 3 minutes of air deprivation, 3 hours without a shelter, 3 days without water will kill you, individually. But eradicating life is an absolutely different story. In C.1, hypotheses on space resistance, will be envisioned the possible resistance of life to space specific constraints. In C.2 hypothesis on time resistance, will be explored the possibility for some lifeforms to sustain extremely long journeys in space, before the hypothesis regarding the survival of interstellar travel is addressed, in C.3 Hypothesis on interstellar travel.

C.1 Hypothesis on space resistance

Resisting to space per our understanding means resisting launch, space environment, reentry, and subsequent landing or crash. The duration of the flight itself may be extremely long and poses subsequent challenges, addressed in *time resistance*, just below.

Some forms of biological life, and life-related elements⁸⁰, are extraordinarily resistant. DNA has proven to survive the temperatures and acceleration of an entire spaceflight, from take-off to reentry, unprotected, on the outer shell of a rocket, sustaining gas temperatures of 1000°C⁸¹. Microbes⁸² to multicellular life, including nematodes have proven to be unharmed, and even reproducing, under 400.000 Gs up to 1 hour duration⁸³. Some spores, such as the ones of *Bacillus subtilis*, are demonstrated to survive crash-decelerations of up to a billion Gs⁸⁴.

Given the above, the hypothesis regarding the space resistance of some forms of life is considered credible. Including the possible survivability to uncontrolled landings or crashes, and the possible ejection of matter following a meteoritical impact on a planetary surface.

C.2 Hypothesis on time resistance

Again, forgetting our anthropocentric perspectives, life also may survive extreme lengths of times, if not infinitely. Lifeforms use energy to build the structure of their organisms, and then to maintain, and animate these. When the structure is built, maintenance and animation may be endless, as long as energy is available, and as long as senescence is nonexistent (which is the

⁸⁰ See glossary, [life-related elements](#)

⁸¹ [35] [\(Thiel et al. 2014\) Functional Activity of Plasmid DNA after Entry into the Atmosphere...](#)

⁸² [36] [\(Deguchi et al. 2011\) Microbial growth at hyperaccelerations up to 403.627 × g](#)

⁸³ [37] [\(Souza et al. 2018\) Caenorhabditis elegans Tolerates Hyperaccelerations up to 400.000 x g](#)

⁸⁴ [38] [\(Barney et al. 2016\) Survivability of bare, individual Bacillus subtilis spores...](#)

case for a range of microorganisms, and for viruses, for example) or may be overcome by a specific process as for the case of hydra, detailed below. This situation is referred to in the literature as biological immortality.

Gametes, stem cells⁸⁵, and cancer cells are biologically immortal. This property can even be induced artificially at the cell level⁸⁶. Then some bacteria and yeast also display this condition⁸⁷, as long as they are kept below certain stress levels. Constantly renewing its tissues, hydra could be such an organism, biologically immortal⁸⁸. Reverting aging and getting back to polyp stage to regrow from there, the medusa *turritopsis nutricula*⁸⁹ is another one. Even vertebrates, such as the naked mole rat⁹⁰ display this property of non-aging, entailing potential immortality.

When organisms do age, slowed metabolisms, or suspended animation may lessen or nullify the requirements for energy, and the degradation of the organisms. Extended survival times are achieved this way in the natural world, under states referred to as cryptobiosis, where all measurable metabolic activity stops, following a response to an adverse environment. Some forms of life may as such be “suspended” to cope with extended periods where energy is unavailable, to be reactivated when proper conditions are available. Sealed in closed environment, cultivable bacterias have proved to survive 500.000years⁹¹. More, microbial life from the seafloor, dated thanks to isotopic analysis, has been demonstrated to be capable of exponential growth after 100 million years of slowed down metabolism⁹². The recent discovery of slow metabolizing life inside rocks dated 3.5 billion years⁹³, while non-conclusive regarding the age of the identified lifeforms, sheds the question whether some of the earliest lifeforms we’ve had on the planet might have survived up to today. Lots is to be learned. Interestingly, DNA, when not encapsulated within a living organism, is found to have decaying time between 100kyr and 1myr. Oldest fossil dna being 1.4My old⁹⁴.

From our investigation, there is little doubt on whether natural or induced biological immortality, slowed or suspended animation may allow for extremely long interstellar flight, or waiting in a

⁸⁵ [Synthesis on \[39\] \(Saez et al. 2018\) Insights into the ubiquitin-proteasome system...](#)

⁸⁶ [\[40\] \(Rassoulzadegan et al. 1983\) Expression of the large T protein of polyoma virus...](#)

⁸⁷ [\[41\] \(Coelho et al. 2013\) Fission Yeast Does Not Age under Favorable Conditions....](#)

⁸⁸ [\[42\] \(Martínez 1998\) Mortality Patterns Suggest Lack of Senescence in Hydra](#)

⁸⁹ [\[43\] \(Piraino et al. 1996\) Reversing the life Cycle: Medusae...](#)

⁹⁰ [\[44\] \(Ruby et al. 2018\) Naked mole-rat mortality rates defy Gompertzian laws...](#)

⁹¹ [\[45\] \(Johnson et al. 2007\) Ancient bacteria show evidence of DNA repair...](#)

⁹² [\[46\] \(Morono et al. 2020\) Aerobic microbial life persists in oxic marine sediment as old as 101.5...](#)

⁹³ [\[47\] \(Lever et al. 2013\) Evidence for Microbial Carbon and Sulfur Cycling...](#)

⁹⁴ [\[48\] \(Kirkpatrick et al. 2016\) Fossil DNA persistence and decay in marine sediment...](#)

time capsule. More, what we've investigated here is the survival of organisms. When considering a live colony, with generation renewal, death might be absolutely acceptable on the way. DNA survival, in this perspective being better maintained within live organisms, than by itself.

When considering interstellar flight, far from stars, or time capsules. Access to energy is critical. From this perspective, the most interesting property might hence not be biological immortality, but the possibility to suspend energy consumption through suspended animation.

C.3 Hypothesis on interstellar resistance

Interstellar resistance is nothing but the combined hypothesis on space resistance with the one on time resistance, required to make it to destination. It is here added that there is a possibility that the considered resistance may be further increased by dedicated genetic engineering.

When life is considered as embarking not as a contamination but intentionally, its packaging may be extremely efficient: capsules 40 micron large may contain 100,000 microorganisms weighing altogether 0.1 micrograms.⁹⁵, meaning that a 1g payload such as planned per Breakthrough Starshot design, may carry a tera (1e12 of these). Every single one of these microorganisms provided autotrophy and landing in a suitable environment, bearing the capability of seeding an entire world.

D) life, as we do not know it

Life as we do not know it is important in our reasoning for its existence affects the typology and to some extent, the magnitude of the potential impacts of releasing life as we know it.

After characterizing life as we do not know it in D.1 Characterisation, the hypothesis on the existence of ETI is addressed (D.2 the hypothesis on the existence of ETI), and considered as extremely unsecured. Eventually, in D.3 A double sided knife, the ambivalence of the hypothesis is outlined, and the impact of its status on the conclusion of the kingmaker situation is considered as very important, from the perspective of the nature of the impacted elements within scope.

⁹⁵ [49] (Mautner 2000) Seeding the Universe with life: Securing Our Cosmological Future

D.1 Characterisation

life as we do not know it is here understood as being unknown: to the very extent of its existence. Life as we do not know it, should no life exist out there, might simply be “no life”.

Then should it exist, it could really be anything, from biologic life, DNA based, similar to us, to whatever imagination may picture, and beyond, as long as it satisfies the definition proposed in B.2 : “life is evolving, self-reproducing, transducing energy and converting its substrate”.

Life as we do not know it is in this essay manipulated exactly as life. And consequently, is interpreted similarly regarding the question of orders of life:

“First order life is autonomous” “Higher order life requires its substrate to be produced by life of a lower order.”, also apply to potential *extrasolar life*.

D.2 hypothesis on the existence of ETI

Investigating the hypothesis along which intelligent life (ETI) exists, capable of picking, and transducing information recovered from a signal, a time capsule or a spaceship, it is considered that intelligent, spacefaring life should it exist, would have no specific difficulty catching on our spaceships, opening a time capsule or deciphering our signals,

Then, the attempt to estimate reasonable probabilities regarding the distribution of life and intelligent life in the universe, is prone to extreme incertitudes, developed in *Annex IV, Scope, 5.B*. Ultimately, the related frequencies could be anywhere between zero and one. These cannot be exactly zero, otherwise we wouldn't be alive and we are. These shouldn't be exactly 1 either, otherwise we would have spotted life or intelligent life already⁹⁶. This consideration, referred to as Fermi's paradox, is at the center of a dense, and very postulative litterature, trying to logically solve the uncertainty by proposing possible scenarios explaining the observed absence⁹⁷. Very little more may be extracted from this absence in the search space, and all the inferences on frequencies related to it, are based on the assumption of some continuity of the would be distribution. Sadly this has no specific reason to be the case, especially when

⁹⁶ unless it was hiding...

⁹⁷ Such as : ET is sleeping so as to save energy for future time, so as to optimise efficiency, see [50] (Sandberg et al. 2017) That is not dead which can eternal lie: aestivation hypothesis...

abiogenesis⁹⁸ is rare, which is a possibility at this stage. To settle the question: I propose this drawing of mines:

Fig 6. The difficulty of inferring distributions out of non-exhaustive search spaces

As a consequence, extreme caution should be taken when considering the provided estimations involving life as we do not know it,

Despite this limitation, the decision leading to the calculation of possibly impacted lifeforms, intelligent lifeforms and related elements, was made considering the very large number of orders of magnitude by which we could be in error in our estimations, before the discussion loses meaning : as much as 14 (See II.D on the explored magnitude). It was considered that the obvious weakness of those estimations, was possibly to be compensated by the increased benefits for the reader, by making it easier to create a mental representation of what is at stake.

Given this environment, the provided estimates have nevertheless been chosen so as to be consistent with the SETI⁹⁹ discussion, and the literature related to the search for life. In the estimation proposed later, we consider frequencies of $1e-10$ per star for ETI, and $2e-3$ per star for ET. The properties chosen consistently for the “typical ET” and “typical ETI”, and the retained parameters for the drake equation, are detailed in *Annex IV Scope*.

⁹⁸ Abiogenesis is the hypothetical process by which life may emerge from a non living substrate.

⁹⁹ Search for Extraterrestrial Intelligence;

D.3 a double sided knife

Aside of being uncertain, the hypothesis of the existence of extrasolar life, has extremely ambivalent consequences on our discussion:

When extrasolar life exist, more paths are provided to the kingmaker situation¹⁰⁰, a substrate may be provided for higher orders of life as we know it to propagate through, preexisting networks and infrastructures may be used, and when informational lifeforms are considered¹⁰¹, their spread, through signals traveling at c , might happen to distances ranging to the event horizon. The kingmaker decision also becomes existential¹⁰², to this extrasolar life, for our decision may impair its survival. It also becomes existential to life as we know it, when considering that preexisting extrasolar life could perceive us as a potentially invasive threat to eradicate.

When extrasolar life is absent, the kingmaker situation is less probable, and first order life must be expanding before any higher order¹⁰³ may expand, to a much smaller flourishing space, limited by the required use of massive transmission, required by first order biological life to expand. When the maximal technological speed of seeding probes is considered to be 90% c , 70% of the volume within the event horizon is accessible. When 20% c is envisioned, this share drops to 0.8% (20% c is the target speed of Breakthrough Starshot). In the absence of extraterrestrial life, the kingmaker decision keeps its existential nature thanks to its relation to the mitigation of existential risk¹⁰⁴, and a fundamental difference is that when extrasolar life is absent, the kingmaker decision might generate a bloom at universal scale, which is not the case in the alternative option, where a bloom has already happened.

As a conclusion to these considerations, the uncertain hypothesis regarding the existence of extrasolar life may be interpreted as a double sided knife, whose eventual status does not impair the criticality of the scope encompassed by the kingmaker decision, while fundamentally

¹⁰⁰ 5 paths against 3, see [figure 2](#)

¹⁰¹ life, or life-related elements, may behold a material or informational nature. From the adopted definition (see Glossary), organisms, viruses, are material forms of life. Ideas, computer viruses, or simulated life, are of informational nature.

¹⁰² In this discussion, something is considered as existential to something else when one conditions the existence or absence of the other. (see Glossary)

¹⁰³ Within the retained framework, higher order life requires its substrate to be produced by life of a lower order. (See III.1B.6 Substrate)

¹⁰⁴ Existential risks may be mitigated by the multiplication of instances: it is much more difficult to eradicate life as we know it when it is established in multiple stellar systems, than when it is solely present in ours.

changing its nature. Last, it has to be envisioned that reality might be a mix of those two possibilities, with, just as drawn on the proposed [figure 6](#), pockets where this hypothesis is satisfied and spaces within which nothing is alive.

In Chapter 1. Life, of section III) HYPOTHESES, we have investigated the hypotheses regarding space, time, and interstellar resistance. To do so, we've proposed a working definition for life, allowing its characterisation and identification, before considering the hypotheses relevant to the kingmaker discussion, regarding resistance to time, space, and interstellar travel. Life as we do not know it was then characterised, and the hypothesis relating to its existence was addressed. Continuing with the assessment of the identified hypotheses supporting the conclusion of a kingmaker situation, we will be in the second chapter of section III, investigating the hypotheses related to extrasolar access.

PART III) HYPOTHESES

Chapter 2: Extrasolar access

Investigating in this chapter, the hypotheses relative to :

- Natural access
- Historical access

With reference to the work presented in:

- **Annex I Solar System**, addressing the question of defining the Solar System in adequation with the questions regarding the expansion of life.
- **Annex III History of Extrasolar Access**, exploring the potential impact life on Earth might have had historically out of the Solar System.

In this second chapter of section III) HYPOTHESES, we investigate the hypotheses related to the natural and historical access of life, as we know it on Earth, to the extrasolar space.

Natural access refers to the extrasolar access that is occurring naturally, naturally here meaning excluding the influence of humans.

Historical access refers to the integration of this natural access over the past history, to which is added the integrated access due to human intervention. Historical access refers as such to every possible access life as we know it on earth might have had along its history, including through the media of human intervention.

To proceed with the evaluation of these hypotheses we start by defining some physical boundaries for the solar system, relevant to our question of the diffusion of life, in **A) The Solar System, physically**, before envisioning it in **B) Habitability**, from the perspective of the evolution of its habitable zone, when defined as per the liquid water criteria.

The boundary of the extrasolar space being defined, a consideration is given in **C) Isolation**, onto what isolation means regarding the evolution of biologic systems, allowing us to consider the Solar System as a relevant unit to discuss with.

The hypothesis on natural then historical access are then investigated, in **D) Hypothesis on natural access** and **E) Hypothesis on historical access**, supported by the work presented in annex *Annex III History of extrasolar Access*, to conclude that the critical hypotheses of no natural nor historical access, may be considered as reasonably robust.

A) The Solar System, physically

According to NASA: “Our Solar System consists of our star, the Sun, and everything bound to it by gravity — the planets Mercury, Venus, Earth, Mars, Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus and Neptune, dwarf planets such as Pluto, dozens of moons and millions of asteroids, comets and meteoroids.”¹⁰⁵

As envisioned, “*life is evolving, self-reproducing, transducing energy and converting its substrate*”. Limits in relation to matter and energy are hence pertinent with respect to the requirements for life, as the Solar System may be conceived as a place where energy and ordinary matter as a substrate may be collected, and that can only be escaped with an input of energy.

From this perspective, the area of the influence of the Sun's gravity with respect to the neighbouring stars is meaningful to define practical spatial boundaries for the Solar System. This translates for the calculations and the discussion, to retain **3.25Ly**, as the radius of the Sun Surface of Influence (SOI) with respect to its closest stellar neighbour, Alpha Centauri, as the spatial boundary of the Solar System. As detailed in *Annex I Solar System*, where formulas, and alternative definitions are explored, with the chosen boundary the Sun is the main gravitational influence regarding all known and hypothesized orbiting objects, including the outermost Oort cloud, which are contained within this boundary. From the point of view of living organisms, and of interstellar navigation, this also delineates the volume inside which energy is required for escaping the solar influence.

This surface of influence is not static, and is dependent on the evolving mass of the Sun, progressively being reduced through mass energy conversion and solar winds. It also depends on the proximity of the other stellar systems in the solar neighborhood, which is changing over time, the spatial boundaries of the Solar System being consequently wobbling with stars passing-by, and reducing with its progressive loss of mass.

On long futures, the flyby, or even flythrough¹⁰⁶ of stellar systems from stellar neighborhood along our orbiting path in the galaxy, and during the merger to happen between our galaxy and M31 galaxy, then M33 galaxy, is segregating two classes of evolution for our system:

¹⁰⁵ [51] [\(NASA 2020\) Our Solar System in depth](#)

¹⁰⁶ When considering the current SOI radius 3.25Ly

When exchanges with the galactic environment are relatively insignificant, exiting its main sequence out of hydrogen, the Sun will start burning helium, turn into a red giant, and expand to engulf all the inner planets, and possibly Earth, within an accelerated expansion happening 5-7 billions years from now. This expansion is ending with an explosive event, the helium flash, happening in the core of the star. The Sun will then suddenly contract, and enter a series of pulses leading to an explosion as a planetary nebula. Eventually, our star will collapse into a white dwarf, 50% of the mass of the actual Sun, whose luminosity will only be fueled by the remaining thermal energy, eventually cooling down.

Alternative, exotic possibilities, consequential to potential short range interaction with stellar systems flying by, are endless. With a probability to happen of 1-2% per billion year, hence of about 30% along the 15Gyr of habitability of the system as explored just below, these may lead to anything from a simple orbit alteration for a planet, to comet showers related to the disturbance of the Oort cloud, to life bricks or lifeforms hopping from one system to the other, or the gravitational binding of stars potentially leading to supernovas, not forgetting the low but existing probability of frontal collisions. The related probabilities are explored in a simple way in *Annex I Solar System*.

B) Habitability

Multiple definitions exist regarding habitable zone¹⁰⁷(HZ), and what has mainly been investigated relates to “biologic, first order life as we know it”. Life as we do not know it, ie artificial, or extraterrestrial biological life, might have absolutely different environmental constraints, some hypothesis even leading to the conclusion that artificial, silicon based life, would favor near zero kelvin temperature due to the increased efficiency at these temperatures¹⁰⁸. In the below discussion, the habitable zone is defined as the volume within which liquid water may exist at the surface of celestial bodies, a volume which shall consequentially be understood as the lower bound for where life, generally speaking, may develop or be sustained.

From the perspective of survivability, for life as we know it, as investigated in detail in *Annex I Solar System*, three main continuous periods have to be distinguished, separated in time by cataclysmic events, problematic for any lifeform to survive, but between which new

¹⁰⁷ [52] ([Horneck & Baumstark-Khan 2002](#)) *Astrobiology - the quest for the conditions of life* p47

¹⁰⁸ [50] ([Sandberg et al. 2017](#)) *That is not dead which can eternal lie: aestivation hypothesis...*

ecosystems may develop in an habitable zone when defined by liquid surface water, which we will consider as a good proxy for discussion the survival of life as we know it. Figure 7 is proposed as a summary of those phases, a,d shows the evolution of the habitable zone with time.

Fig 7. The three main phases for the habitable zone in the Solar System

With the surface liquid water criteria, separated by cataclysmic events note: according to the above simple estimation, over the 15gy ahead, this scenario holds a +70-85% probability, the 15-30% remaining being a wide range of possible exotic futurs, driven by interactions with other stellars systems, amplified, 5.8gy ahead, by the merger with M31 then M33 galaxy.

Solar System 1.0, the one we are living in, where life will be sustainable for 7 another billion years or so provided it migrates outbound with an accelerating pace, from the current habitable zone located 0.8-1.1 AU from the Sun, across to the extreme limits of the Kuiper belt, following the growth of the Sun as a red giant. Solar System 1.0 is doomed to a cataclysmic end due the helium flash, resetting the habitable zone back to 7-10 AU.

Solar System 2.0 The eye of the cyclone, a short period ranging between 0.1 and 1Gy, in between the asymptotic helium flash, and the pulsing phase of the asymptotic giant.

Solar System 3.0, Where life will be sustainable for further billions of years, should there be a celestial body or support for it, within a smaller slowly shrinking habitable zone, lasting 7 billion years and ultimately bounded by the tidal disruption due to the proximity of the star, when the habitable zone surface freezing limit is reduced to about 0.005AU.

C) Isolation

When the rate of exchanges with the outside is high with regards to the time for evolution, the evolution may not be considered as independent of this outside. On Earth, this effect is well documented thanks to the changes induced by globalisation¹⁰⁹: above a certain level, the rate of interaction between ecosystems may no more be neglected, those may no more be conceived as isolated, and the global ecosystem has to be considered.

We propose that the same logic might apply to the spatial isolation at the scale of the solar system. Biologic evolution takes thousands to millions of years to happen. While it might be considered that the pace of exchanges in the past, between Earth and the other bodies of the Solar System, has been slow in comparison to this, and hence that Earth has had an isolated biologic evolution, this is changing.

The current rate of exchanges within the Solar System is 10 to 20 new missions a year i.e. 20 million/Myr. This does not mean that every mission is going to transfer microorganisms, to survivable places, but it is significant enough to challenge the idea along which Earth might be considered as biologically isolated from the rest of the Solar System. Next steps are terraforming or colonisation missions. Those are on the calendar, with consequent budget, SpaceX mogul, E.Musk, explicitly targeting the creation of a million people colony on Mars, with an assumed disconsideration for any form of planetary protection¹¹⁰. The rate of exchange is already high, and is going to accelerate in the years to come, if plans come to end.

Our discussion considers large timescales. The terrestrial or not-terrestrial value of life as we know it has started to lose its meaning, and this is accelerating.

¹⁰⁹ [53] (Mooney and Cleland 2001) The evolutionary impact of invasive species

¹¹⁰ See answer to NASA in "2019 Starship Update" Video.

This is the reason why we are choosing the Solar System boundaries as the reference for this discussion, for which the interaction rate with the outside today keeps small, in comparison to the rate for biological evolution (one stellar flyby every 80.000 years). When considering that life as we know it on Earth is about to become extrasolar, this is what is referred to: in the discussed possible near term future, where Breakthrough Starshot is operational, the rate of biologic interaction with the extrasolar space is bound to increase dramatically, overtaking the time for evolution. The Solar System originated life, will become extrasolar.

D) Hypothesis on natural access

Investigating hypothesis on natural access: life has little to no natural possibility of interstellar access

Interstellar panspermia, as the concept of free ranging spores, organisms, or elements of, being transferred through space, is a possibility that has been considered for long, and which today may not be ruled out regarding the origin of life on Earth. Allowing the spread of life through the universe, it could account for a high frequency of life in the universe, even when the probability of abiogenesis is low.¹¹¹ The very recent identification on Earth, of microbes surviving for millions of years¹¹², metabolizing extremely slowly, from the elements inside the rocks they live in, give a particular credit to a range of hypotheses called lithopanspermia: bits of rocks being ejected following collisions, protecting and feeding the microbes for their million year journeys through space.

The below possibilities are identified for natural interstellar access:

Some lifeforms, capable of surviving direct head on collision of a billion Gs¹¹³ could survive a collision happening inside the Solar System, and be embarked on materials being expelled with speeds in excess of the Solar System escape speed. It is agreed that about one third of planetary ejecta following collisions, eventually escape the Solar System¹¹⁴.

Also, life could be living, or in revivable state (cryptobiosis) on a substrate, comet, asteroid, planet, being expelled through gravitational interactions. Models show that planets as big as neptune have possibly been expelled like this in the past.

¹¹¹ [54] ([Sadlok 2020](#))[...] [Interstellar life Transfer Trough Nomadic Objects](#)

¹¹² See [III\) Chapter1.C The resistance of life.](#)

¹¹³ [38] ([Barney et al. 2016](#)) [Survivability of bare, individual Bacillus subtilis spores...](#)

¹¹⁴ [55] ([Melosh 2003](#)) [Exchange of Meteorites \(and life?\) Between Stellar Systems](#)

Then the ejecta of the carrying body could fracture and the remaining particles be ejected through radiation pressure from the star.

Any combination of the three system may be envisioned, with for example shorter range, interplanetary lithopanspermia seeding an object before it is being expelled, or even a free ranging object such as a rogue planet¹¹⁵

For interstellar transfer to be achieved, though, the expelled object has to be eventually collected. And here is the main issue: most of the spatial environment is empty: which leads to probability of random ejection to eventually reach a gravitational influence strong enough to capture the object and induce its collection, and eventual arrival on a planet or a moon, to be extremely small. Indeed, with a rate of extrasolar ejection, calculated to be as of 15 rocks bigger than 10 cm, from planetary ejecta, going extrasolar, per year¹¹⁶, the probability of one meteorite size object to be collected following such an ejection in the Solar System, is calculated to be of 1 per billion years. As a consequence from this analysis, the natural transfer processes possibly occurring between stellar systems are considered to more probably happen from direct interactions between systems, like for example when one of the average 12 systems per million years, flies through - our current SOI.

By the investigated literature, natural interstellar exchange of lifeforms is considered to be slow, if ever happening. When happening, it is considered to probably take place by hopping between flying by systems, rather than through long interstellar flights. As such, the hypothesis is considered reasonably secured, that no, or close to no natural access occurs, of lifeforms from the solar system, to naturally reach out to the extrasolar space.

E) Hypothesis on historical access

Investigating “life has had no historical possibility of interstellar access”

The history of potential extrasolar access is extensively detailed in *Annex III History of extrasolar access*, including a proposed listing of intentional electromagnetic transmissions (METI), and the presentation of the detailed methodology leading to the numbers below. Here is a synthesis of this work developed in annex.

Mankind has elaborated theoretical communication and travelling systems, with ranges far beyond the Solar System. This, not only from the perspective of space, via theoretical

¹¹⁵ [54] (Sadlok 2020)[...] Interstellar life Transfer Trough Nomadic Objects

¹¹⁶ [55] (Melosh 2003) Exchange of Meteorites (and life?) Between Stellar Systems

spaceships¹¹⁷ and electromagnetic beams¹¹⁸ capable of intergalactic range, but also from the perspective of time, with time capsules designed to last more than $1.40e+10$ years¹¹⁹, a duration longer than the age of the universe itself, and billions of years beyond the most optimistic estimations for the duration of the Solar System itself. As incredible as can be, these theoretical extrasolar activities have made their debuts:

If the first interstellar messages like the one from Arecibo in 1974, have been mainly sent to spark a debate, it appears that today, we are transmitting to identified extrasolar planets only light-years away, messages engineered to be understood, and specifically intended to test the possible presence of extraterrestrial intelligence¹²⁰, this, not forgetting that beyond the omnidirectional untargeted and low power emissions of our telecommunication systems, whose overall power has been increasing since the debuts of wireless telegraphy, today's radar tracking system might have a way wider impact¹²¹.

Our farthest ranging probes, Voyager probes 1 & 2, launched in 1977 are just past the heliosphere. While the media has largely claimed otherwise, this physical limit, set by solar activity, is irrelevant to space travel. The travelled distance is still well within the gravitational limits of the Solar System (SOI= 3.25Ly).

Incidental time capsules such as the geological layer of the anthropocene, will be conserved for billions of years on Earth¹²². Intentional ones, have been developed and produced: conceived for withstanding billions of years. One of these has survived a crash on the Moon¹²³, which was containing presumably revivable extremophiles organisms, and human DNA samples.

Historical opportunities

So as to evaluate the extrasolar impacts that Solar System originated life might have had, including considering the human intervention, we propose to compare the amount of possibly impacted stellar environments, with the maximal amount of stars, reachable by causal processes originating in the Solar System, as limited by today's event horizon. This maximal amount of stars will be here below noted S^∞ , as an abbreviated form of $S(\Omega^\infty)$, where Ω^∞ is the

¹¹⁷ [7] ([Breakthrough Initiatives 2020](#)) [Starshot](#).

¹¹⁸ [11] ([Lubin 2016](#)) [Implications of Directed Energy for SETI](#), considering Starshot Laser.

¹¹⁹ [8] ([Arch Mission Foundation, 2020](#)) [5D Optical Memory Crystal](#).

¹²⁰ [56] ([SONAR CALLING, 2020](#))

¹²¹ [57] ([Zaitsev 2008](#)) [Detection Probability of Terrestrial Radio Signals by a Hostile Super-civilization](#)

¹²² [3] ([Zalasiewicz et al, 2017](#)) [Scale and diversity of the physical technosphere...](#)

¹²³ [8] ([Arch Mission Foundation, 2020](#)) [The Lunar Library](#)

set of conditions corresponding to unlimited technological development. In this set, the maximal speed of all causal processes is considered to be the speed of light, c , and the maximal range of those processes will be considered to be the event horizon. *Annex II de Sitter Model* is used to perform this calculation, leading to $S^\infty = 1.7e+21$ stars within the event horizon, which represent 2% of the observable universe.

When relevant, the quantity of potentially impacted extraterrestrial lifeforms noted nET and intelligence noted $nETI$ are given as well as the fraction this number represents, against the total estimated quantity of ET or ETI within the event horizon, noted: ET^∞ and ETI^∞ . To compute these quantities, the frequency of ET was considered to be of $2e-3$ per star, and the one of ETI, of $1e-10$ per star. Those estimates related to ET and ETI are only given as representational purposes and susceptible of extreme uncertainties, while chosen so as to be coherent with the SETI literature and the recent observations¹²⁴. See *Annex IV Scope/IV*, for details. The below is a synthesis of the work performed in *Annex III Historical Access*.

Signals

With technology similar to ours, since its birth ~ 4.5 billion years ago, the presence of Earth in the habitable zone could have been picked up by the entire galaxy, counting 100-400 billion stars, accounting for less than $\sim 2e-10$ of the total amount of stars within event horizon ($\sim 2e-10S^\infty$), and counting less than 40 stars occupied by intelligent ET. In present times (last 25.000 years), the presence of Earth in the habitable zone could have been picked up by about a quarter of the galaxy (25-100 billion stars, $nETI < 10$, $\sim < 5e-11ETI^\infty$,).

Similarly, the indications of life on Earth could have been noticed for 3.5 billion years, by a \sim billion stellar systems ($\sim 6e-13 ETI^\infty$, $nETI < 0.1$), from atmospheric biomarkers in observed transits, and in present time (last 5400 years), from about a million of these ($\sim 6e-16 ETI^\infty$, $nETI < 1e-3$), more probably from direct observation.

The indication of intelligent life on Earth started leaking as electromagnetic transmissions about 100 years ago. The maximal signals are the one of over the horizon radars, and of satellite tracking radars. With a square kilometer array telescope (SKA) pointing at us, these could have been picked up 50-325 Ly away, from 1000-241.000 stars. ($\sim < 1e-16 ETI^\infty$)

Amongst the 38 identified METI signals, it is estimated that only 9 are of significant conception and magnitude, and could be picked up, should intelligent life be looking at it with a SKA

¹²⁴ [58] [\(Tremblay and Tingay 2020\) A SETI survey \[...\]Orders of magnitude expansion in search space](#)

telescope, for the duration of their broadcast ($\sim 5e-21$ ETI ∞). The above envisioned causal access from the Solar System out, is nullified in the hypothesis where we have been the sole intelligent life out there, up to now. Should intelligent ET exist, chances are that less than 40 of these know about the habitability of Earth. The probability is less than 10% that one ETI knows about life on Earth. The probability that one ETI has captured our electromagnetic leakage and knows regarding intelligent life on Earth, is less than a thousand of a percent. The chances that it has picked one of our METI (Messaging Extraterrestrial Intelligence) signals, is about one in a billionth. Should we consider that ET development is more or less parallel to ours and that its technological capabilities are recent (last 5400 years), reduces the quantity of ET knowing about habitability of Earth, to 10, and the probability of anybody knowing about life on Earth to $1e-5$.

Massive transmitters

With ~ 54.000 stellar systems flying through the Solar System as defined from the Oort cloud boundaries (3.25Ly), along its 4.5Gy of existence, with a $\sim 5\%$ probability of one of these flying within the Kuiper belt¹²⁵, it is reasonable to consider that some collision or ejection has possibly occurred. The ejection of comets and materials from the oort cloud might have happened, that could have contained bricks or forms of life originated in the Solar System. More, giant planets the size of Uranus or Neptune, could have been expelled from our system¹²⁶. Worse case, considering that exchanges have systematically happened with the systems flying through, we get to 54.000 impacted stellar environments ($\sim 3 \times 10^{-17} S^\infty$, QETI < 6e-6).

On spaceship side, the only four probes with extrasolar ambitions are traveling at desperately slow speeds (<0,006% of c) with reference with the interstellar scales, and have ~ 50.000 years ahead minimum before becoming extrasolar from a gravitational point of view. At this stage, no spacecraft has achieved any extrasolar opportunity.

Time Capsules

Even at lightspeed, travelling takes time. More, traveling through time, hence surviving, is by itself a prerequisite to any possible distant impact. Specifically, time capsules are to be considered, which do represent a credible transmitter for extrasolar causality, in the hypothesis of existing extraterrestrial intelligence. It is to be noted, that with the proposed separation of the Solar System into three consecutive livable periods separated by cataclysmic events, as

¹²⁵ See III/Hypotheses,C) [Solar System](#)

¹²⁶ [59] [\(Nesvorný 2011\) YOUNG Solar System's FIFTH GIANT PLANET?](#)

proposed in C) Solar system, and detailed in *Annex 1 Solar System*, time capsules may also represent ways of communication across cataclysms and allow a communication or an expansion between Solar System 1.0, 2.0, and 3.0 or through similar phases of any stellar environment.

None of the 14000K+ earthbound time capsules, geological markers, fossils or artifacts built on Earth has any chance of surviving the Sun's red giant phase, should it engulf Earth, something science is unsure about. Should it not engulf it, it is going to be extremely close to do so, and Earth will accordingly turn in a lava ocean, leaving no trace of the life on Earth, for post helium flash archeologists to investigate.

Time capsules orbiting Earth will very likely be destroyed as such, and so will the ones with orbits closing to the Sun at or closer than 1 AU, including -sadly- the arch mission foundation library installed in the transmartian Tesla.

Still, humans have built and flown a large array of robots to the outer regions of the Solar System, and it may be envisioned that remains of some kind, do withstand the +7Gy shock, and why not, the potential planetary nebula to follow. From this perspective, there is a chance that some consequence of life in Solar System 1.0, connects with 2.0 (beyond helium flash) and 3.0 (white dwarf). A strategy which might be interesting to investigate in such a perspective, could be to park a backup time capsule at the L2 lagrange point of a planetoid in the outer region, so as for it to be shielded by the planetoid, from the solar related events.

Synthesis on historical extrasolar access

If Earth is probably known as possibly habitable by a few ETI in the galaxy, should these exist, we can be affirmative about the very seldom probability of anybody knowing that life, let to say intelligent life, is there.

The maximal extrasolar impact from life as we know it might have been through exchanges of asteroid, comets or even planets with flying-by stellar systems, and our interstellar probes shall not yet be considered extrasolar, for these will be under the Sun's major gravitational influence for another ~50.000 years.

Of the produced timecapsules and of the time defying elements life as we know it is leaving behind, none is likely to withstand the end of the Sun's red giant phase, but some of the remains of automatic robots in the outer Solar System, and life itself, should it be lurking in a place

survivable to the events to come, such as the kuiper belt, could come to survive this and connect with the future environment of the post red giant Sun.

As a consequence of this analysis, with an overall maximal potential historical impact inferior to 0.2 billionth of the stellar systems within the event horizon, ($2e-10ETI^\infty$, from the information that Earth is in the habitable zone), should intelligent ET exist, and of ($\sim 3e-17S^\infty$, from the possible exchanges with flying by stellar systems), should it not exist, we can conclude that life as we know it has had up to now, a negligible impact onto the extrasolar space. The hypothesis on historical access is found credible.

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In Chapter 2. Extrasolar access, of section III) HYPOTHESES, we have been exploring the hypotheses regarding the extrasolar access that life as we know it on Earth might have, without the influence of humans, and might have had, including the human contribution, overall its past 4.5 billion years of history. To do so we've defined the Solar System boundaries with reference to our theme of life expansion, spacewise, with a SOI at 3.25ly, and timewise, with three separated periods of habitability, which we've named solar system 1.0, 2.0 and 3.0, that we propose to conceptualise as separated from each other. Then, after a consideration regarding the meaning of isolation when considering evolving species, the work performed in Annex I, Solar System, addressing the question of defining the Solar System in adequation with the reflexion regarding the expansion of life, and the one proposed in Annex III History of extrasolar Access, investigating the potential impact life on Earth might have had historically out of the Solar System, were synthesized.

This led to the conclusion that today, life has little to no opportunity of interstellar access excluding the intervention of humans, while historically, including the human contribution, the possibility that an extrasolar access occurred may be considered as remote.

Continuing with the assessment of the identified hypotheses supporting the conclusion of a kingmaker situation, we will in the third and last chapter of section III, be investigating the hypotheses considered as mainly relating to humans.

PART III) HYPOTHESES

Chapter 3: Humans

Investigating in this chapter, hypotheses relative to :

- Interstellar signaling: interstellar communication systems are developed.
- Time capsules: time capsules are developed.
- Interstellar travel: interstellar probes or spaceships are developed.
- Boarding: some life Forms may be embarked intentionally, incidentally, or malevolently, on a probe or a spaceship made by man, and life related information, such as ideas, technologies, computer virus, genetical codes may be transmitted via onboard information systems, or signals
- Technological civilisation: the odds of survival of our technological civilisation
- Irreversibility: control may not be exerted on life out of the Solar System

After having developed hypotheses regarding life (III.1.Life), and its natural and historical extrasolar access (III.Extrasolar Access), this last chapter of section III) HYPOTHESES, is exploring the conditions considered as mainly relating to humans.

To proceed, we first in (A) Breakthrough-type technologies, detail what is referred to when considering near term technologies, considered realistically operating 20 years ahead. Amongst these, we focus on the perspectives offered by Breakthrough Starshot model (A.1), and reinforced by recent strategies for photo gravitational assist, amongst which a proposition by the author (A.2). The potential signaling power of the Breakthrough Starshot laser is envisioned (A.3). Cost considerations, and contextual elements, (A.4) will give us an indication on the reasonability of Breakthrough Starshot goals (A.5), informing our hypotheses regarding interstellar signaling an interstellar travel, the question of time capsules being settled by the achievements of the Arch Mission Foundation. (A.6)

The technological hypotheses being considered as realistic in the near term, the critical question of incidental, intentional, or malevolent boarding of life or life-related elements, onto our soon to come probes, signals or time capsules, is addressed, in B) Hypothesis on Boarding. The question of the survival of civilisation is investigated, in C) Hypotheses on technological

civilisation, and the reversibility by humans means, of the process of incidentally, intentionally or malevolently seeding a world is questioned in D) Hypothesis on irreversibility.

A) Breakthrough-type technologies

In this discussion, we refer to Breakthrough-type technologies, as technologies possibly mature in the near term. The set of retained technologies is: Breakthrough Starshot project, promising laser propelled probes traveling at 20%*c* within a generation¹²⁷, light sails allowing 20%*c* on long range trajectories¹²⁸ without the support of a laser¹²⁹, and the already prototyped Arch Mission Foundation time capsules, designed to last 10e14yr¹³⁰. These technologies, considered possibly mature 20 years ahead, are referred to as Breakthrough-type, or near-term technologies.

A.1 Breakthrough Starshot

Breakthrough Starshot project targets a 20 years development time, to engineer swarms of nano crafts, “the cost of an iphone”, capable of 20% of the speed of light, being accelerated thanks to 10 minutes pulses from an Earth bound Laser, pushing on a meter scale light sail. Crafts would be sent as swarms to provide “redundancy and coverage”, and communicate back using radio transmission. The design case is a mission to the Alpha Centauri system. At such a speed, no braking would be possible upon arrival, and no flight back to Earth either. The mission would hence have feedback sent to Earth via radio, with the assumed goal of providing Yuri Milner with pictures of Centauri planets, within a generation lifetime, guaranteed by the 40 years timeframe for the project: 20 years for development, 20 years for the mission. The reached hyperbolic excess speed of 99,96%¹³¹ of 20%*c*, is way above all local escape speeds¹³². While eventually offering no more feedback due the distance overtaking the radio feedback limit, those probes, if they are not crashed or self destructed, will possibly be initiating some very long journeys.

¹²⁷ [9] ([Parkin 2018](#)) [The Breakthrough Starshot system model](#),

&[11] ([Lubin 2016](#)) [Implications of Directed Energy for SETI](#),

¹²⁸ Detailed III.E) [Strategies for photo gravitational assist](#)

¹²⁹ [12] ([Heller et al. 2017](#)) [Optimized trajectories to the nearest stars...](#)

&[13] ([Heller and Hippke 2017](#)) [Deceleration of High-velocity Interstellar Photon Sails...](#)

¹³⁰ [14] ([Arch Mission Foundation, 2020](#)) [5D Optical Memory Crystal](#).

¹³¹ Calculated using the formulae presented in *Annex IV Scope, 4, a)*

¹³² See *Table 1. Estimated escape velocities, from the gravitational wells Earth is bound to, with reference to Earth position* in *Annex IV Scope*

Regarding the transmission of life or life related elements, I propose the below analysis, by phase of flight:

Launch: The 10.000g launch acceleration for ten minutes could be sustained by a range of organisms, from microbes¹³³ to multicellular life, including nematodes unharmed by equivalent 400.000g up to 1 hour duration (1 to 10.000g in 10seconds)¹³⁴. Some spores, such as the ones of bacillus subtilis, are demonstrated to survive crash-accelerations of up to a billion Gs¹³⁵(while probably not reproducing in the meantime !)

Enroute: During the flight, I propose that ETI may identify the object, and even intercept it. The Oumuamua case is a practical reflexive application of this possibility. indeed, this interstellar traveler has in our example been interpreted due to its trajectory, as a being a possible ETI lightsail¹³⁶, and a scaledown of Breakthrough Starshot has been considered as a viable option to chase it and collect information on it¹³⁷.

Crash: Research is ongoing regarding the survivability of crash for microbial and multicellular life. The highest tested hard surface impact speed identified in the literature review¹³⁸, while showing survival of the bacillus subtilis spores impacting glass, unprotected, in the vacuum, at 0.3km/s, is still a 200 million time slower than the considered 20%c. It is assumed that a crash from the reached 20%c would not leave any surviving live contamination, nor usable information.

Capture: At 20%c, only extremely massive celestial bodies such as black holes would possibly capture the probe.

Slowing down slowly: Eventually the probes will be slowly naturally braking in relation with the traversed environment, due to the expansion of the universe, as a function of $\exp(-Ht)$ (this being envisioned as a handy way to save fuel, in some interstellar strategies)¹³⁹, due to momentum transferred from dust, or possibly because of the effect of dilatant vacuum (to such an extent that it might render starshot unsuccessful, should the probes be too light)¹⁴⁰.

Ultimately, the horizon due to the expansion of the universe limits the maximal range of such probes, and of the possibilities offered by life on the way, which for 20%c is calculated to be

¹³³ [36] ([Deguchi et al. 2011](#)) [Microbial growth at hyperaccelerations up to \$403.627 \times g\$](#)

¹³⁴ [37] ([Souza et al. 2018](#)) [Caenorhabditis elegans Tolerates Hyperaccelerations up to \$400.000 \times g\$](#)

¹³⁵ [38] ([Barney et al. 2016](#)) [Survivability of bare, individual Bacillus subtilis spores...](#)

¹³⁶ [60] ([Bialy and Loeb 2018](#)) [Could Solar Radiation Pressure Explain 'Oumuamua's...](#)

¹³⁷ [61] ([Hein et al. 2019](#)) [Project Lyra \[...\] along with Breakthrough project position on this.](#)

¹³⁸ [38] ([Barney et al. 2016](#)) [Survivability of bare, individual Bacillus subtilis spores...](#)

¹³⁹ [62] ([Sandberg 2018](#)) [Space races: settling the universe fast](#)

¹⁴⁰ [63] ([Fedi 2019](#)) [Starshot Failure](#)

2.6e9Ly, using a de Sitter model¹⁴¹, which is to be understood as the limit range for probes using Breakthrough Starshot level technology.

A.2 Strategies for photo gravitational assist

Amongst the research work incentivized by the project (Starshot is cited by 528 research papers)¹⁴² objections on technical and theoretical feasibility have arisen, as well as fascinating ideas. The use of lightsail nano crafts have been extensively explored, and the combined options offered by gravity assist, photonic braking, and electrodynamic braking have been investigated thoroughly, with the goal of expanding starshot potentiality, opening extremely interesting options for lightsails with a surface mass sufficiently low and using astucious trajectories. The surfacic mass (σ) for the calculations below is of $\sigma_{nom} = 8.6 \times 10^{-4}$ gram m^{-2} , which is realistic with graphene sails (although graphene will be problematic due transparency). Travel times for different σ values scale as $\sqrt{\sigma/\sigma_{nom}}$.¹⁴³ The proposed strategies below originate from the same paper.

Laserless launch: by combining gravitational assist, and light sail navigation, without the need for a square kilometer expensive array of lasers, sails may be launched from the Solar System, up to speeds of 4.6% c , with a minimal input of energy (the conventional spaceship to take it to near Earth orbit), the major part of the acceleration being powered by the radiation pressure from the star, combined with the use of gravity assist.

Photogravitational hub: very luminous stars may be used so as to decelerate, and reaccelerate in any chosen direction. In the solar neighborhood, Sirius A (24 L_{\odot}), 9 ly away, is such a star. It is reachable within 180 years from a laserless launch from Earth (69 years with laser assist), and could be navigated to decelerate a sail from as high as 12% c , and reaccelerate it to any direction to such a speed. “Sirius A with its huge luminosity and relative proximity to the Sun is the most natural choice for an interstellar photogravitational hub for humanity.”

Stellar afterburner, and braking: very important boosts in speed, up to 9% c , or equivalent decelerations, may be achieved by flying by luminous stars such as sirius A, with trajectory deviations up to 20°, a process referred as “afterburner”

¹⁴¹ See *Annex II De Sitter Model*

¹⁴² as per 23/09/20, request from [google scholars](#)

¹⁴³ [12] ([Heller et al. 2017](#)) [Optimized trajectories to the nearest stars...](#)

& [13] ([Heller and Hippke 2017](#)) [Deceleration of High-velocity Interstellar Photon Sails...](#)

Chained navigation: using the investigated possibilities, I propose the following strategy for very long range navigation, depicted on figure 8, below. Once the direction of exploration has been set using a departure hub (minimal time to closest hub is 69years, laser assist to Sirius A, or 180 years, laserless launch), a chain of luminous stars may be chosen in the 20° cone to destination, and used, first to accelerate further to relativistic speeds, then to brake down to the maximal injection speed to the arrival hub (12%*c* for a sirius A type star), the arrival hub being then used to redirect the probe to the target, while slowing it to the required injection speed at destination. Such a strategy allows for travel to happen at speeds higher than 20%*c*, while permitting braking upon arrival, the use of an arrival hub allowing the deceleration to very low speeds, which is of peculiar interest when the target has little luminosity. When contacted by email, Pierre Kervella, contributor to the article on photo gravitational assist, confirmed the theoretical feasibility of this.

Fig 8. Near term interstellar navigation using photon sails

As proposed by the author from the perspectives opened by [12] & [12][13][12]¹⁴⁴

¹⁴⁴ [12] (Heller et al. 2017) Optimized trajectories to the nearest stars...
 & [13] (Heller and Hippke 2017) Deceleration of High-velocity Interstellar Photon Sails...

First possible stages of a long range interstellar navigation:

Solar System -> Sirius A, 24Ls, 4,6%c, 8.6Ly, 180yr (69 with Laser)

Deceleration and reacceleration to 12%c

Sirius A -> Procyon A, 7Ls, 12%c, 5.2Ly, 43yr

Stellar boost +5%c, to 17%c

As seen here, in 220 years, (110 with laser assist), including a trajectory reorientation through a “hub”, and a reacceleration, a sail is possibly heading to destination at 17%c

Enroute compensation for deceleration. The “afterburner” technique may also be used to compensate for decelerations related to dust, dilatant vacuum¹⁴⁵, or, on a very long range, due to the expansion of the universe. At speeds around 20%c, the expansion of the universe starts to have noticeable effects (+1% on travel time)¹⁴⁶ at distances farther than 50 million ly (the distance to Virgo barycenter), after a journey lasting 300 million years. At 20%c, it is calculated that repetitive enroute reacceleration to the initial speed may up to double the reachable distance, to 5e9Ly, and hence multiply by eight the accessible volume.¹⁴⁷

As a synthesis on those strategies, it is proposed that these, allowing to possibly compensate for underachievements in the Breakthrough Starshot developpement, do reinforce its credibility. Also, by showing that the technology of a beaming laser is not a prerequisite to relativistic speeds when thin solar sails are conceived, it adds redundancy to the proposition along which speeds of about 20%c might be reached. Last, by collecting the energy required for travel via the radiation pressure of stars along the journey, such strategies allow for the conceptualisation of infinite seeding probes, possibly independent of infrastructures or onboard fuel, as proposed in V.E) On the assumption for a continued spread

A.3 Laser

The concept for the pushing laser of Breakthrough Starshot is a square kilometer array of phased lasers, total 100Gw, also used as a telescope for recovering information. Its power

¹⁴⁵ Should the dilatant vacuum theory be valid

¹⁴⁶ See *Annex II, De Sitter Model*

¹⁴⁷ [62] (Sandberg 2018) Space races: settling the universe fast. See: Fig 2.

would allow to make it a shiny object as seen from Proxima B, with a magnitude of -4 , (as visible as venus from Earth), and visible to the naked eye, (6 mag), to distances of $6.5e3 \text{ ly}(2\text{kpc})$ ¹⁴⁸.

Fig 9. Detection range for near term signaling, as a function of detection thresholds
 The availability of Breakthrough Starshot 100Gw laser classifies Mankind as a Class 3.5 civilisation as per Lubin range. Modified figure to outline interesting detection thresholds.
 Initial figure: (Lubin 2016) (fig 3)¹⁴⁹

As such, while not marketed as such Breakthrough Starshot beaming laser may also be interpreted as a signaling device of a galactic range. Its targeting capability, developed for tracking meter size objects at spatial distance, will also presumably be capable of targeting precisely targets to signal to. More, even when no signaling is intentional, the inadvertent lighting of targets beyond the projected trajectory of the probes is evident, and potentially problematic, by advising in advance, of the arrival of the given probe. No discreet stellar exploration may happen with nanoprobes using such a propulsion system: the target is in line of sight with the pushing laser, which has a very significant magnitude and range.

¹⁴⁸ [64] (Hippke 2018) Interstellar communication: The colors of optical SETI

¹⁴⁹ [11] (Lubin 2016) Implications of Directed Energy for SETI, considering Starshot Laser.

A.4 Cost considerations

The laser would be accelerating the probes at 20%*c*, with 10 minutes long pulses. Assuming a 25% maintenance time, a 50% data acquisition time, and a cooldown time of 20 minutes per launch, a maximum of 4K launches per year could happen. The anticipated price of the probe (1K\$) is not limiting, but the energy cost of the launch is (6millionUSD per launch). Given the space agency yearly budgets (ESA:7billion US\$, NASA: 22billion US\$, global, around 40 billions US\$), and the cost of the beam director station (8 billion US\$)¹⁵⁰, a maximal 10 billion US\$/year for the launch of probes seems realistic, leading to a maximal launch frequency of **1700 probes/year**. Such a frequency would land the total cost of the project somewhere around 150 billion US\$ for 15 year, which is comparable to the expenses for building and maintaining the international space station (ISS), with an incomparable range and potential scientific yield.

Using laserless, photo gravitational departures, the costs would be dramatically reduced. While for a similar 1g payload the graphene sails would have to be way larger ($1e5m^2$ for a 1g payload, about 1MUS\$/probe)¹⁵¹, the total launch cost would be limited to the low Earth orbit launch of the 86g probe, which would be negligible against the cost of the sail, even when accounting for a deployment system 10 times more massive than the probe itself. (SpaceX Falcon 9 launch, 2020: 2700\$/kg)¹⁵². With a max payload of 100.000kg to low Earth orbit, SpaceX Starship vessel, currently under testing, will allow for lower cost and could permit to envision the simultaneous launch of 100.000 sails of interstellar class, each of these carrying their 1gr cargo, for less than 270M\$ (calculus based on Falcon 9 cost). With an ISS/starshot comparable budget of 10billionUSD/year, the probe frequency could climb to **10.000 probes/year**, using no specific ground infrastructure.

More, when the ambition for solar manoeuvring are dropped, as well as the one for possible stellar “afterburner” acceleration, the sail may be a simple sphere, and concepts are developed of extreme low cost spacecrafts(1000USD/unit) based on aerolith spheres, capable a decent 0.2*C* when dropped at 0.04 AU (parker solar probe distance)¹⁵³. Fig 10 synthetizes the limits and promesses of laser and laserless photon sail launches:

¹⁵⁰ [9] [\(Parkin 2018\) The Breakthrough Starshot system model](#)

¹⁵¹ [12] [\(Heller et al. 2017\) Optimized trajectories to the nearest stars...](#)

¹⁵² [65] [\(Cobb 2019\) How SpaceX lowered costs and reduced barriers to space](#)

¹⁵³ [66] [\(Heller et al. 2020\) Low-cost precursor of an interstellar mission](#)

Fig 10. Possibilities for photon sail launches, depending on the use of a laser station

Laser assist (Starshot). 1g payload 4 m² sail	Laserless launch 1g payload 10⁵m² sail (300m x 300m)
Max speed 20%c off the Solar System.	Max speed +-20%c after two chained stellar accelerations. (Sirius + star max 20° off the targeted direction)
Unit cost = 6million \$ (mainly energy)	Unit cost = 1million \$ (mainly graphene sail)
Ground laser station is a central element to the entire project, leading critical questions regarding feasibility, political stability of the host country, and fiability of the system itself.	Same technology dependence, less the ground laser station.
Potential pictures of A Centaury 20 years after departure. Probe lost.	101 year to orbit in α Centauri A. Fly back possible
For long range navigation, about 110 years saved, by allowing the shortest flight to the photo gravitational Hub.(example of Sirius)	Savings insignificant (below 1%) for one way flights to destinations farther than 2000 ly, or return flights further than 1000 ly (flight time >10.000 year)
Unable to brake at A Centaury (sail too small)	Possible braking and injection in orbits.
1700 launch/year max, (ISS type budget) 4K launch/year max, system limit.	10.000 probes/year, (ISS type budget) No system limit. Fully scalable. Possibly launching 100.000 probes in one shot.
High cost for initial tests: 8billions\$ for ground laser station.	Smaller access cost: prototype sail less than 1 billions\$
No discretion: the laser propulsion beam is advising the target of our presence and of the arrival of a potential probe.	More discreet: the probe starts to be visible when using photonic braking on arrival. A flyby without braking could be reasonably discreet.

The Starshot laser assist system, 6 times less cost effective than simple photogravitaionnal launch from Earth orbit for the same payload, and ultimate speed, provides insignificant advantages for long range travel (less than 1% time difference on return flights over 1000 ly), and does not allow for return flights nor orbits around α Centauri. It is proposed that its main asset is the reduction of the mission duration to human lifetime experiences, favorising

incentives for funding the mission. A point of caution is the question of discretion: the beaming laser will advise of any launch.

A.5 Feasibility of Breakthrough Starshot goals.

Scientific credibility

While the above may feel like science-fiction, we've selected the Breakthrough Starshot project as a reference because it has been scientifically backed by Stephen Hawking, who has predicted the since-then confirmed evaporation of black holes through radiation. His insight on the project is not a guarantee, but an indication of credibility.

Financing

The project has already been backed with 100 millions USD, invested by the russian billionaire Yuri Milner. This is already 10% of a minimal laserless mission. Such a budget is insufficient to entirely finance Starshot, but has demonstrated to be very efficient to have braintime running on the subject.

Risks regarding anticipated developments

Solar sails are something real, today. Their use has been demonstrated for controlling spacecrafts attitude and altitude (Mariner 10, Hayabusa, MTSAT-1R), then from primary propulsion: the 200m² IKAROS (Interplanetary Kite-craft Accelerated by Radiation Of the Sun) mission successfully demonstrated interplanetary capability for solar sailing, by being the first spacecraft using solar sail as primary propulsion. Detail designs have been performed to near financing, for sails 40m*40m(Okeanos project). NASA is currently funding a 400.000\$ Solar cruiser conceptual design, while lightsail projects(1&2), currently flying, are demonstrating the manoeuvring possibilities of 32m² lightsail cubesat. While development is underway, it is not impossible that design issues prohibit reaching the required 8.6×10^{-4} gram m⁻² necessary for optimised photogravitational navigation. Should the development fail in this area, and not in the one of lasers, laser assistance could compensate for some of the loss, and allow the target of interstellar probe, to be met.

The most innovative, untested one is the laser beaming station. The project is resilient to a failure in this domain: as proposed above, while the mission duration would be extended, given proper solar sails, Breakthrough Starshot could exist without its ground station. The entire laser

station, and related technology, are optional to the concept and to the capability, when thinking beyond human lifetime.

Miniaturisation, on its side, being pushed by the very dynamic smartphone industry, and by the still not disproved Moore's law, is considered to be on a very resilient technological pace.

Three main technical areas: laser beaming, solar sails, and miniaturisation are constitutive of the project. Critical failure of miniaturisation is considered improbable. Critical failure of solar sails technology is considered improbable given the successful demonstrations. Critical failure of the development of the pusher beam and targeting receiver station is considered possible. But in such a case the solar sail development could partly compensate, should it not suffer a partial failure. Only the total failure of the laser pusher concept, combined with a partial failure to develop low sigma solar sails, could to my understanding prevent the starshot goals to be reached within a proximate future. The fact that starshot test probes, "Sprites", are right already flying above our heads, contributes to the credibility of the overall project.

A.6 Hypotheses on interstellar travel, time capsules and interstellar signaling

Vectored by human technology, life has hence just started to develop its extrasolar impact. Still, should we let it happen, its potential impact, driven by the means obtained through mankind technological progresses, is about to exponentially increase:

- hypothesis on interstellar signaling: With an initial funding of 100 million US\$ and proposed to be operational 20 years ahead of us, Breakthrough Starshot laser array will have the theoretical capability of signaling us to a naked eye in the sky of 70 million nearby stellar systems, and with a magnitude 30 capable telescope, to about a quarter of the $250e9$ stars in the galaxy¹⁵⁴.
- (hypothesis on interstellar travel) The Starchip system, part of the same Breakthrough Starshot project, will have the capability to launch miniaturised spaceships called sprites, up to 20% of the speed of light.¹⁵⁵
- (hypothesis on time capsules) Financed, within developpement, the billion Year Archive of the Arch Mission Foundation, proposes to "maintain a backup of planet Earth,

¹⁵⁴ [11] (Lubin 2016) Implications of Directed Energy for SETI, and GAIA DR2 Archive Considering Starshot Laser. Detectability as detailed in *Annex IV Scope*.

¹⁵⁵ [9] (Parkin 2018) The Breakthrough Starshot system model, and

designed to continuously preserve and disseminate humanity's most important knowledge across time and space", onboard supports with a calculated survivability of $1.40E+10$ years¹⁵⁶. Such technology, When embarked on Breakthrough style probes, might allow intergalactic survivability of the information, or of encapsulated elements, such as dehydrated lifeforms, DNA, or elements of. The Moon Arch Foundation Library, crashed on the moon, had amongst its payload, revivable tardigrades in cryptobiosis state, preserved in epoxy.

B) Hypothesis on boarding

Investigating the hypothesis on boarding, according to which some life related informational elements, such as ideas, technologies, computer virus or genetical codes may be transmitted via onboard information systems, or signals, and some life forms may be embarked intentionally, incidentally, or malevolently, on a probe or a time capsule made by man.

The three investigated means: signals, spaceships and time capsules, may carry self-reproducing, potentially exponential¹⁵⁷ Life, or life-related elements of two kinds, depending on their material, or informational nature.¹⁵⁸

1. **Material** life or life related elements are understood as not being possibly reduced to purely informational representations and have a physical, material nature, and a mass. Examples would be microorganisms. These may board on material transmitters, such as spaceships, probes, rocks, but may not be transmitted via signals.
2. **Informational** life or life related elements, such as computer viruses, ideas, or coded genetic information, may board on both signals to be sent, and onboard some material transmitters, such as onboard computers, softwares, or navigation systems.

Thanks to their capacity to self-reproduce, given the proper substrate upon arrival, both types of entities may sustain an exponential growth, which behold a transformative power for their environment.

¹⁵⁶ [8] [\(Arch Mission Foundation, 2020\) 5D Optical Memory Crystal.](#)

¹⁵⁷ See [III.Chapt1.B.3 Self-reproduction](#), and [Tool n°4, picturing exponential growth](#)

¹⁵⁸ See Glossary, Life ([material and informational](#))

Signals may carry self-reproducing informational life, of life related elements such as Ideas or computer viruses, that may then develop exponentially on the substrate and via the network and resources of would-be extraterrestrial beings, should these exist.

Spaceships, automated or not, intentionally or not, may carry such self reproducing informational elements, and also artificial or biological life. Such life may then develop exponentially, through the increased range of accessible resources, and/or via the network and resources of would-be extraterrestrial beings, should these exist.

Time capsules, similarly could transmit both informational or material life or life-related elements, which may then either be timely reactivated, automatically, or through the intervention and via the networks and resources of would-be future civilisation, or extraterrestrial beings, coming in contact with the time capsule.

It is proposed that this boarding may happen A) Intentionally, B) incidentally, or C) malevolently. At last, we argue that the transmitters itself is potentially carrying life or life related elements

A) Passengers - Intentional boarding

Ideologists, scientists, why not both at the same time, such as Claudius Gros, with his “genesis” project¹⁵⁹, could push towards the use of those probes for a directed, or undirected panspermia campaign. When cargo is optimised to maintain alive, and to deliver, there is little doubt on the survival capability of some elements: as developed above; DNA, viruses, microbial life and up to multicellular organisms could survive the journey and end up in a favorable environment in an extrasolar world.

B) Hitchhikers - Incidental boarding

Alternatively, the probes could be poorly decontaminated, if decontaminated at all. First, planetary protection measure following space treaty are not explicitly targeting extrasolar worlds, second, the decontamination procedure itself could fail, given the non-exhaustivity of the knowledge regarding survival capability of organismes, and third, opinion leaders such as musk are ridiculising these¹⁶⁰. Today, the planetary protection measures are exclusively instrumental: their goal is to protect the information regarding the origin of life¹⁶¹. As no intrinsic value is given to potential ecosystems, these are not protected by the texts but if considered valuable for

¹⁵⁹ [4] (Gros, 2016) [Developing Ecospheres on Transiently Habitable Planets: The Genesis Project.](#)

¹⁶⁰ See answer to Planetary protection concern on Mars in “2019 Starship Update” Video.

¹⁶¹ COSPAR planetary protection policies states: “Category I includes any mission to a target body which is not of direct interest for understanding the process of chemical evolution or the origin of life. No protection of such bodies is warranted and no planetary protection requirements are imposed by this policy.”

human knowledge, which is extremely highly subjective. Such stowaway passengers, due to their incidental nature, would be much less protected and prone to survival. Still, as explored in lithopanspermia hypothesis, it might be enough to transfer live elements, capable of flourishing given they eventually land in a favorable environment, given a capture by ETI or a survivable crash.

C) Stowaways - Malevolent boarding

Then, intentional, stowaway passengers could be integrated. Again, and sadly, this is not science fiction. In 2018, the Arch Mission foundation loaded a payload in a Moon lander, with undeclared humane DNA, and dehydrated, revivable, extremophile organisms.

D) Cargo, computer systems, drawings, trajectories.

If self-replicative, miniaturised, autonomous machines such as von neumann probes or similar concepts¹⁶² are not envisioned as credible in the near-term, informational self-replicating entities such as ideas, computer viruses, genetical codes, may be, intentionally, incidentally, or malevolently, included as cargo. With developed storage of calculated survival time of 14 billions of years¹⁶³, cosmic radiation, temperature (1000°C) and crash resistance to some extent, such cargo may be resilient enough to eventually be picked up by some ETI millions to billions of years ahead. But cargo is not the only collectible information, and even a fully decontaminated, cargoless probe would carry an impressive amount of information by its sole existence: its trajectory may allow it to infer from where it is flying from. Isotopic ratio may inform about the kind of environment it has been assembled in, navigation systems even if deprived of signatures, will tell about the mathematical arsenal of the originator.

From this analysis, it appears that depriving entirely a signal, a vessel or a time-capsule, from any life or life-related element eventually capable of inducing exponential life-related consequences appears extremely complex. The hypothesis along which signals, time capsules and spaceships may be boarded intentionally, incidentally, or malevolently, is then considered to be secured.

¹⁶² [67] [On the interstellar Von Neumann micro self-reproducing probes](#)

¹⁶³ [8] [\(Arch Mission Foundation, 2020\) 5D Optical Memory Crystal.](#)

C) Hypothesis on technological civilisation

Investigating the hypothesis according to which our technologically capable civilisation survives.

Organisms might be apprehended as vehicles for genes¹⁶⁴ across time and space. In a similar way, the technological artifacts developed by mankind: signals, spacecraft and time capsules, may be understood as vehicles for informational and material life or life-related elements.

Mankind, through its technology, is becoming a vehicle to the extrasolar space and time. For life as we know it on earth, the loss of our technological capability, would mean to lose an extrasolar vehicle that took 3.5 billions of years to develop, just when it is about to deliver access to 29 more orders of magnitude. From this perspective, managing the risks of loss of technological capability, also embodied within the risk of extinction of our civilisation, and the one of our species is not only an existential issue for us, it is also one for life as we know it on earth.

In this subsection, out of reasonable clues regarding the potential loss of the technological capability itself, or the one of our civilisation, we investigate the risk of the human species going extinct, which is encompassing both of these risks (a), and the one of life going extinct (b). In the hypothesis of the strong astrobiological copernican principle, where evolution takes a similar time to go from one stage to the other¹⁶⁵, the loss of opportunity (loss of potentially accessible volume), embodied by the risk of life going extinct or suffering a catastrophic setback is envisioned (c), and the conditions required to acquire again the lost technological capability, following a cataclysm, are considered (d)

It is eventually concluded that the condition on the existence of a technological civilisation capable of supporting the required technologies for the gateway to exist, is extremely uncertain, while some strategy might exist to allow for a quicker reboot to the considered capability, in case it is lost..

(a) Mankind: risk of going extinct bounded by a minimum of 7E-5 per year

99% of all species that ever have existed on Earth have gone extinct. The existential risk community¹⁶⁶ has well documented the risks for mankind to suffer a dramatic setback, or to disappear. This risk comprehends natural and anthropic components. The Bulletin of Atomic

¹⁶⁴ [30] (Dawkins 2016) *The Selfish Gene*

¹⁶⁵ [68] (Westby and Conselice 2020) *The Astrobiological Copernican Weak and Strong Limits...*

¹⁶⁶ *Future of life Institute, CSER, Nick Bostrom, Future of Humanity Institute...*

Scientists¹⁶⁷, sees us 100 seconds to self annihilation, but while multiple paths to self extinction are envisioned, from unsurvivable anthropic climate change to the development of a rogue artificial intelligence, The literature does not agree on probabilities. The natural component, regarding which a historical analysis can be used for estimation, is consequently a lower bound for the overall risk of human extinction, and has been estimated to be of 0.001% per year(+7E-5)¹⁶⁸.

Interestingly, the risk for mankind to go extinct each year is consequently more than 500 times higher than the one you take when boarding a commercial flight¹⁶⁹. You'd have to fly more than 500 flights a year, for your risk to die in an aircraft to be superior to the one of observing the extinction of humans. If you are afraid to fly, you should be afraid to witness the extinction of our species.

(b) life: risk of going extinct bounded by a minimum of 5E-10 per year

A statistical analysis of the fossil extinction records in the last 540 millions years, allows for a an estimation of the probability of extinction of all life on Earth, ex the anthropic effect, to be of 1 out of two billion per year¹⁷⁰(+5E-10). To the current understanding, because for example we are today incapable of preventing a supervolcanic event or a very large collision with a celestial body, the presence of modern Human on Earth does not fundamentally change the resilience of life to natural events susceptible to set it back dramatically, or to induce complete extinction. More, arguably, with the creation of technological risks such as nuclear warfare, or climate change, mankind adds more risks than it mitigates. As a consequence, the above estimation may be considered as a lower bound for the yearly risk of all life going extinct, which is 150.000 times lower than the risk for Mankind extinction, and 250 times lower than the one of you dying in the airplane you board.

(c) Cataclysmic setbacks

Should we make the hypothesis that starting anew, evolution takes a comparable duration, to achieve comparable progresses¹⁷¹, the loss of opportunity of access due to the expansion of the universe while re-evolving life to the state of extrasolar capability is depending on the magnitude of the setback and can be computed easily using a de Sitter model.

¹⁶⁷ [69] [\(The bulletin of atomic scientists 2020\) Doomsday Clock](#)

¹⁶⁸ [70] [\(Snyder-Beattie et al. 2019\) \[...\] the background rate of human extinction](#) = 1/87000

¹⁶⁹ [71] [\(Barnett 2020\) Aviation Safety: A Whole New World?](#)

¹⁷⁰ [72] [\(Tsumura 2020\) Estimating survival probability... using formula \(6\)](#)

¹⁷¹ Strong astrobology copernican principle

In a *Planet of the Apes* scenario, where life has to re-evolve from the capability of the earliest hominids, the loss of opportunities due to the expansion of the universe is of less than a percent and hence, is presumably not dramatical from the point of view of lost opportunity due expansion.

Conversely, in a scenario of total eradication, where evolution would have to start again from scratch, the opportunity loss reaches $\frac{2}{3}$ of today's accessible universe. This is not only significant: the time required to do so, 4.5 billions of years, is not realistic on Earth, whose liquid water is planned to suffer a runaway evaporation starting in a billion year or so, turning the planet into an unsurvivable venus within about 150 million years, through a process called moist greenhouse effect, induced by the natural increase in solar luminosity.¹⁷²

When considering life as a whole. There is hence a maximal cataclysmic setback that has to be avoided for life to maintain reasonable opportunities, lying somewhere in between these extremities. The proposition is made that a setback to the stage of multicellular animals, from which life has demonstrated to be able to evolve to extrasolar capability within about 600 millions years, might be the limit of acceptability, should we want to preserve extrasolar opportunities: with this limit, the opportunity loss due expansion would be limited to about 1/7, and the ocean evaporation issue is avoided. Once extrasolar capability recovered, 400 millions years would be remaining for expansion, should it be something good to happen.

(d) Re-evolution impaired by the exhaustion of intermediate resources.

The above reasoning has an obvious flaw, which is that to rebuild interstellar capability, life would have similar starting grounds to the preceding ones. The thing is that to get there we have been using extensively, and depleted, the stocks of easily accessible fossil fuels, and resources such as minerals. Even modern humans having suffered a mild technological collapse would have a hard time finding accessible petrol. While it may be argued that over time, (20-350million years), fossil fuel stocks could regenerate, it is untrue regarding most mined material. This effect could prevent a rebuild of interstellar capacity, and in this hypothesis, entail the loss of all opportunities out there.

As a conclusion, the hypothesis on the survival of the technological capability allowing for the creation of spaceships, time capsules and signals, being dependent on the survival of our civilisation, of the one of our species, and of life as a whole, appears very uncertain. As this

¹⁷² [73] [\(Leconte et al. 2013\) Increased insolation threshold for runaway greenhouse processes...](#)

hypothesis is a critical condition to the kingmaker situation, this uncertainty is problematic to the argumentation, and while theorisation is possible regarding the loss of opportunity associated to the potential temporary loss of the condition, our opinion is that the strong astrobiological principle, upon which it is grounded, holds very little trustability. More interesting is the consideration along which no guarantee is held that any rebuild may happen, following the exhaustion of resources of easy access, which are potentially a necessity for this capability to be acquired, and which anyhow make life way easier to do so. This consideration will lead, at the stage of the conclusion, to the proposition to safeguard a quick restart kit, comprehending a minimal amount of such easy access resources, preserved for a restart to happen quicker, should our civilisation or species somehow go extinct.

D) Hypothesis on irreversibility

Investigating the hypothesis according to which “Control may not be exerted on life out of the Solar System”

The appealing quantity of examples of our failure to control life on Earth, starting by ourselves, then ranging from patagonian beavers, to australian camels via rats on the pacific islands, sheds little doubt on this later hypothesis. Pretending to control blooming, evolving life, light-years away out there, when you are unable to manage a beaver, appear unreasonable. Even for god-playing geneticists.

This is an extremely important issue: we’ve proven on Earth that 4.5 billion years are enough to conceptualise, and to achieve near term feasibility for universal panspermia projects. As later explored in V.E [On the hypothesis for continuous spread](#), a 150 years project concentrating 10% of the global gross world product (GWP) would allow us, should we elect to do so, to send seeding probes to each of the 200 million galaxy of the universe reachable at 20%*c*, each of these probe with the potential to seed multiple star systems within each galaxy, following the presented principles of chained navigations with photonic sails. Human history, from pyramids to cathedrals, have demonstrated the capability for multigeneration programs, sustaining similar economical load, when metaphysically driven. From biotism (saving life as we know it, at all prices), panbiotism (our purpose is to seed the universe with life), the simple purpose of “giving mankind a purpose”, or even an interpretation of the biblical injunction to multiply, metaphysical reasons exist, and could be promoting such a program. So 4.5 billion years have been enough

to take us from earliest known life form, to a species with demiurgic ambition, near term to reach the related capability.

If seeding happens with microbial life selected for faster evolution than on Earth, such as envisioned in the Genesis project (“fast forward evolution by 3-4 billion years“ !), evolution to space age could take as little as a billion year from seeding¹⁷³. More, by shortcutting evolution thanks to the evolved organisms that are being sent, bottlenecks in survival or evolution might be avoided, and the odds of life evolving to space age be higher than the ones we had on Earth.

With the above projections, the single successful seeding of a single world could lead to the birth of a new local demiurgic species¹⁷⁴, reaching similar demiurgic possibilities to ours, unleashing a universal seeding project less than a billion years after its seeding by us. Involved losses in opportunities due to some of the universe expanding out of reach are explored in Evaluations/The universe, Flowing Away. Such a demiurgic species would have access to about 75% of today’s reachable galaxies. Then within each of the seeded galaxies, a single seeded world could lead to another demiurgic panspermia, within, or outbound the given galaxy.

Here is the issue: when we have no control over the seeded worlds, massive panspermia projects are not required, for the maximal consequences of our acts to be universal: when we may not guarantee control of the seeded world, the single seeding of a single world, could lead to universal colonisation, out of control.

In Chapter 3. Humans, of section III) HYPOTHESES, we have been exploring the hypotheses mainly related to us humans. The technological hypotheses being considered as realistic in the near term, the critical question of the possibility of incidental, intentional, or malevolent boarding has been addressed, and considered serious. The question of the survival of civilisation was investigated, found very unsecured, and the reversibility by humans means, of the process of incidentally, intentionally or malevolently seeding a remote world, has been considered as extremely unlikely.

Having explored the hypotheses related to life itself (Chapter 1), to extrasolar access (Chapter 2), and to human beings (Chapter 3), The twelves hypotheses identified in the logical scheme outlined in figure 2. have now been considered. Amongst these, Two are embodying a large

¹⁷³ [4] (Gros, 2016) Developing Ecospheres on Transiently Habitable Planets: The Genesis Project

¹⁷⁴ In this discussion, a demiurgic species refers to a species amongst which some individuals are pursuing the goal, for any given reason, to achieve the widest possible seeding of life, to the maximal possible amount of stellar systems, and which have some capability to do so

part of uncertainty: the one regarding the survival of civilisation, which is a prerequisite for the kingmaker situation to happen or be maintained, and the one regarding the existence of extraterrestrial intelligence.

The only critical hypothesis found to be unsecured is the one regarding the survival of our technological civilisation, when conceived as a civilisation within which, the technologies considered as near term today and referred to as breakthrough type technologies, are accessible within a short timeframe.

The assessment of hypotheses being over, and the logic defended in II) ARGUMENTATIVE concluding to the very probable creation or existence of the kingmaker situation, The next section, IV) EVALUATION, is dedicated to the assessment of the magnitude of the scope encompassed by the potential decision laying into the hands of humans.

IV) EVALUATION

In this section, the potential impacts of the kingmaker decision are evaluated.

This section is relying on the work presented Annex IV Scope, which proposes numerical estimations for the elements potentially impacted by the decision humans may or may not take regarding the extrasolar advent of life.

It also takes grounds on Annex II De Sitter Model, where is developed a constant expansion model allowing to easily estimate elements within reach as a function of the initial speed of the transmission or travel.

In I) PREREQUISITES, after a cautionary statement regarding numbers, and a reminder about the uncertainties related to the frequency of ET, or ETI, we powered up our representations with tools adapted to large scales. In II) ARGUMENTATION, we've detailed the reasoning leading to the conclusion that humans are reaching a kingmaker situation in respect to life as we know it on Earth. We've ordered hypotheses within a logic scheme, whose robustness was assessed and considered high. In III) HYPOTHESES, the detailed investigation of hypotheses outlined two uncertain conditions, the question of the survival of the civilisation, critical to the advent of the kingmaker situation, and the question of the existence of ET and ETI, acting as a double sided knife, fundamentally conditioning the nature of the scope to consider, whatever its outcome.

It has been considered probable that the envisioned kingmaker situation is realised soon, if not already existing through the developed capability regarding time capsules. In this context, it is important to explore the scope, and the magnitude of the possible impacts of the decision permitted by this situation. This is the purpose of this section, IV) EVALUATION, which is proposed as a synthesis of the work detailed in *Annex IV Scope*,.

Section IV) EVALUATION, will start with A) a finite accessible space, by bounding the question of the potential impacts. The scope of the kingmaker decision, defined as the maximal set of things possibly impacted by the decision, is then envisioned in B) An existential choice, leading to the consideration that the kingmaker decision is existential¹⁷⁵, not only to humans, but to life

¹⁷⁵ Oxford languages defines existential as “relating to existence”. In this discussion, something will be considered as existential to something else when the first conditions the existence or absence of the later.

as we know it on Earth, and to the potential extraterrestrial biodiversity, should it exist. A synthesis of the work detailed in *Annex IV Scope* is then proposed, in C) A significant magnitude, where the maximal set of things possibly impacted by the decision, are estimated numerically, and considered very significant..

When an existential decision, potentially impacting such a wide environment, is to be taken, time is valuable for a proper assessment to happen. In D) The universe flowing away, considerations are shared regarding the ongoing losses of opportunities inherent to the constant expansion of the universe, and the relative urgency of this decision. In E), the impossibility is of exponential growth, the limits of our finite, accessible environment, are demonstrated ad absurdum, before strategies for compensating for the losses of opportunities are discussed, in F) Compensating for the loss of opportunity.

A) A finite accessible space

In the current paradigm, while no conclusion can be drawn on whether the universe is unlimited or not, it appears that the combination of the expansion of the universe and of a limited speed for causation, implies that the accessible universe, even with the most effective envisionnable technology, is of finite dimension. In this paradigm set by Einstein special relativity and Hubble observation of an expanding universe, the speed of light is the ultimate speed limit for any causation, and consequently, no impact and no access may happen beyond a distance called the event horizon, and located today about 15.7GLY away from us, and reachable after infinite times, at the speed of light.

Should life be given extrasolar access, the reachable universe and resources would be increased, in volume, by 29 orders of magnitude, and limited by the event horizon. Depending on the speed of the considered causation, smaller horizons would limit the access. Providing estimation for future times, from the account of constant expansion, a de Sitter model is handily used for evaluating such opportunities.¹⁷⁶ For the details of this mathematical model, see *Annex II De Sitter model*.

¹⁷⁶ *Annex II de Sitter Model*, is providing tools and formulas for this.

B) An existential choice

Due to the existence of this event horizon, releasing life to the extrasolar space would not mean releasing it “to infinity and beyond”, but to a space of opportunity about 1.000.000.000.000.000.000.000¹⁷⁷ bigger than what it may access today.

Doing so would not only open significant possibilities for expansion in space, for life as we know it on earth: it would also reduce the risks of extinction, these being simply due to the eventual loss of habitability of the solar system, or due to the cataclysmic events as envisioned in III.Chapter 2.A Solar System and in III.Chapter 3.C.The odds of losing life.

Humans hence have a card to play or not to play, which is critical to the odds of survival of Earth originated life, as well as to the magnitude of its interstellar possibilities. In this perspective, humans face a choice which is existential regarding the advent of life as we know it on earth, and to themselves, as part of the biosphere.

There is more: should some extraterrestrial biodiversity exist, the assumption being made that it may be susceptible to and threatened by invasive species, the spread of life as we know it on Earth is also existential to Life as we do not know it. In such a case, Life as we know it on Earth is possibly perceived as a threat, and a decision of expansion may lead to a negative feedback from life as we do not know it. When ET exists, the kingmaker decision is also existential to humans from the perspective of a possible negative feedback.

The decision at the center of the kingmaker situation is as such existential not only to Life as we know it on earth and for us, humans, but also to life as we do not know it, should it exist.

¹⁷⁷ Volume of space within event horizon, as compared with 3.35Ly radius of the SOI of the Solar System

C) A significant magnitude

The scope of the kingmaker decision does not only encompass some existential perspectives, also, while finite as argued in A), it relates to important magnitudes in the impacted environment.

In *Annex IV Scope*, the scope of a decision was defined as the maximal set of things possibly impacted by the decision. A neutral moral position was adopted, our purpose being to evaluate the maximal quantity of impacted things, not their goodness or badness, should these exist.

Five points of evaluation were chosen, referred to as opportunities¹⁷⁸, noted Ω , for which the potentially impacted elements, constitutive of the scope of the possible decision regarding life advend out there, were to be evaluated.

The estimations were performed at each point of evaluation, of the potential range accessible via massive, then non-massive transmitters, defining at each point and for each mean, a maximal accessible volume, within which the amount of accessible mass and energy within reach were calculated. The point by point detail of this estimation is detailed in *Annex IV Scope*, where tables are presented with the estimation of the potentially impacted environnement, by life as we know it on earth, given the universe accessible depending on the considered opportunities.

A bounding of the incertitudes was performed, and excluding estimations related to ET and ETI, which are indicative only, the presented estimates are considered to be trustable within the order of magnitude when considering the parameters used, within four orders of magnitude when considering estimated quantities, such as potentially impacted planets, of mass within reach, and within seven orders of magnitude when estimating the size of networks. While enormous, these incertitudes do not impair the conclusion that the size of the potentially impacted environment, 29 orders of magnitude higher by volume than the one where life is evolving right now, is significant.

¹⁷⁸ “an opportunity is a time or set of circumstances that makes it possible to do something.” In this work, opportunities are considered as a set of circumstances at a moment in time, where the potential impacts constitutive of the scope of the decision humans may take or not take from their kingmaker position, are evaluated.

Fig 11. The scope of the elements possibly impacted by earth-originated life

Plain lines: potential impact via massive transmitters, such as asteroids, spaceships, probes.

Dashed lines: potential impact via non-massive transmitters, such as, laser, radio transmissions.

(Mag XY): detectability with a technology capable of detecting a signal of equivalent magnitude XY

ETI: potential impact in case extraterrestrial intelligence exist with a probability of 1e-10/star

ET: potential impact in case extraterrestrial life exist with a probability of 2e-3/star

Habitable: the probability of habitability is considered 10%/star

See Annex IV: Scope for detailed calculations and argumentation

Fig.11, above, is proposed as a synthesis of this work: here are displayed the elements possibly accessed by life as we know it, as per the chosen points of evaluation:

- Historical opportunities: noted $\Omega_{\text{historical}}$, set of parameters used to calculate historically potentially impacted elements, by the extrasolar access of life, as we know it on Earth;
- Natural opportunities: noted $\Omega_{2020 \text{ ex man}}$, set of parameters used to calculate potentially impacted elements, by life as we know it with its capability in 2020, excluding the contribution of mankind
- 2020 opportunities, noted Ω_{2020} : set of parameters used to calculate potentially impacted elements by life as we know it with its capability today, including via the media of human spatial activities as per 2020 demonstrated capabilities.
- Breakthrough opportunities, noted Ω_{2040} : set of parameters used to calculate potentially impacted elements by life as we know it with its projected capability in 2040 when considering Breakthrough-type technology, and in particular a speed of 20%*c* for probes
- Total opportunities, noted Ω_{∞} : set of parameters used to calculate absolute maximal scope, with signals limited to the event horizon, and probes to the horizon at 90%*c* .

Three very important elements are to be noted. First is that this graph is on a logarithmic scale: the incredible increase of orders of magnitude, ranging from 5 to 34, being so high that these are impossible to represent on a sheet of paper. A sheet a hundred thousand of billions of billion times taller than this A4 sheet would be required to represent the maximal increase of opportunities.

Second is that, by order of magnitude, the highest historical increase in potential access, **EVER**, is to happen between today (Ω_{2020}) and the advent of the Breakthrough-type technologies (Ω_{2040}), considered to be realistic in the generation to come.¹⁷⁹, further expansion being then possible, but soon to be limited by the physical limits of the accessible universe, due to the effects of expansion.

Third is that while most of the potential impact due to the use of electromagnetic signals, and some of the ones due to massive transmitter, is dependant upon the hypothesis on the existence of extraterrestrial life, and intelligence, the maximal rise in opportunities is found to be

¹⁷⁹ [9] [\(Parkin 2018\) The Breakthrough Starshot system model](#)

on the question of the size of the possible networks, physical and informational, that may exist between habitable worlds, a question which is independent of the hypothesis regarding ET.

The scope of our decision, with or without ET out there, is the biggest ever, in the future of the accessible universe.

D) The universe, flowing away.

So, beyond its existential aspects (see C), the scope potentially impacted by the impacts of the decision to take or not to take is extremely high. The issue is not only there: there is some sense of urgency. According to the current paradigm, the accessible universe is not only finite in space, it is also limited in time. Indeed, due to the expansion, elements are flowing out of reach, beyond the horizons for causation. As developed in *Annex II, de Sitter model*, at lightspeed, the access to 98% of the observable universe has already been lost, and only 2% is remaining within reach.

Fig 12. Percentage of lost accessible universe, as a function of elapsed time
As calculated from formulas developed in Annex II De Sitter Model)

	Time to extrasolar capability (in years)	Percentage of lost accessible volume, during that time frame
From the earliest hominids	7,200,000	0.2%
From multicellular animals	6.50E+08	14%
From cyanobacterias	3.50E+09	55%
From Earth formation	4.50E+09	64%

Each year passing by, about 40 galaxies are flowing out of observation, 5 are disappearing out of reach at lightspeed, beyond the event horizon, and about 3 billions stars are lost to access via spaceships travelling at 20% of the speed of light¹⁸⁰.

More, the current consensus points towards a sustained or accelerating expansion, and investigating this points to somehow depressing conclusions: about 3 billion years in the future, a minimum of 50% of what is accessible today will have expanded beyond reach. Eventually, a

¹⁸⁰ Calculations made by the author using a de Sitter model: see *Annex II De Sitter Model*.

maximum of 100 billion years ahead, every single gravitationally bound structure in the universe will become isolated in what literature refers to as a causal patch. Fig.13, below, produced in *Annex II, de Sitter Model*, is presenting this effect, and shows the evolution of the fraction of any homogeneous distribution, as a function of elapsed time.

Fig 13. Fraction of homogeneous distributions, remaining within reach below horizon, as a function of elapsed time.

This graph, produced by the author from the exploitation of the de Sitter model as proposed in annex, presents the issue of causal fracturation due to the universe expanding. Note: it is interesting to realise that the timing is independent of the considered speed: raising speed augments the volume within reach, but does not impact the time at which the separation occurs, from structures expanding with the universe.

Eventually, for us, the accessible universe will be reduced to what will be remaining of the merger of our galaxy (the Milky Way) with M31 (Andromeda, colliding 5Gyr ahead) and M33(before 10Gyr)¹⁸¹. While a space of opportunity 500 time bigger¹⁸² (2-3 orders of magnitude) could be maintained by somehow managing the jump to the collapsing part of Virgo supercluster, 50 million ly away, the amount of habitable places within this gravitationally bound assembly, within which life could spread without us through ejection and collisions, still being a billion times smaller (9 orders of magnitude) than what lies out in the accessible universe, today. At 20%c (Breakthrough Starshot speed), the opportunity of jumping is lost within the 70 billion

¹⁸¹ [74] (van der Marel et al. 2012) [The M31 Velocity Vector. III. Future Milky Way-M31-M33...](#)

¹⁸² [75] (Chon et al. 2015) [On the definition of superclusters](#)

year to come due to causal separation. Should the plan be to hop on the possible planetary¹⁸³ system associated to a high velocity star (HVS) such as S5-HVS1¹⁸⁴, being ejected by our galaxy (about 10.000 like this per billion year)¹⁸⁵, just as we'd do on a full comfort intergalactic bus, heating included, the decision would have to be even more urgent: the opportunity is to close in 10 billion years or so. Should life be something good to be spread, time is counted.

Fig 14. A chronology of causal fracturation
 The progressive isolation in the billions of years to come.
 Calculus and methodology detailed in Annex II De Sitter model

E) The impossibility of exponential growth

The above numbers, pointing to limitations appearing at orders of magnitude 29 times bigger than what we access to today, are so well beyond imagination that we have real difficulties at conceptualizing that speed of light and expansion do bound opportunities. In this finite accessible universe, where resources are flowing away with time passing bye, infinite growth may nevertheless not be sustained.

Reductio ad absurdum

So as to grasp this more intuitively, a mind experiment is proposed. In 2019, mankind's demand for energy was 6E+20 joules, increasing by 1.6%/year. While this 1.6%/year “feels” like

¹⁸³ [76] (Ginsburg et al. 2012) Hypervelocity planets and transits around hypervelocity stars

¹⁸⁴ [77] (Koposov et al. 2019) Discovery of a nearby 1700 km s⁻¹ star ejected from the Milky Way...

¹⁸⁵ [78] (Brown et al. 2018) Gaia and the Galactic Center Origin of Hypervelocity Stars

a small growth, when sustained, it would lead to requiring yearly to harvest the total solar radiation produced by the Sun, less than 2000 years ahead, and the entire mass-energy of the entire accessible universe, less than 5000 years later ($3E+68$) joules. At what we perceive like a small growth rate, the entire accessible universe would be evaporated, in a shorter time than what it took for humans to develop from the mesopotamian civilisation to today's space faring species.

In a similar way to which our generation is struggling, realising Earth is a limited environnement, unable to sustain unlimited growth, the hard conclusion is that expanding to space may not be considered as a solution to this issue. No constant growth may be sustained indefinitely, even to space, and the temporal limits are very near for any uncheck growth in this environnement.

The thing is: as considered when developing our toolkit, exponential growth, is precisely what living things do. Interestingly, thinking at extreme range of time, some propose that the “renewable energy”, outbound the burning stars, eventually lacking, and in order to sustain the growth when universal scales distribution of life are considered, life forms eventually end up converting a significant share of the remaining mass of the universe into energy¹⁸⁶ eventually radiated and lost to the expansion, to the extent which this conversion could have an impact on the rate of expansion of the universe itself.¹⁸⁷ Not only would an absurd constant growth target lead to exhausting the entire matter of the universe within 5000 years. It would also, by evaporating it, accelerate the expansion of the universe itself and precipitate its causal separation !

True and somehow crazy, what we have been envisioning here is the direct or indirect entire, heterogenous conversion of the accessible universe, which our decision could be eventually inducing (When Earth is the only place where life appears) or have an impact on (If others are here) to the extent which, to some authors, the eventual competition between civilisations (Earth originated, or ET) may lead to the mass-energy conversion to be significant enough, to eventually shift the scale factor and accelerate expansion, leading to earlier causal fracturation¹⁸⁸. When the advisors for unsustainable development on Earth rely on space dreams to feed

¹⁸⁶ (something we already to a very limited extend on Earth, nuclear energy extracted via human technologies, only representing 0.4% of the total energy processed by life on Earth)

¹⁸⁷ [79] [\(Olson and Jay Olson 2015\) Homogeneous cosmology with aggressively expanding civilizations](#)

¹⁸⁸ [79] [\(Olson and Jay Olson 2015\) Homogeneous cosmology with aggressively expanding civilizations](#)

them with infinite growth, they just forget that unsustainable development in space could well end up “ripping apart” space itself. When you are evaporating mass to radiation to feed your growth: gravity stops holding the structure you’re harvesting from.

F) Compensating for the loss of opportunity

For causation travelling already at C , on electromagnetic beams, little may be theoretically done to recover the lost opportunities due to elapsed time, for special relativity prohibits further acceleration. For slower means, though, it looks very feasible to compensate the effects of the expansion with technological progress: at the current rate of expansion, the sustained speed increase only has to be about 1% every 130 million years.

Whatever the causation speed, it appears that only a billionth of the possible causal access, is lost every 5 months. When compared with the current technological progress, this is extremely slow. This shed another light on the possibility of compensation: even when considering the absolute loss of access, the opportunities might not be diminishing with elapsed time, for within the same duration, spared resources may be invested in technological development allowing for a way better use of the remaining access.

Last but not least, one shall not forget that science is an ongoing, self revising process, and that both hypotheses leading to the depressing conclusion of a finite spacetime of opportunity, special relativity, and the expansion of the universe, might eventually prove false or limited. Should the standard model of cosmology be false, or the speed of light possibly somehow exceeded, causal horizons would disappear and the perspectives of an infinite universe could be recovered.

Time is passing by, true, but not only do we lose a ridiculously low amount of access with time passing by: it might also be worth waiting, to actually increase the overall opportunities, not forgetting that we are only beginning, to understand the universe we lay within.

In section IV) EVALUATION, the scope of the kingmaker decision, was envisioned, limited to distances below the event horizon, and leading to the consideration that the kingmaker decision is existential¹⁸⁹ to humans, life as we know it on Earth, and to the potential extraterrestrial

¹⁸⁹ Oxford languages defines existential as “relating to existence”. In this discussion, something will be considered as existential to something else when the first conditions the existence or absence of the later.

biodiversity. The maximal set of things possibly impacted was then estimated, and considered very significant. The urgency of the decision was assessed, considerations were shared regarding the ongoing losses of opportunities inherent to the expansion of the universe, and the limits of our finite, accessible environment, were demonstrated ad absurdum, outlining the ultimate possibility of the expansion of life impacting the dynamic of the universe itself, this before strategies for compensating for the losses of opportunities were discussed.

I) PREREQUISITES, II) ARGUMENTATION III) HYPOTHESES, and IV, EVALUATION, having been addressed, we propose in the next section to consider some objections that have been raised along this work.

V) OBJECTIONS

In this section, some objections to the defended thesis are addressed.

The presented thesis, that humans do hold or are close to hold a kingmaker position regarding life as we know it on Earth, and that this situation relates to a decision whose scope is existential to humans, life as we know it, and life as it is not known, while bearing a very important magnitude, admits multiple critics and objections.

This section is trying to address some of these, starting with general consideration regarding A) Flaws in the logic, B). Issues with hypotheses, and C) the choice of exploring the maximal set of impacted elements. In D). Errors and imprecision in the proposed evaluation are addressed, before E) the assumption of a continuous spread is challenged, and defended.

A) Flaws in the logic

When considering flaws in the presented logical path leading to the conclusion of a kingmaker situation, it is proposed that this flaw is not forcefully critical to the conclusion, thanks to the redundancy of the paths as seen on figure 2. Despite our efforts, the presented conditional scheme may be false, implicit hypotheses might have been missed, or some critical element overlooked. Should you spot something similar to this, please kindly send me an email: anormier@gmail.com

B) Issue with hypotheses

When consideration is given to an hypothesis, estimated to be audacious, optimistic, missing or irrealist, a difference has to be made regarding the criticality of the hypothesis, weakness being non conclusive to the argumentation when it is not related to a critical hypothesis (natural access, historical access, boarding, technological civilisation)

C) On the choice of exploring the maximal set of impacted elements

The objection is received that even if we where to send millions of signals and probes a day to interesting places, there is simply no possible conclusion to be made on the happening of the potential impact, because it depends critically of the reached environment: when first order life is reaching exclusively environments where from it may harvest no energy, or when substrate

based life is to reach, let say solely aliens that will never engage in space travel, or never try to decode our signals because they are too busy binge watching netflix : journey ends. This is definitely true, and what is to be clarified is that what we are considering here is not what is going to happen, but the maximal extent of what may happen, and consequently the importance of the scope to consider when deciding about intervening or not on the process of this gateway to the star, in the process of being built. By ultimate limits set by physics, nothing ever is going to be impacted beyond the event horizon. When beholding the capability to directly send out millions of spore bearing sprites to potentially $5e19$ stellar systems, the consideration that nothing might as well happen is not really helpful for taking responsibility. Looking up maximal impact is our only way to take informed decisions.

D) Errors and imprecisions in the proposed evaluation

Objections to the above work may be raised on the basis of the precision of the presented calculations, and regarding the methods used to infer probabilities (ETI, habitability), some from null positive observation, including from very small sets of negative observation. While the best efforts have been made for providing the estimations the most coherent possible with the current scientific paradigm and literature survey, this objection would be missing the reason for which those numbers are provided:

Numbers are proposed here primarily to provide us with elements regarding the magnitude at stake, and allow us to answer the question whether creating a gateway to the stars for life as we know it, is important or not, in comparison to what life has access to, without our involvement.

Calculated from our de-sitter model as within reach as per 20% c breakthrough starhot speed, and given the robust estimation of the frequency of about one planet per star per the current paradigm, we end up with a calculated $5e19$ planets out there, within reach of breakthrough spaceships. When compared with the maximal natural $5e4$ planets accessible via flythrough, (See Annex II, Historical extrasolar access) the difference is of 15 orders of magnitude.

Considering the global hype raised by Elon Musk's projects for colonizing mars, a planet smaller than Earth, out of the habitable zone as defined by liquid water in the Solar System, and the initiated debate for and against the protection of its local potential biodiversity, it is here considered that an increase of one order of magnitude, by the number of planets out there, is enough to justify the question as important.

As a consequence, 14 orders of magnitudes are left to accommodate for uncertainties, approximations and errors regarding the amount of reachable planets, before we may consider our question as unimportant due to errors in numerical evaluations. This being set, our proposition is that according to the a) strong base of literature used for providing our simple estimations, and to b) the overall coherence of estimations regarding life out there

a) Strong base: as developed in *Annex I Solar System* and *Annex IV, Scope* when looking up the construction of the model leading to the proposed evaluations, the qualification of the gravitationally bound structures is confirmed from various agreeing papers, the considered escape speeds, while calculated using large approximations, are found to be coherent with estimations from literature from observations. The amounts of stars at short galactic range are extracted from the direct observations of GAIA DR2¹⁹⁰. At large scales, the geometric de-sitter model, bounded by an approximated constant expansion, is used as a standard reference for later cosmological times, and most of the formulas are derived very simply from peer reviewed papers. As a consequence, the results regarding maximal potentially impacted volumes and amount of stars depending on speed are considered reasonably strong, and realistic within or better than the order of magnitude.

b) Overall coherence of estimations regarding life out there: Estimations, related to the distribution of ET, ETI, or habitable planets, are less reliable. Still, here is proposed that the multiplicity of the considered approaches, to the estimations of the parameters, and the cross coherence between the calculated elements, may minimize the uncertainty, which is nevertheless considered as high. No estimate is provided for this uncertainty, which should be the purpose of future work. The proposed evaluation is to be easily updated with advances in SETI and search of life programs.

As defended in *Annex IV Scope*, a very interesting element with the reflection regarding other forms of life is that the estimations are linked: the amount of possible communicating intelligent form of life is dependant on the amount of life, which is dependant on the amount of habitable planets, all of these being dependant on the characteristics of life, and the survival rate of its interesting, potentially observable properties, regarding which we have a sole example: us in the Solar System. For now, our conclusions and probabilistic approaches are limited to negative

¹⁹⁰ [80] ([Gaia DR2 contents - Gaia - Cosmos](#)) [Access to Gaia database](#)

information: wherever we've looked, we've not found extrasolar life yet. When digging for solutions regarding the estimations of probabilities, I have been surprised by the relevance of SETI(Search for extra-intelligent life) searches regarding any inference on life. When the assumption is made that it is way easier to spot communicating ET, than biomarkers of life out there, a method which is only balbutiating, SETI has indeed searched an incredibly wider environment, leading to the evaluation of the probability of life, to be today possibly better served by assumptions regarding the relative frequencies of life regarding communicating life, and habitable planets, than by its direct search.

E) On the assumption for a continued spread

The question is raised regarding the possibility for life, once seeding a world, to re-engage in interstellar travel, which, beyond reproduction in the arriving ecosystem or substrate, is required for accessing the next resources allowing the potentially envisioned exponential growth and transformative action. In other terms: is the risk the one of our civilisation to soon ideologically engage in seeding massively, from Earth, worlds that are to undertake local exponential transformations, and in this case, there is a link between the amount of probes or signals to be sent, and the resulting impact ? Or is the risk that a single inadvertently contaminated spaceship or signal arriving in a single favorable ecosystem, leads to an autonomous exponential transformation of everything below the event horizon ? Both, simultaneously:

Reevolution to space age, and jump again:

Given a bloom on arrival, from a proper set of microbes to be released at destination, evolution, could be sortcutted by as much as 3-4 billion years¹⁹¹, and provide a space capable civilization within a billion year, itself to re-engage in such a directed panspermia activity, while seeding the space around it through natural exchanges, that might be way more probable there than in our environment (higher density of planets¹⁹² neighbouring stars, collisions, hills mechanism). Given this understanding, a single successfully seeded world, could autonomously restart an entire seeding campaign, and be way more aggressive in this than us.

Infinite seeding:

¹⁹¹ [4] (Gros, 2016) [Developing Ecospheres on Transiently Habitable Planets: The Genesis Project.](#)

¹⁹² [81] (Krijt et al. 2017) [Fast litho-panspermia in the habitable zone of the TRAPPIST-1 system](#)

Given a miniaturized gene lab such as the one proposed in the referenced paper, or a miniaturized hatchery from where to multiply a population of microbial colonizers, and given the endless possibilities offered by solar sail navigation, explored in III)full power, a single probe could virtually seed an infinite number of worlds, the sole limit being the required embarked matter from which to have microbes reproducing, or assembled, and the lifetime of materials. A near term all-out directed panspermia scenario, could pretend to send such an “infinite” seeder probe, to every single of the 200 million galaxies within the reachable horizon at 20%*c*. When a laser launch is considered, the limit factor is the global economic effort, of 10%GWP, (considered limits: cost, energy for launch, total mass of probes)¹⁹³. Given the targeted “smartphone type” mass production of the probes, and the 3 billions of smartphones around right now, 200 million probes seems an achievable task should it be a global or big nation project. 150 years would be required to send all probes due to the economic limit, and no higher hypothesis has been made than the target objectives of Breakthrough Starshot.

Use of existing interstellar networks of a relevant substrate found at destination

Way faster, could be the use of pre existing interstellar network: a biological, or a computer virus collected and flourishing on a would be alien substrate, could gain an incredible access should the discussed ET possess an interstellar network.

The main objections, known to this stage, having been addressed, a discussion is proposed in section V, below regarding the ethical implications of the thesis.

¹⁹³ Using constraints of 0.2C scenario from [9] ([Parkin 2018\) The Breakthrough Starshot system model](#))

VI) DISCUSSION

In this section, some ethical implications of the established kingmaker situation are discussed

Prerequisites (I) have been proposed, the argumentation was detailed (II), along with its underlying hypotheses (III), leading to the evaluation of the possibly impacted environment.(IV) This process led to the establishment of the thesis along which humans do hold or are close to hold a kingmaker position regarding life as we know it on Earth and its possible expansion within the accessible universe, this situation relating to a decision whose scope is existential to humans, life as we know it, and life as it is not known, and having the potential to impact a very large environment. Some objections to this reasoning were then addressed (V)

In VI) Discussion, after precisising in A) Kingmaking the relation the human species may have to its kingmaking position, we propose, in B) Empowerment, to consider that we hold some control, and as such have some responsibility over this situation we now are aware of, arguing in C) Moral imperative, that the existential considerations and magnitude at stake leads to the moral obligation of trying to act in perspective. In D) Cause election, an utilitarian approach is used, to conclude that personal involvement on the question might be worthwhile, the question being tractable, important and widely underassessed. In E) Moral uncertainty, the issue of being incapable of a moral conclusion on the topic is addressed, and a conservative approach is proposed, of a course of action allowing for the minimisation of the potential damage, the time for a moral decision to develop.

A) Kingmaking

For Oxford English Dictionary 2nd edition (1989) a kingmaker is “One who makes or sets up kings”. In game design theory, a kingmaker situation refers to games with a minimum of three players, where one of the players, while unable to win the game, is given the power to decide who is to win the game.

To our analysis, the current situation may be synthesized as a kingmaking scenario where the three players are *life, as we know it* (Known), *life, as we do not know it* (Unknown), and us: *21th century humans*. The game is being played over the “kingdom”¹⁹⁴ of the accessible universe.

¹⁹⁴ (excluding any religious or metaphysical meaning)

Life as we know it on earth, defined as proposed earlier, has little to no natural opportunity reaching out, without the involvement of humans¹⁹⁵ : as investigated, spreading through natural exchanges, if potentially working, is comparatively a very slow process. Right now, there is no other civilisation than us on Earth, to offer the extrasolar access, and should we collapse, the lost opportunities have been calculated¹⁹⁶ and would be horrendous, due to the ongoing expansion. More, the possibility is challenged that a reboot is possible, due to the lack of easy access resources¹⁹⁷. Without our gateway to the stars, life (unknown) is ruling the universe. Conversely, given *life as we know it*, its resistance, its exponential growth, its adaptability, and depending on the existence and nature of its unknown counterpart, we may be providing dominance over the kingdom.

life as we do not know it (Unknown), is here understood as being unknown: to the very extent of its existence. life(unknown), should no life exist out there, might simply be “no life”. Whatever the existence or the nature of this life(unknown), we may choose, either to let it dominate the extrasolar space, and the “kingdom” be the domain of nothing, giant glowing octopuses or whatever you may picture it like, or put its dominance at risk, by opening our technological gateway and release life(Known) out.

21th century humans, striving for power and resources, from the individual level to entire nations, do fantasise they are running this race, as glorified in our fictions, filled from top to bottom with intergalactic empires¹⁹⁸. The thing is, for good or for bad, we are already disqualified for the expansion over space and time: the human identity is built over the concept of species, and as earlier defended in Tool n°4, species shift extremely rapidly with time. Species have their survival suspended to natural risks and to natural evolution. There is no “living fossil”¹⁹⁹ & ²⁰⁰, over billions of years, little doubt is shed: we’ll either go extinct, or evolve, diverge and adapt, possibly beyond possible identification. There is more in our case. First because we do self-produce increased extinction risks such as climate change, nuclear armament, artificial intelligence. Second because we are the engineers of an accelerated evolution, through the

¹⁹⁵ See [hypothesis on natural access](#), and [hypothesis on historical access](#)

¹⁹⁶ See earlier: [cataclysmic setbacks](#)

¹⁹⁷ See earlier: [re-evolution impaired by the lack of resources](#).

¹⁹⁸ Foundation (Asimov), Star wars, Startrek, Dune....

¹⁹⁹ [49] (Casane and Laurenti 2013) [Why coelacanths are not ‘living fossils’](#)

²⁰⁰ [82] (Mathers et al. 2013) [\[...\]...the concept of ‘living fossils’](#)

self modification of the species, possibly itself leading to speciation, through the processes of post-humanism, transhumanism, and genetical engineering.

When we may not win the game, when humans as considered as *the human species*, will most probably have disappeared long before the first interesting moves are showing their results, the creation and the activation of a gateway to the stars, will most probably set the game. When we open the gate, life as we know it on Earth has its chances. When we keep it closed, it has very little. We humans are the kingmakers, for the expansion of life as we know it in the universe.

In relation to this situation, we will advocate that we have some capability to act, and huge responsibilities.

B) Empowerment

At stake, numbers beyond imagination, and nothing less the entire accessible universe, to be impacted not directly by us, humans, but by life as we know it, directly expanding as first order, and/or as higher orders, via the media of unknown life, should it exist.

What has to be outlined here is that we now are in a position similar to the one of the scientists of the early 20th century, unpacking the possibility of nuclear reactions: nothing has happened yet. Nature and History show little examples of what will be played with. Beyond unpacking an emergent possibility, there is another similarity: the potential exponential growth of effects, of the chain reaction itself, with some incertitude on how it will be damped, or fed by, the medium where the experiment takes place.

Just before the atomic bomb concept was put to real life test at los alamos, on July the 16th, 1945, Enrico Fermi accordingly jokingly took bets on “whether the atmosphere will be set on fire” mocking earlier concerns raised by Edward Teller and other physicists that the fission explosion might trigger a runaway fusion and ignite the atmosphere, burning down the entire planet. “The energy liberated was clearly near the upper limit, or in excess of our rather dubious predictions”, would say Emilio Segrè²⁰¹, of the moments following the Trinity test. At least Segrè²⁰², Compton²⁰³ and Fermi (while joking about it), had then in mind that, while theoretically discarded at that time, the ignition was an option to be tested during the test. Not quite the ignition of the atmosphere, but still, off calculated consequences. A few decades only separate

²⁰¹ [44] [\(The bulletin of atomic scientists, 2020\) “In their own words](#)

²⁰² [83] Segre: “I believe that for a moment I thought the explosion might set fire to the atmosphere and thus finish the Earth, even though I knew that this was not possible.”

²⁰³ [84] [\(Achenbach 2015\) The man who feared, rationally, that he'd just destroyed the world](#)

the real life large scale experiment of a technology for which the predictions were “dubious” to the extent that some participants considered it as a possible existential risk. We are just there: the concept of our universal life “bomb” is unpacked, some early calculations are made, and if we do not react, dubious calculations will be put to test.

“The extinction of the human race will come from its inability to EMOTIONALLY comprehend the exponential function.” would later say Teller. Will we make a more responsible risk management, with our kingmaker position, to possibly spread life to the entire Universe ? Or, even worse than the positive decision that was taken as Los Alamos on “dubious” grounds, will we simply “let it happen” not even trying to decide on this ?

Because we’ve anticipated, and because nothing has happened yet, we do have a margin of manoeuvre. Exploring the path to the creation of the gateway, we’ve identified in II) that the conditions we might have an impact on are the development of the technological means (hypothesis on interstellar travel, interstellar signaling, and time capsules), the management of our risk of technological collapse (hypothesis on technological civilisation) along with the governance of the question whether or not to use or not to use the obtained capability, once we have it. The condition on boarding, as the control regarding what may embark onboard time capsules, spaceships or signals, is another lever for action.

With nothing less than five conditions to pull, plus the policy of use to play with, Mankind has six options for influencing the pace at which things go, and their advent. We may act.

Nobody but us may realise nor react. We have realised, and we may act. As such, we are empowered by responsibility.

C) Moral imperative

So we are responsible. Knowing about the reasonable possibility above, having considered the consequences, we understand that our responsible decision has to consider an impressingly important scope.

Considering moral aspects now, it is interesting to think in perspective with the amount of potentially impacted sensibilities. Because we need to somehow identify with the living “things”, bacteria, gloomy aliens, giant worms, and other wild life forms that populate the future and that will be as strange to us as we are strange to amibes after millions of years of diverged evolution, we propose to consider our impact on “equivalent humans”, considering that 70 kg of live biomass for 70 years is an “equivalent human experience”. You’ll object that from the

perspective of sensibilities there is definitely no equivalent between a human and 70kg of bacterium, 70 kg of whale or 70kg of tree. I will propose in return that you are right, but that due the considered temporality, evolution will anyhow transform any live form we take as a reference, into a range of entirely different beings. We need our imagination to run and to do so to identify with something valuable. As egotic as we are, equivalent humans will do way better than metric tons of per unit time.²⁰⁴, or kilogram years of integrated biomass, as expressed by some of the literature envisioning future biomass²⁰⁵. On Earth, with such an analysis, we do have right now 36.000 billion equivalent humans.

Now, when the Solar System, its biomass and habitability are considered as a possible approximation of the average stellar system out there, and using the above evaluations, we end up with the total equivalent human experience to be of $1e41$ ²⁰⁶ lives: should one of us be possibly capable of doing anything about the considered discussion, the equivalent impacted human experience is 10.000 billion global oceans, to 1 imperceptible droplet being your experience of life. Of course, this very frontal approach totally forgets the existence of emergent properties and of higher orders of life on the way, including informational life, (such as potential A-life, ideas, civilisations, cultures...), that have no mass and consequently may not be accounted for with such an approach.

A responsible stance considering the kingmaker position has to envision sensibilities, emotions, 41 orders of magnitude higher than our experience of life, plus whatever might be alive on this when considering it as the possible substrate for higher order life. We as humans have a common responsibility, and the scope is simultaneously existential and important to elements that are important to us, from a moral perspective. Still, should we personally get involved to try and have humans take the best possible course of action ?

D) Cause election

Theorists in cause selection, such as the 80.000 hours, and open philanthropy ecosystem, do rely on an evaluation of causes, funded on tractability, underassessment, and importance. The

²⁰⁴ With $5.50E+14$ kgC total Earth biomass, humans represent 0.02% of the total. Should we evaluate the entire biosphere of Earth in equivalent humans, the population would be 36.000 billion equivalent humans

²⁰⁵ [49] (Mautner 2000) Seeding the Universe with life: Securing Our Cosmological Future

²⁰⁶ Within range at reaccelerated 90%c: habitable systems = $9e19$, system biomass = $1.3e15$ kg, system habitability = $18e9$ yr, equivalent human = 70kg, 70years. To compare with $1e42$ equivalent humans for our galaxy as calculated in [49]

proposed approach is found to be interestingly operational. We'll evaluate our thema against this grid, plus one element: urgency.

Urgency: Before our space civilisation collapses, before a probe is outbound of the Solar System (we have four enroute, thousands processed by 2040 !) to inadvertently (we are only decontaminating where life AS WE KNOW IT, is suspected^{207,208}), malevolently (as the tardigrades on the Moon²⁰⁹, eventually legal²¹⁰) or intentionally (for example with the existing genesis roadmap) seed an extrasolar world, before a signal from us is send to something capable of interpreting it (as we just did with Sonar Calling²¹¹). Here is our urgency to address the question.

Depending on the credit given to the seriousness of those things happening, happening, we might have as little, worse case, as 100 seconds to go²¹².

Importance has largely been explored in IV) EVALUATION and appears not questionable.

Tractability, as envisioned in B)Empowerment, with five levers to pull, plus the use policy, that we may influence through advocacy, is certain.

Underassessment, is a dimension extremely difficult to evaluate, for it requires an exhaustive understanding of who is considering the question as important, and who is trying to do something about it. When looking up to the spheres of interest considering the issue we find four groups of people, by decreasing order of presence:

1) Scientists: envisioning the question as a research thema, scientists, interested in the study of the dynamics of life expanding in the universe, do have for goal and purpose the creation of knowledge. A very important research axis is the quest for the origin of life on Earth, which leads this group to mainly consider the search of life from this perspective. These connect with the question and contribute to the problem via the questions of planetary protection, via the probes they produce and the targets they choose. We indeed launch probes where life could be existing which means: precisely where a poorly decontaminated spacecraft could spread it.

2) Biotists: Groups, ideologists, and even scientists, who do propose that it is the purpose of humans to support the colonisation of the Universe by life, or even that it is the ultimate

²⁰⁷ [85] (The International Planetary Protection...2019)

²⁰⁸ With a degrading trend, the Moon protection status has just been degraded by NASA, from class 2 to 1, and Mars being reviewed for allowing humans on it.

²⁰⁹ [86] (Taylor 2019) "I'm the first Space Pirate!" "We didn't tell them we were putting life in this thing"

²¹⁰ [87] (de Gouyon Matignon 2019) Tardigrades on the Moon and space legal issues

²¹¹ [56] (SONAR CALLING, 2020)

²¹² [69] (The bulletin of atomic scientists, 2020) Doomsday Clock

responsibility or purpose of us to do so. It being to safeguard life, (Biotists), or so as to permit a universal flourishing of life (Panbiotists)²¹³

3) Humanists: Groups pushing for the human interstellar spread, considering life from an instrumental perspective. humans being heterotrophs (2nd order), life is a requirement to build a suitable ecosystem on the targeted planets, this reasoning leading some to conclude that autotroph humans (turing us to 1st order life) would be very handy for space colonisation, something which could be technologically achieved through the artificial production of food from non-organic matter. Others, making it simpler, advocate that releasing life, would provide us with a purpose²¹⁴

4) Utilitarians of all kinds: Such as hedonists utilitarians, humanists utilitarians, Meti-ists (People who want to connect with ET, for the ultimate utility of connecting with ET), or more, which all end up with the conclusion that whatever the considered utility: “Connection”, “Hope”, “bliss”, and other “Happiness”, things are always better when these go universal for a simple reason : there is more of it !

Looking up this inventory, it appears that the positioning of scientists is observational (while contributing to the issue), and that the positioning of the others is political: we should spread life, if not for itself, at least for us, or for our ultimate values.

No opposing stance is encountered. When the sole players in a field are observers and actors pushing in a unique direction for metaphysical considerations (their perception of what is good), the question might be raised whether the alternative (we should not, we should wait, we should let it be by natural exchanges...), are given sufficient assessment and consideration.

As such, our understanding is that alternative thesis to the one of positively seeding life, are widely underassessed, leading to the question itself not being formulated, of our position as kingmakers: we either do it, or no. the options of positively deciding not to, to try to prevent, to try to delay, are not being considered at all.

Worth getting involved

As the possibly most **important** decision mankind will ever take, it being largely **tractable**, while **critically urgent** and **underassess** apart from the sides pushing for it, the critical matter of allowing an universal bloom, or to save the universe from life as we know it ,might consequently be considered as valuable cause for **getting involved**

²¹³ [49] [\(Mautner 2000\) Seeding the Universe with life: Securing Our Cosmological Future](#)

²¹⁴ [49] [\(Mautner 2000\) Seeding the Universe with life: Securing Our Cosmological Future](#)

E) Moral uncertainty

So according to this development, it would be reasonable, if we can, to get involved. But an immediate issue arises, which is the one of moral uncertainty. There is no clear side to take. At the individual level this is a real issue. At the species level, it is equally critical, for this is very demotivating. Our proposition here is to address this question from a conservative stance:

First, we have to admit that we have absolutely no idea whether what is happening is good, or bad.

Second, we're not even sure that good and bad are workable concepts for assessing the possibilities of a universe we represent so little within. Indeed, those representations could well be exclusively relevant to us (should these be, which is also uncertain...)

Third, nor are we affirmative about the normative ethics to elect or develop.

Fourth, ethics change with time. Just in case you are indifferent, or already have a strong position regarding spreading life at universal scales, you have to account that you might be wrong, that your ideas might change, and that your kids might end up looking at you like we do look at nazis. As examples, of themes with shifting moral status: pedophilia, eugenism, colonisation, slavery, antropophagy, euthanasia.

Last but not least, is the existence of ET. When ET exists, the impacted life is potentially $1e41$ equivalent human lives, of "pre-existing" impacted ET, while when we're alone, the potential existence of the $1e41$ equivalent humans is created by the onset of the provided access. There is a huge difference: should ET not exist, we do create the problem, at least regarding 1st order life. Incertitude regarding ET, adds to the overall moral uncertainty.

For those reasons, we have to cope with both possibilities: whether it's being wise, or not, to allow life out. For this analysis, the concept and numerical evaluations of opportunity losses due risk and expansion are used, as developed earlier in *IV*): *compensating for the loss of opportunity*.

Should letting life expand not be a wise thing to do

Then expanding now would mean a 100% loss of opportunity

Then waiting a little and not expanding before having decided to not expand is not a loss of opportunity

Then In the case of loss of technological capability within that timeframe whatever gets in our position hundreds to billions years later or so may decide to expand, in which case, the loss of opportunity is related to the time for reboot, the longer the time, the lesser the opportunity loss. On a reboot requiring 3.5 billion years of evolution, the loss be about 50% of the spatial access, due to expansion, to our analysis.²¹⁵ When reboot is impossible, no opportunity is lost.

Then if we realise that letting life expand would have been wise, a ridiculous loss of opportunity of a millionth of a percent per waited century has happened, and no harm is made.

Should letting life expand be a wise thing to do

Then expanding now would mean no loss of opportunity at all.

Then waiting a little before deciding would be a ridiculous loss of opportunity of a millionth of a percent per century, and no harm is made.

Then in the case of an existential setback within that time frame, this time the longer the reboot, the higher the loss in opportunities. the loss of opportunity would be about 50% of the spatial access, should a reboot take about 3.5 billion years.

Then if we realise that letting life expand was indeed unwise, the release cannot be cancelled, and the loss of opportunity is of almost 100% (minus a millionth of a percent per century before this is realised)

A conservative approach accounting for moral uncertainty

According to these views, it appears that

1. Letting life expand now is a bet, while waiting is conservative
2. Due to the impossibility to control life in the extrasolar environment, (hypothesis on irreversibility), letting life expand is irreversible, while waiting can simply be reversed
3. The effect of waiting to decide is a small loss of opportunity, of a millionth of a percent per century, due expansion, as long as the survival of the technological civilisation is guaranteed.
4. Minimising the risk of a cataclysmic setback is conservative as it allows to preempt the transfer of decisional power to a rebooted civilisation, which could then be less cautious than us

If the assumption is made that a cataclysmic setback within the timeframe required for building a decision is more probably from an anthropic origin than from a natural one, for example due

²¹⁵ See [Compensating for the loss of opportunity](#)

climate change, the development of a rogue artificial intelligence or the initiation of an all-out nuclear war, then the assumption may be made that it is an indication of the incapability of life as we know it, to have a sustainable development in general, hence also in space. Considering this: when during the time for building up the decision, a collapse happens, we might want this collapse to be as deep as possible. First, with the hope that a longer, different evolution may lead to some different, possibly more sustainable, life dynamics before it gets back to possible interstellar access. Second, because when the rebooted life evolves to be not wiser than us, a deeper collapse minimises its access and possible damage out there. This leads to :

Should a cataclysmic setback happen for anthropic reasons, we might want it as deep as possible, so as to maximise chances of a better restart

This being identified, a strategy we propose regarding the release of life, to the extrasolar environment, is proposed as a conclusion, after the below synthesis:

VII) SYNTHESIS

In this section, a synthesis is proposed of the entire analysis.

This work has developed the idea along which humans are building a gateway to the stars, for life as we know it on earth, and as such, are now, or soon, in a kingmaker situation regarding the advent of life in outer space. The decision at the center of this situation is existential to humans, life as we know it, and life as we do not know it, and has the potential to impact a very large set of elements, including the matter content and expansion rate of the accessible universe. The discussed scope is spanning over a volume of potentially impacted elements, 29 orders of magnitude bigger than our solar system. A decisional window being existent, it is considered that time is given, to build up an informed moral decision. In the meantime, opportunities might be saved by a conservative stance.

Gateway to the stars

Historically, life as we know it has had negligible opportunities of impacting anything out of the Solar System. Through technological development, humans are opening a gateway to the extrasolar environment. This door is opening along our century, a split second as per astronomical scales, but a long time to us, impairing our understanding of what is at stake.

The maximal impacted universe, when considering the technological targets of currently financed, going-on programs such as Breakthrough Starshot, is beyond imagination. This, even when the given targets are missed by multiple orders of magnitude, and when errors in estimation are large. Our species is about to possibly release lifeforms, or life-related elements, to a space of opportunities thousands of billions of billions times bigger ($1e29$) than what it historically had access to: energy, matter to be transformed, potential for species, biospheres, sensibilities, hopes, risks, bliss, suffering, death... Considering orders of magnitude, the discussed increase in opportunities is the highest possible ever, due to the physical limitations of the event horizon. More, should the thirst for energy not be satisfiable, and growth be sustained by all means, the eventual significant conversion of mass to energy is possibly precipitating the causal separation of the accessible universe, via a faster evaporation of the masses gravitationally holding things together.

The mechanics to the creation of the decisional power are resilient thanks to the multiplicity of possible paths to the acquisition of the extrasolar capability, and critical hypotheses are unlikely

to be deceived. Single failures of hypotheses may be sustained, and in some cases, even double failures. The issue stands as long as our technological capability survives, hence potential large delays in technological progress are not critical to the reasoning, some of the paths, the ones using time capsules, being already active.

The largest modifier regarding possible impact is the hypothesis of the existence of other forms of life, but it is a double sided knife. Unexistence of extrasolar life makes our decision critical to universal bloom, conversion and accelerated causal separation. Existence makes our decision critical via the substrate provided by preexisting life, allowing possibly the direct spread of elements related to life as we know it on earth, at a higher speed and for a lower energetical cost, when considering informational life-related elements, such as codes or ideas, traveling at lightspeed on electromagnetic signals. While the existence of extraterrestrial life forms would partially relieve us of responsibility regarding an astronomical bloom (it happens without us), the criticality stays regarding the possible transformation of the existing extraterrestrial life through interaction with earth originated lifeforms or life-related elements. In the hypothesis where life on earth is not alone, responsibility towards the risk of modified causal separation of the accessible universe is maintained, as is the risk of impacting a large amount of individual experiences.

The kingmakers dilemma

The advent of extrasolar access of life as we know it on earth is dependent on conditions humans may choose to have an impact on. We may act upon the development of technological means, we may act regarding the management of our risk of technological collapse, and we may decide to tackle the governance of the question whether or not to use or not to use the obtained capability, once we have it. Last but not least, should the capability be achieved, we may attempt to control what may embark onboard time capsules, spaceships or signals. Humans are this century in the position to decide, or decide not to decide, to accelerate, forbid, delay, or just let happen, the extrasolar advent of life as we know it on Earth.

This decision is irreversible, for humans cannot pretend to be close to control evolution. Just as on Earth, within a few million years, evolution could lead on any seeded world, to the uncontrolled advent of species engaging in further expansion in space. It is a one way path.

This decision further beholds multiple existential aspects. Indeed, when life as we know it on Earth is alone in its class, existence may be prolonged by expansion in space, reducing the risk

of eradication following cataclysmic events, by the multiplication of biospheres. Also, it is reasonable to assume that the expansion of life as we know it on Earth, may represent an existential threat to some of the extrasolar biodiversity, should it exist²¹⁶. Then, the decision embodies an existential risk for the universe itself, within the event horizon, whose mass could be evaporated faster as a consequence of life-related mass to energy conversion, leading to an earlier thermal death. Back to our scales, to us humans, the extrasolar activity sheds an existential risk, not only via the possible triggering of an aggressive action from extrasolar life, should it exist, but also via the creation of extrasolar life itself, should it not exist, which, on the long run, being uncontrolled, could preempt resources or become aggressive.

With nothing less than an irreversible decision to take regarding the existence and magnitude of the future of life as we know it on earth, itself impacting the potential extrasolar biodiversity and pace of evaporation of the universe, we are here facing a decision with extremely high moral implications. The thing is: while the astronomical magnitude may be estimated, as demonstrated, the moral evaluation is for the least, uncertain, and worse, likely to shift along time, should a moral certainty ever be reached.

Decisional window

The timeframe for decision making is counted. Indeed while the progressive loss of opportunity due to the expansion of the universe is slow and may be partly compensated, a first temporal limit is that the decision must happen before lifeforms or life-related elements are released without decision-making, which is precisely what is going to happen in the decades or centuries to come if no control is exerted. The second time limit is given by the risk of human civilisational collapse or extinction, which on top of removing the decisional power from the hands of humans, could entail from the perspective of life as we know it on Earth, the temporary or definitive disparition of the gateway itself, depending of the magnitude of the setback, and taking into account that we we may have already burnt on Earth the easy access resources (fossil fuels, minerals...) required to get back to interstellar capability.²¹⁷

²¹⁶ Just as invasive species in a garden...

²¹⁷ [88] (Dartnell 2015) *Out of the ashes, in Aeon*. interestingly, Lewis Dartnell, astrophysicist, is the author of “*The knowledge, how to rebuild our world after an apocalypse*”, and happens to also be an advisor to the [Arch Mission Foundation](#)

We have time: let's study morals, keep options, save opportunities.

So as to buy time to build an informed and morally valid decision, the idea is submitted to enact an immediate enforced moratorium on funding and use of extrasolar capability, with the exclusion of the exclusive purpose of mitigating existential risks for humans, the time for the global governance to operate, and for the moral discussion to reach an agreement. This moratorium would be specifically targeting METI (Messaging to Extraterrestrial Intelligence), directed panspermia, and time capsules beyond 5 billion years of survivability.

So as to minimise the risk of total loss of opportunity for life as we know it on Earth, independently of our survival, or of a catastrophic setback, the solution is proposed to intentionally preserve a depot of intermediate resources and knowledge, so as to allow for possible capacity rebuilt given a catastrophic setback.

VIII) CONCLUSION & RECOMMANDATIONS

This section is presenting our conclusions, recommendations, and proposes a path to action.

Deciding upon the extrasolar access of life as we know it, might be the most important decision ever, for us as a species. Five classes of decision have been identified: accelerate, forbid, delay, let happen, take no decision. Let happen is underlined because it is our current track. Once we've released life out there, we won't trap it back. In our kingmaker position, we have a limited time to decide, and possibly elect a non-return path. Nothing less than life itself, known and unknown, the universe within the event horizon, its mass content and its dynamics, are possibly at stake, not excluding the question of the involved existential risks for us humans.

The window for deciding is narrow and could close out of luck as soon as in 100 seconds from now²¹⁸ with a cataclysmic setback as anticipated by the Bulletin of Atomic Scientists, or as soon as twenty years ahead, if we are to believe the Breakthrough Starshot calendar. This while the consequences lie up to billions of years and light-years away, 90% of which we will never possibly be aware of. This is an extreme challenge for advocacy.

Given the scope, and now that we are aware of its existential aspects and astronomical magnitude, we cannot escape the responsibility of assessing the issue, which is encompassed within the broader concept of having, as a species, a responsible impact beyond space and time.

As the only possible conclusion to this work, I propose to initiate here a broader effort to advocate a **responsible astronomical reach for mankind**, implying, that outer space and celestial bodies are non derogatory regarding the need for:

1. A strategy of long term thinking and sustainable decision making.²¹⁹
2. The attribution of a proper value²²⁰ to non-human objects and lifeforms, including to potential extraterrestrial lifeforms and biospheres.
3. The respect of the sensations and emotions potentially experienced by lifeforms, including potential extraterrestrial lifeforms and biospheres.

²¹⁸[69] ([The bulletin of atomic scientists, 2020](#))

²¹⁹ Is sustainable, something "able to be maintained at a certain rate or level". In the context of this discussion, are considered sustainable, processes that do not impair their own existence: decision making inducing existential risks for the decision maker, or what is critical to him is unsustainable.

²²⁰ See Glossary, [Value \(instrumental or proper\)](#)

4. A global governance of all subjects with potential existential²²¹ consequences regarding the human species, life as we know it, Earth biodiversity and biosphere, potential extraterrestrial biodiversity and biospheres.
5. The application of the precautionary principle for subjects with potential existential consequences regarding the above entities, and considering the uncertainties in the pursued ethics.

RECOMMENDATION

So as to address the moral issue, and provide contradictory insight on the problem of the access of life to the extrasolar environment, we advocate the creation of an **International Panel on Life Access to Extrasolar Scales** (name to refine) whose primary tasks will be by all means, to advocate, sponsor and organise:

- A global governance of the question.
- A global empowerment of philosophers with this question.
- The promotion of a sustainable vision of space

So as to prevent the potentially harmful interference, and build the time required for an informed, collaborative and responsible decision process to happen:

- In accordance with the advice of Billingham and Benford,²²² We advocate an absolute moratorium on METI until an international consensus is reached.
- We advocate an absolute moratorium on extrasolar missions, until international consensus is reached, excluding missions conceived to a very limited extent and for the sole purpose of mitigating existential threats to life.
- We advocate the exhaustive monitoring of the observance of the given moratoriums, and their enforcement.

To the advocated ethical panel, beyond the primary goal which has to be the ethical evaluation of our kingmaker position, and the coordination of a global effort in this perspective, we propose the below:

²²¹ See Glossary, [Existential](#)

²²² [89] ([Billingham and Benford 2011](#)) [Costs and Difficulties of Large-Scale 'Messaging'](#),...

With the purpose of reducing existential risks: organise a global communication about the urge to address problems here on Earth, participating to the reduction of the anthropic risks by making it clearer to the public opinion that space expansion will not save mankind.

For the purpose of an improved policy control: consider the entire reworking of the planetary protection measures, beyond their current instrumental exclusivity regarding the protection of the research of the origin of life, to encompass a perspective integrating the intrinsic value of life, sensibilities, and extrasolar potential biospheres.

For the purpose of the preservation of opportunities, while the ethical decision is being constructed : consider the evaluation of the pertinence of strictly controlled expansion, so to maintain the probability of extinction or existencial setback/century, for life as we know it, to an acceptable level. Investigate the intelligence and ethics of dead man's switch activated directed panspermia projects, that could be a lifeboat for life as we know it, in case of cataclysmic setback. Investigate directed panspermia to the kuiper belt. Consider the evaluation of an opportunity mission to the collapsing central part of virgo supercluster, with the purpose of an increased opportunity range for life as we know it, by 2 to 3 orders of magnitude, before causal separation happens with it. Consider the advocacy of a programmed migration of life to follow the habitable zone of Earth. Consider the evaluation of the possibility of seed systems associated with chosen hypervelocity stars, as a solution for intergalactic travel.

For the purpose of compensating opportunity loss due to the universe expansion while building up a decision, consider the advocacy of a minimal research effort to maintain an average of spaceships speed increase per year of $\pm 10e-9\%$, and as such maintain the entire opportunities for causation slower than C.

For the purpose of not spoiling ressources, consider the advocacy of a redirection of ressources working on interstellar travel, to work on the ethics of the extrasolar reach of life, and to the mitigation of existential risks on Earth.

For the purpose of building up an informed ethical view, investigate the hypothesis along which the outer space, celestial bodies, and potentially existing biosphere, may, from a deontological standpoint, have a proper value, and that existing non-human sensibilities of all kinds should possibly be respected.

Note 1) To researchers from the SETI community: if not already the case, the search for ETI, primarily in the intersection between the galactic plane and the ecliptic plane of the Solar

System might be of added value, due to those potential locations being more likely to spot us via atmospheric biomarkers detected via transits.

Note 2) To sustain this advocacy: websites are developed: <https://www.stopmeti.org/>, and www.banseeding.org whose content is under development.

Note 3) As a support for outreach regarding the discussed concepts: a board game has been developed: *Existence: life & the Universe*

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